

**The Use of Wearable Technology and Digital Health
Platforms to Enable Remote Monitoring of Physical
Activity and Health.**

Nicola Kayleigh Thomson

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of
the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

October 2024

Abstract

Physical inactivity is a major risk factor for premature death and non-communicable diseases (NCDs). Participating in regular physical activity (PA) and reducing time spent in sedentary behaviour supports mental and physical health. Measurements of population PA are essential for understanding the influence of PA on NCD. Therefore, the overarching aim of this PhD was to determine validity and user experience of wearable technology to measure step count, energy expenditure (EE), heart rate and PA intensity.

Twenty healthy adult men and women took part in the experimental trial study in chapter 4. Participants wore an iPhone 5S and GT3X+ in a waist-mounted pouch during bouts of treadmill walking, jogging, and other physical activities in the laboratory. Step counts were manually counted (MC), and EE was measured using indirect calorimetry (IC). During two weeks of free living, participants (n = 17) continuously wore a GT3X+ attached to their waist and were provided with an iPhone 5S to use as they would their own phone. The data showed that the iPhone accurately estimated step count during laboratory walking but recorded significantly lower daily steps compared with the GT3X+ during free living. In the next chapter, a mixed-methods study explored the use of participants' own iPhone in estimating PA during free living compared to another iPhone and GT3X+ worn continuously on the waist. Results showed that the user's own iPhone recorded significantly fewer steps than both devices attached to the waist. The usability of a novel digital health platform (DHP) was established in chapter 6 (study 3). A sample of healthy adults and health care professionals (HCPs) were recruited for this qualitative study. The data showed that both cohorts believed the DHP had the potential to be implemented within the NHS. Lastly, in chapter 7, the change in PA behaviours prior-to, during and post-COVID-19 lockdown was investigated with a mixed-methods approach in a sample

of healthy adults. Data showed that PA and mental health was negatively affected by the lockdown, however, PA increased a month into lockdown, but not to pre-COVID-19 levels.

The results of this PhD expand the knowledge of PA monitoring using mHealth technologies in both laboratory and free-living settings, provides “proof of concept” of a novel DHP and confirms previous findings of a reduction in PA at the commencement of the COVID-19 lockdown.

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	II
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	IX
DECLARATION	X
LIST OF FIGURES	XI
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	XIV
FOREWORD	XVI
CHAPTER 1: GENERAL INTRODUCTION	1
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	6
2.1 CHAPTER OVERVIEW	7
2.2 PA, SB AND HEALTH	7
2.2.1 Health benefits of PA	7
2.2.2 Sedentary behaviour	10
2.2.3 PA guidelines and prevalence	13
2.3 MEASUREMENT OF ADULT PA	16
2.3.1 Overview	16
2.3.2 Accelerometry	17
2.3.3 Consumer wearable devices	23
2.3.3.1 Consumer activity trackers	26
2.3.3.2 Smartphone apps	33
2.4 DIGITAL AND MOBILE HEALTH	35
2.4.1 Remote monitoring of health	39
2.5 STUDY AIMS AND OBJECTIVES	40
2.5.1 Study 1 (chapter 4)	40
2.5.2 Study 2 (chapter 5)	41
2.5.3 Study 3 (chapter 6)	41
2.5.4 Study 4 (chapter 7)	41
CHAPTER 3: GENERAL METHODOLOGIES	43

3.1 OVERVIEW	44
3.2 ETHICS	44
3.3 CONTRIBUTIONS	44
3.3.1 <i>Study 1 (chapter 4)</i>	44
3.3.2 <i>Study 2 (chapter 5)</i>	45
3.3.3 <i>Study 3 (chapter 6)</i>	46
3.3.4 <i>Study 4 (chapter 7)</i>	46
3.4 MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES	47
3.4.1 <i>Anthropometric measurements</i>	47
3.4.2 <i>Step count and EE</i>	47
3.4.3 <i>iPhone 5S</i>	47
3.4.4 <i>GT3X+</i>	48
3.5 MIXED METHODS	49
3.6 QUALITATIVE DATA	49
3.7 QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS	50
3.8 DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS	52
3.9 CHAPTER 6 PLANNED PROGRESSION	52
CHAPTER 4: STUDY 1 - VALIDITY OF THE IPHONE M7 MOTION COPROCESSOR TO ESTIMATE PA DURING STRUCTURED AND FREE-LIVING ACTIVITIES IN HEALTHY ADULTS	54
4.1 INTRODUCTION	55
4.2 METHODS	56
4.2.1 <i>Study design</i>	56
4.2.2 <i>Phase 1: Laboratory</i>	57
4.2.2.1 <i>Participants</i>	57
4.2.2.2 <i>Procedures</i>	57
4.2.2.3 <i>Data analysis</i>	60
4.2.3 <i>Phase 2: Free living</i>	61
4.2.3.1 <i>Participants</i>	61
4.2.3.2 <i>Experimental design and procedures</i>	61
4.2.3.3 <i>Data analysis</i>	62

4.3 RESULTS	62
4.3.1 Phase 1: Laboratory.....	62
4.3.1.1 Treadmill walking, jogging and running.....	62
4.3.1.2 Cycling and aerobics	68
4.3.2 Phase 2: Free living.....	69
4.4 DISCUSSION	71
4.5 CONCLUSION	74
CHAPTER 5: STUDY 2 - A MIXED-METHODS STUDY TO EXPLORE THE USE OF SMARTPHONES IN ESTIMATING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY DURING FREE LIVING	76
5.1 INTRODUCTION	77
5.2 METHODS	80
5.2.1 Participants	80
5.2.2 Procedures	80
5.2.3 Instruments.....	82
5.2.4 Data Processing.....	82
5.2.5 Interviews	83
5.2.6 Data Analysis	83
5.3 RESULTS	84
5.3.1 Wear-time and step count.....	84
5.3.2 Interviews	89
5.3.2.1 PA monitoring.....	89
5.3.2.2 PA.....	92
5.3.2.3 Wearing devices	93
5.4 DISCUSSION	95
CHAPTER 6: STUDY 3 - EVALUATION OF A DHP: THE USABILITY AND FEASIBILITY OF THE LENUS HEALTH PLATFORM WITHIN HEALTHY ADULTS AND HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS.	100
6.1 FUNDING AND COLLABORATION	101
6.2 INTRODUCTION	101
6.3 METHODS	103

6.3.1 <i>Research design</i>	103
6.3.1.1 Part 1- ‘Mock patients’	104
6.3.1.1.1 Procedures	104
6.3.1.1.2 Data collection.....	108
6.3.1.2 Part 2 – HCPs.....	108
6.4 RESULTS	111
6.4.1 <i>Part 1 – Mock patients</i>	111
6.4.1.1 Data collection and sharing.....	112
6.4.1.2 Usability of the Lenus HealthPlatform’s apps	114
6.4.1.3 Recommendations	116
6.4.1.4 Impact on the NHS.....	119
6.4.2 <i>Part 2 – HCPs</i>	120
6.4.2.1 Implementation of the Lenus Health Platform within the NHS.....	120
6.4.2.2 Usability of the Lenus Health Platform.....	125
6.4.2.3 Technology.....	126
6.4.2.4 Recommendations	128
6.5 DISCUSSION	131
CHAPTER 7: STUDY 4 - FITBIT MEASURED PHYSICAL ACTIVITY DECREASED UPON COMMENCEMENT OF UK COVID-19 LOCKDOWN	137
7.1 INTRODUCTION	138
7.2 METHODS	140
7.2.1 <i>Participants</i>	140
7.2.2 <i>Procedures</i>	140
7.2.3 <i>Interviews</i>	141
7.2.4 <i>Data processing and analysis</i>	142
7.3 RESULTS	142
7.3.1 <i>Wear-time</i>	142
7.3.2 <i>METs</i>	143
7.3.3 <i>EE</i>	144
7.3.4 <i>Step count</i>	144
7.3.5 <i>HR</i>	144

7.3.6 Interviews	148
7.3.6.1 PA monitoring	149
7.3.6.2 PA before Lockdown	150
7.3.6.3 PA during Lockdown	151
7.3.6.4 PA after Lockdown	156
7.4 DISCUSSION	161
CHAPTER 8: GENERAL DISCUSSION.....	168
8.1 INTRODUCTION	169
8.2 SUMMARY OF MAIN FINDINGS.....	169
8.2.1 Study 1 (Chapter 4) – <i>Validity of the iPhone M7 Motion Coprocessor to Estimate PA during Structured and Free-Living Activities in Healthy Adults</i>	169
8.2.2 Study 2 (Chapter 5) – <i>A Mixed-Methods Study to Explore the Use of Smartphones in Estimating Physical Activity during Free Living</i>	171
8.2.3 Study 3 (Chapter 6) – <i>Evaluation of a DHP: The Usability and Feasibility of the Lenus Health Platform Within Healthy Adults and Healthcare Professionals</i>	172
8.2.4 Study 4 (Chapter 7) – <i>Fitbit Measured Physical Activity Decreased upon Commencement of UK COVID-19 Lockdown</i>	174
8.3 THE IPHONE AS A PA MEASUREMENT TOOL	175
8.4 THE EFFECT OF COVID-19 LOCKDOWNS ON PA	177
8.5 STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS	178
8.6 SIGNIFICANCE.....	181
8.7 FUTURE DIRECTIONS.....	182
8.8 OVERALL CONCLUSIONS.....	184
REFERENCES.....	186
APPENDICES	225

Acknowledgments

Firstly, I would like to thank my lead supervisor, Professor Chris Easton. Chris, you have been incredibly patient with me over the years and always made me feel like this was something I could achieve, even when I didn't believe it myself. You encouraged me to keep going when personal life circumstances got in the way, and for that I will be forever grateful. My second supervisor, Dr Eilidh Macrae, your guidance and support particularly during the final push of writing-up my thesis has really been so appreciated – thank you. I would also like to thank Dr Beverley Young, for your advice and assistance when I needed it most.

I couldn't have done this without the unconditional love and support of my wonderful husband, Robert. You have been there with me every step of the way, cheering me on and reminding me that I could do it. You honestly must be sick of hearing about my PhD, but I know you are so proud of me. You have been my rock through this and your unwavering belief in me is something I will never forget.

Last but certainly not least, I thank my baby girl, Penelope. I hope that one day you are proud of me and go on to do great things knowing your Mummy achieved this.

Declaration

The work in this thesis is the sole work of the candidate. This work has not previously been submitted for award at any other institution. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the thesis contains no material previously published by another person except where due reference is made in the thesis itself.

List of Figures

FIGURE 2-1: ILLUSTRATION OF HOW THE DIFFERENT MOVEMENT-BASED TERMINOLOGY FIT TOGETHER AROUND A 24-HOUR PERIOD. THE INNER RING SHOWS THE MAIN CATEGORIES OF BEHAVIOUR USING EE. THE OUTER RING SHOWS POSTURAL CATEGORIES. THE PROPORTIONS ARE NOT INDICATIVE OF HOW MUCH TIME SHOULD BE SPENT IN EACH BEHAVIOUR (TREMBLAY *ET AL.*, 2017)¹. REPRINTED UNDER THE TERMS OF THE CREATIVE COMMONS ATTRIBUTION 4.0 INTERNATIONAL LICENSE ([HTTPS://CREATIVECOMMONS.ORG/LICENSES/BY/4.0/](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).
.....11

FIGURE 2-2: ILLUSTRATION OF HOW DIGITAL LITERACY AND ACCESS RELATE TO THE DOMAINS OF SOCIAL DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH (SIECK *ET AL.*, 2021). REPRINTED UNDER THE TERMS OF THE CREATIVE COMMONS ATTRIBUTION 4.0 INTERNATIONAL LICENSE ([HTTPS://CREATIVECOMMONS.ORG/LICENSES/BY/4.0/](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).
.....38

FIGURE 4-1: BLAND AND ALTMAN PLOTS OF IPHONE AND GT3X+ STEPS VERSUS MANUALLY COUNTED (MC) STEPS DURING A LABORATORY-BASED TREADMILL TRIAL AT LIGHT, MODERATE AND VIGOROUS INTENSITIES WITH MEAN BIAS (SOLID LINE) AND 95% LIMITS OF AGREEMENT (DASHED LINES): (A) IPHONE; (B) GT3X+
.....64

FIGURE 4-2: BLAND AND ALTMAN PLOTS OF IPHONE AND GT3X+ ESTIMATED EE VERSUS MEASURED EE (IC) DURING A LABORATORY-BASED TREADMILL TRIAL INCLUDING LIGHT, MODERATE AND VIGOROUS INTENSITIES WITH MEAN BIAS (SOLID LINE) AND 95% LIMITS OF AGREEMENT (DASHED LINES): (A) IPHONE; (B) GT3X+
.....66

FIGURE 4-3: BLAND AND ALTMAN PLOT OF DAILY IPHONE STEPS VERSUS DAILY GT3X+ STEPS DURING A FREE LIVING STUDY WITH MEAN BIAS (SOLID LINE) AND 95% LIMITS OF AGREEMENT (DASHED LINES).
.....70

FIGURE 5-1: FRONT VIEW OF THE IPHONE AND GT3X+ WORN AROUND THE WAIST IN A NEOPRENE POUCH.82

FIGURE 5-2: MEAN (SD) DAILY STEP COUNT OF GT3X+, PARTICIPANTS' PERSONAL IPHONE AND WAIST-WORN IPHONE (WAIST IPHONE). * DENOTES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE BETWEEN INSTRUMENTS.
.....86

FIGURE 5-3: BLAND AND ALTMAN PLOTS OF: (A) PARTICIPANTS' PERSONAL IPHONE AND WAIST-WORN IPHONE (WAIST IPHONE) DAILY STEP COUNT; (B) WAIST IPHONE AND GT3X+ DAILY STEP COUNT AND (C) PERSONAL IPHONE AND GT3X+ DAILY STEP COUNT DURING A 7-DAY FREE LIVING PERIOD WITH MEAN BIAS (SOLID LINE) AND 95% LIMITS OF AGREEMENT (DASHED LINES).
.....87

FIGURE 5-4: DAILY STEP COUNT OF GT3X+, PARTICIPANTS' PERSONAL IPHONE AND WAIST-WORN IPHONE (WAIST IPHONE) FOR TWO INDIVIDUAL PARTICIPANTS: (A) PARTICIPANT 14 (B) PARTICIPANT 7. FOR PARTICIPANT 14 (A), WEAR-TIME OF THE GT3X+, PERSONAL IPHONE AND WAIST IPHONE WAS 13, 8 AND 15 HOURS·DAY⁻¹ RESPECTIVELY. FOR PARTICIPANT 7 (B), WEAR-TIME OF THE GT3X+, PERSONAL IPHONE AND WAIST IPHONE WAS 15, 14 AND 15 HOURS·DAY⁻¹ RESPECTIVELY.
.....88

FIGURE 6-1: SCREENSHOTS OF THE LENUS HEALTH PLATFORM’S ASSOCIATED APPS (A) BP APP, (B) BC APP AND (C) PEDOMETER APP.....107

FIGURE 6-2: SCREENSHOT OF THE LENUS HEALTH PLATFORM.....110

FIGURE 7-1: AVERAGE TOTAL DAILY MINUTES IN LIGHT (1.6 - 2.9 METs), MVPA (>3 METs) ACROSS A FULL WEEK THE ‘YEAR BEFORE’, ‘MONTH BEFORE’, ‘START’ AND ‘MONTH IN’ OF THE COVID-19 LOCKDOWN. * DENOTES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE FROM ‘START’, \$ DENOTES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE FROM ‘MONTH IN’.145

FIGURE 7-2: BOX AND WHISKERS PLOT OF TOTAL DAILY EE ACROSS A FULL WEEK THE ‘YEAR BEFORE’, ‘MONTH BEFORE’, ‘START’ AND ‘MONTH IN’ OF THE COVID-19 LOCKDOWN. EACH BOX REPRESENTS THE INTERQUARTILE RANGE, EXTENDING FROM THE 25TH TO THE 75TH PERCENTILE OF EACH GROUP’S DISTRIBUTION OF VALUES. THE LINE INSIDE EACH BOX REPRESENTS THE MEDIAN AND THE + REPRESENTS THE MEAN. THE WHISKERS REPRESENT THE MINIMUM AND MAXIMUM VALUES. * DENOTES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE FROM ‘START’, \$ DENOTES STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE FROM ‘MONTH IN’.146

FIGURE 7-3: BOX AND WHISKERS PLOT OF TOTAL DAILY STEP COUNT ACROSS A FULL WEEK THE ‘YEAR BEFORE’, ‘MONTH BEFORE’, ‘START’ AND ‘MONTH IN’ OF THE COVID-19 LOCKDOWN. EACH BOX REPRESENTS THE INTERQUARTILE RANGE, EXTENDING FROM THE 25TH TO THE 75TH PERCENTILE OF EACH GROUP’S DISTRIBUTION OF VALUES. THE LINE INSIDE EACH BOX REPRESENTS THE MEDIAN AND THE + REPRESENTS THE MEAN. THE WHISKERS REPRESENT THE MINIMUM AND MAXIMUM VALUES.147

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 4-1: MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATIONS FOR IPHONE, GT3X+ AND MANUALLY COUNTED (MC) STEPS DURING TREADMILL WALKING AND JOGGING AT LIGHT, MODERATE AND VIGOROUS INTENSITIES.	63
TABLE 4-2: COMPARISON OF IPHONE AND MANUALLY COUNTED (MC) STEP COUNT, AND GT3X+ AND MC STEP COUNT DURING TREADMILL WALKING AND JOGGING AT LIGHT, MODERATE AND VIGOROUS INTENSITIES.	65
TABLE 4-3: MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATIONS FOR IPHONE, GT3X+ AND IC ENERGY EXPENDITURE DURING TREADMILL WALKING AND JOGGING AT LIGHT, MODERATE AND VIGOROUS INTENSITIES.	67
TABLE 4-4: COMPARISON OF ENERGY EXPENDITURE MEASUREMENTS BETWEEN THE IPHONE AND IC, AND GT3X+ AND IC DURING TREADMILL WALKING AND JOGGING AT LIGHT, MODERATE AND VIGOROUS INTENSITIES. ..	68
TABLE 5-1: PERSONAL IPHONE USED BY PARTICIPANTS.	80
TABLE 5-2: THEMES AND SUB-THEMES FROM THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF TWELVE QUALITATIVE INTERVIEWS.	89
TABLE 5-3: WEARABLES AND SMARTPHONE APPLICATIONS PREVIOUSLY USED BY PARTICIPANTS.	90
TABLE 6-1: THEMES AND SUB-THEMES FROM THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF ‘MOCK PATIENT’ INTERVIEWS.	111
TABLE 6-3: THEMES AND SUB-THEMES FROM THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF HCP INTERVIEWS.	120
TABLE 6-4: HCP RECOMMENDED ADDITIONAL MEASUREMENTS FOR THE LENUS HEALTH PLATFORM.	129
TABLE 7-1: DATES FOR EACH WEEK OF DATA.	141
TABLE 7-2: AVERAGE VALID WEAR MINUTES ACROSS FOUR WEEKS: THE ‘YEAR BEFORE’, ‘MONTH BEFORE’, ‘START’ AND ‘MONTH IN’ TO THE COVID-19 LOCKDOWN. ONE FULL DAY = 1440 MINUTES.	143
TABLE 7-3: THEMES AND SUB-THEMES FROM THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF ELEVEN QUALITATIVE INTERVIEWS.	148
TABLE 7-4: MODELS OF FITBIT USED BY PARTICIPANTS.	149
TABLE 7-5: WEARABLES AND SMARTPHONE APPS PREVIOUSLY USED BY PARTICIPANTS.	150

List of Abbreviations

AC	Activity Counts
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
App	Application
BC	Body composition
BM	Body mass
BMI	Body mass index
BP	Blood pressure
CCC	Concordance correlation coefficient of Lin
CI	Confidence interval
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease
DHP	Digital health platform
EE	Energy expenditure
ENMO	Euclidian norm minus one
GPS	Global positioning system
HCP	Healthcare professional
HR	Heart rate
HRR	Heart rate reserve
IC	Indirect calorimetry
LOA	Limits of agreement
MAPE	Mean absolute percentage error
MC	Manually counted
MET	metabolic equivalent of task
MHR	Maximal heart rate
MPE	Mean percentage error
MVPA	Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity
NCD	Non-communicable disease
NHS	National health service
PA	Physical activity
ProPASS	the Prospective PA, Sitting, and Sleep consortium

RHR	Resting heart rate
RPE	Rate of perceived exertion
SB	Sedentary behaviour
VILPA	Vigorous intermittent lifestyle physical activity
VVPA	Very vigorous physical activity
WHO	World health organisation

Foreword

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a major alteration to this PhD. Study 4 (chapter 7) of this PhD should have been a follow-on study from study 3. The intended framework for the PhD was to, first, determine the validity of mobile devices to remotely measure physical activity and clinical outcomes (studies 1 and 2). Secondly, to explore patient and clinician user experience of a novel digital health platform – initially using mock patient data (study 3) and subsequently within an NHS secondary care environment. All planned research was completed prior to the NHS capstone study, however, NHS ethical approval to commence data collection was granted in February 2020. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was not possible to complete this study and instead I had to pivot to an entirely different research question for the final study of my PhD. While the final study is still firmly aligned with the overarching objectives of my PhD research, it was important to provide this context to the reader to clarify what had originally been intended.

CHAPTER 1: General Introduction

Physical inactivity is a leading risk factor for premature mortality and non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as cardiovascular disease (CVD), chronic respiratory disease, diabetes and cancer (Lee et al., 2012). While NCDs are generally considered to primarily affect the elderly, 9 million deaths worldwide in 2019 were people below the age of 60 (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network, 2020). NCDs, or chronic diseases as they are otherwise known, are long-term conditions that arise owing to genetic, environmental, lifestyle, and physiological influences. Although changing one's DNA is not possible, lifestyle modifications can prevent the onset of such diseases. Cessation of smoking, reduction of alcohol ingestion, and consumption of a healthy and balanced diet are three actionable ways to reduce the risk of dying from NCDs (Scarborough *et al.*, 2011). The fourth factor is the overarching theme of this PhD thesis, physical activity (PA). In 2019, low PA accounted for over 800,000 deaths globally and almost 11,000 deaths in the United Kingdom (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network, 2020). On the other hand, participating in regular PA and limiting sedentary behaviour (SB) supports mental and physical health, at all ages. The World Health Organisation (WHO) recommends adults perform 150-300 minutes of moderate-intensity or 75-150 minutes of vigorous-intensity PA, as well as muscle-strengthening activities on two or more days per week. They reported that doing more PA is associated with further health benefits; however, they begin to level off at higher levels and that *some* PA is better than *none* (Arem et al., 2015; Ekelund et al., 2019; Ding et al., 2020).

Measurements of population PA are essential for understanding the influence of PA on NCD. Therefore, validated PA questionnaires have been developed (Craig *et al.*, 2003; Bull, Maslin and Armstrong, 2009), enabling the surveillance and inter-country comparison of PA levels. This, in turn, enables policymakers to put programmes in place with the intention of increasing PA, thereby decreasing the risk of NCD. While using a questionnaire is inexpensive and easy

to administer to large populations, it relies solely on an individual's ability to accurately recollect their past PA habits. Unfortunately, this type of subjective self-reporting has been shown to lack validity and reliability (Sallis and Saelens, 2000; Troiano et al., 2008; Helmerhorst et al., 2012), with researchers suggesting that PA questionnaires should only be used as an adjunct to objective methods. Accelerometers are used to measure and monitor free living PA objectively and are often used in large-scale population studies (Troiano et al., 2008; Schuna, Johnson and Tudor-Locke, 2013; Doherty et al., 2017). Accelerometers are small, unobtrusive devices that are worn on the body and provide accurate estimations of the intensity, frequency, and duration of PA (Aadland and Ylvisåker, 2015; Lee *et al.*, 2015). However, to obtain meaningful data, most researchers adopt a minimum accelerometer wear-time of > 10 hours/day for at least four days/week (Troiano et al., 2008). Although this is methodologically sound, it can be burdensome for study participants (O'Brien *et al.*, 2017), thereby reducing compliance (Troiano et al., 2014). Furthermore, the large number of accelerometers required for population PA surveillance can be expensive and requires the safe return of the devices. Finally, expert knowledge is necessary to analyse the output data, which lack real-world transferability.

Consumer-grade and accelerometer-based PA trackers are growing in popularity with brands such as Fitbit (Fitbit, San Francisco, CA, USA), Apple (Apple Inc., Cupertino, CA, USA), and Garmin (Garmin International, Kansas City, MO, USA) leading the way. This relatively new phenomenon of self-tracking via wearable technology and smartphone applications (apps) is big business, with Fitbit bringing in \$1.2 billion, selling over 10 million devices and having 111 million registered users in 2021 (Statista, 2023a). Devices such as Fitbit come in the form of a watch and measure PA using an in-built accelerometer. Some Fitbit models also contain a photoplethysmography optical sensor that enables heart rate (HR) measurement. Another

device that the vast majority of the UK's population already owns (Taylor and Silver, 2019), which has the potential to continuously measure and display PA data, is a smartphone. Similar to PA trackers, most smartphones contain an integrated accelerometer, providing the user with estimates of step count and distance travelled. The benefit of utilising the smartphone as a PA tracker is that third-party apps using bespoke algorithms can be downloaded, allowing for the estimation of variables, such as energy expenditure (EE). Additionally, internet-based platforms enable users to upload and store their smartphone-measured PA data, which can then be accessed remotely by a third-party. Adopting smartphones in research allows for the continuous collection of PA data to be viewed and downloaded remotely by researchers. Furthermore, this type of widespread and consistently collected PA data enables prospective and retrospective investigation of PA behaviours.

Remote monitoring is not limited to just PA data alone. With the emergence of digital health platforms (DHPs), patients can monitor their health and wellbeing using mobile technology and integrated mobile apps. For example, patients can measure their blood pressure (BP) at home with a Bluetooth-enabled BP monitor linked to a mobile app. Their BP readings can then be uploaded from the mobile app to an internet-based DHP, allowing both patients and healthcare professionals (HCPs) to view and monitor the data. This type of telemonitoring healthcare can reduce the demand and burden on healthcare systems, such as the National Health Service (NHS) (Shah *et al.*, 2021), while improving the patient experience (Walkden, McCullagh and Kernohan, 2019). The recent Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic substantiated the necessity of remote monitoring of healthcare (Majeed, Maile and Bindman, 2020), as GP surgeries suddenly had to drastically reduce the number of patients seen face-to-face. However, further research is required to assess the validity and reliability of mHealth

technology, as well as the usability of DHPs as essential medical resources from both patient and healthcare provider perspectives, before their widespread implementation.

This thesis adopts a mixed-methods approach to expand the evidence on the importance of accurately measuring and monitoring free living PA. The focus of this PhD was to explore the validity and use of smartphones and PA trackers in the measurement of PA, the use of a DHP in remote monitoring of PA and health, and to investigate the changes in PA prior to, during, and after a national lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

This PhD was funded by the Digital Health & Care Innovation Centre (DHI) and conducted in collaboration with Lenus Health (Lenus Health Ltd, UK), a UK-based software engineering company formerly part of Storm ID (Storm ID Ltd, UK). The primary objective of Lenus Health was to evaluate the usability of their Lenus Health Platform and associated mobile apps within a cohort of secondary care patients. Before this aim could be pursued, it was necessary to validate their proposed method for measuring PA, namely step count estimated via iPhone. Accordingly, study 1 assessed the validity of the iPhone for step count estimation. Findings from this study raised questions regarding the influence of user wear-time behaviour on measurement accuracy, which became the focus of study 2. The objective of study 3 was to conduct a pilot trial assessing the usability of the Lenus Health Platform in a cohort of healthy adults acting as proxies for secondary care patients. This was intended to be followed by the same study within an NHS secondary care cohort; however, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted this progression. Consequently, study 4 was adapted to be conducted remotely.

CHAPTER 2: Literature Review

2.1 Chapter overview

The literature pertinent to this thesis will be critically reviewed and presented in this chapter as follows. Firstly, an overview of the health benefits derived from PA, the recommended guidelines for PA and prevalence of PA will be provided. Secondly, literature regarding measuring PA with the use of accelerometers, wearable PA trackers and smartphone apps will be deliberated. Lastly, monitoring health remotely with the use of digital and mobile health will be discussed. Following the discussion of the relevant literature, the study aims and objectives of the sequential chapters will be presented.

2.2 PA, SB and health

2.2.1 Health benefits of PA

PA is defined as *‘any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that results in EE’* (Caspersen, Powell and Christenson, 1985). Exercise, a term often used interchangeably with PA, is a subcategory of PA and is defined as *‘physical activity that is planned, structured, repetitive, and purposive in the sense that improvement or maintenance of one or more components of physical fitness is an objective’* (Caspersen, Powell and Christenson, 1985). Throughout the various forms of leisure-time, occupational, and movement activities there is a continuum of EE rates - often grouped into categories of intensity. PA intensity can be conveyed as an absolute measure, such as HR or metabolic equivalent of tasks (METs), or as a relative measure, such as a percentage of maximal HR. Additionally, there are rate of perceived exertion (RPE) scales, such as the Borg RPE scale (Noble *et al.*, 1983; Borg, 1998), which are based on the relationship between perceived exertion and exercise intensity.

1 MET (3.5ml oxygen uptake/kg/min) is assumed to be resting EE (Norton, Norton and Sadgrove, 2010). Subsequently, PA of 1.6 – 2.9 METs is regularly defined as light and does not cause an obvious change in breathing rate. PA of 3-5.9 METs is usually defined as moderate; this intensity of PA results in a slight increase in HR and breathing rate, while the participant can still maintain a conversation. PA of ≥ 6 METs is defined as vigorous, which results in a greater increase in HR and the inability to converse.

Vigorous-intensity PA can be a time-efficient way to exercise and can exert positive effects on health and reduce all-cause mortality (Samitz, Egger and Zwahlen, 2011; Gebel *et al.*, 2015; Rey Lopez *et al.*, 2019) achieved at shorter bouts. However, participation rates in these types of structured exercises at vigorous intensity (such as high-intensity interval training) are low (Rey Lopez *et al.*, 2019) as they are not always practicable or attractive to middle-aged adults (Hoare *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, vigorous intermittent lifestyle PA (VILPA) (Stamatakis *et al.*, 2021), a type of brief movement pattern that occurs at random in everyday life – for example running for a bus or walking upstairs, can also have a profound effect on health. A recent study found a reduction in mortality risk of 22% - 28% by accumulating 3.4 – 4.1 minutes of VILPA per day, compared to not doing any VILPA (Stamatakis *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, small amounts of very vigorous PA (VVPA), with an EE of ≥ 8 METs, have been shown to improve HR variability (Fornias *et al.*, 2019) – a measure of cardiovascular health. However, the benefits plateaued at approximately 21 min/week of VVPA, suggesting no additional benefits beyond this dose. On the other hand, there are studies suggesting that too much ($> 60 - 90$ minutes per session) VVPA can have harmful effects on cardiovascular health (Lavie, O’Keefe and Sallis, 2015). However, a recent systematic review and meta-analysis

found that PA amounts as high as seven times the recommended PA guidelines, did not increase mortality risk, and that 10 – 12 hours of vigorous PA per week is not detrimental to longevity (Blond *et al.*, 2020).

Participation in regular PA has long since been credited with substantial health benefits, such as reducing the risk of premature mortality, heart failure, breast cancer, colon cancer, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and CVD (Hupin *et al.*, 2015; Pandey *et al.*, 2015; Kyu *et al.*, 2016). Conversely, physical inactivity is the cause of 9%, or more than 5 million premature deaths worldwide (Lee *et al.*, 2012). CVDs, relating to disorders of the heart and blood vessels, are the world's leading cause of mortality with more than 17 million people dying of the disease in 2019 (World Health Organization, 2020a). Regular PA has been shown to be effective in preventing and improving the symptoms of depression and anxiety (Singh *et al.*, 2023; Schuch *et al.*, 2018; Mammen and Faulkner, 2013; Rebar *et al.*, 2015), treating obesity (Hill and Wyatt, 2005) and reducing the risk of developing obesity (Jakicic and Otto, 2005; Hill and Wyatt, 2005). This is significant, as obesity can lead to the chronic diseases previously mentioned. Interestingly, a recent systematic review found that participation in PA at higher intensities elicited greater health benefits, particularly in relation to waist circumference and body mass index (BMI) (Brady *et al.*, 2022).

Lastly, increasing PA is not only beneficial for the individual but can also increase productivity and reduce mortality of working-age individuals, potentially leading to large economic gains (Hafner *et al.*, 2020). It is predicted that nearly 500 million new cases of NCDs worldwide will ensue between 2020 and 2030 owing to physical inactivity. If the current physical inactivity prevalence does not change, this will incur treatment costs of around US\$ 300 billion, or INT\$

524 billion, with high-income countries encountering the majority of this economic cost (World Health Organization, 2022).

2.2.2 Sedentary behaviour

SB is defined as ‘any waking behaviour characterised by an EE \leq 1.5 METs, while in a sitting, reclining or lying posture’ (Tremblay *et al.*, 2017). It was previously thought to reflect the lower end of the PA continuum; however, it is now recognised as a distinct construct independent of a lack of PA. Figure 2-1 demonstrates how the different movement behaviours fit together across a 24-hour period.

Figure 2-1: Illustration of how the different movement-based terminology fit together around a 24-hour period. The inner ring shows the main categories of behaviour using EE. The outer ring shows postural categories. The proportions are not indicative of how much time should be spent in each behaviour (Tremblay *et al.*, 2017)¹. Reprinted under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Owing to the amount of evidence suggesting a link between SB and adverse health outcomes, there has been significant growth in research investigating SB and sedentary time over the last decade. SB has been associated with metabolic dysfunction, including reduced high-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels, reduced insulin sensitivity, and increased plasma triglyceride levels (Yanagibori *et al.*, 1998; Tremblay *et al.*, 2010; van der Berg *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, high levels of SB have been associated with poorer cognitive function, depression, and reduced physical health-related quality of life (Saunders *et al.*, 2020).

After five days of bed rest (23.5 hours per day), Hamburg *et al.*, (2007) found that healthy participants' developed dyslipidaemia, insulin resistance, increased BP, and microvascular dysfunction. A large-scale population study also found that accelerometer-measured sedentary time, independent of PA, was adversely associated with numerous cardiometabolic and inflammatory risk biomarkers, such as increased levels of C-reactive protein, an inflammatory marker linked with an increased risk of CVD (Healy *et al.*, 2011). However, interruptions in sedentary time were beneficially associated with cardiometabolic health, particularly waist circumference (Healy *et al.*, 2011). They also theorised that a reduction in sedentary time of just 1-2 hours per day could have an extensive influence on CVD prevention.

A recent meta-analysis assessed the influence of time spent in SB on stroke risk and discovered a non-linear association (Wang *et al.*, 2022). They observed no significant difference in the risk of stroke at a sedentary time of <3.7 hours per day, however, every further hour after 6.5 hours per day resulted in a 6% increase. At >11 hours of sedentary time per day, the risk of stroke increased by 21%. Similarly, Pandey *et al.*, (2016) conducted a meta-analysis and observed a non-linear association between sedentary time and CVD risk, with an elevated risk

only at >10 hours per day. Furthermore, a recent systematic review and harmonised meta-analysis discovered that spending >9.5 hours per day in SB results in a significantly higher risk of death (Ekelund et al., 2019).

Interestingly, a recent study investigated whether participation in high moderate-to-vigorous PA (MVPA) levels, as measured by accelerometers, modified the effects of SB on cardiometabolic health. The highly active adult participants exceeded the current PA guidelines by spending 60 – 126 minutes per day undertaking MVPA; however, they also spent 7 – 13 hours per day partaking in SB. There was no difference in cardiometabolic health markers (for example, BP, total cholesterol, and insulin sensitivity) among the three groups with low, intermediate, and high levels of SB. The high sedentary group (mean sedentary time of 695 ± 37 minutes per day) still achieved 60 minutes of MVPA per day, suggesting that this amount of MVPA attenuates the negative effects of prolonged SB (Franssen *et al.*, 2023). Even more encouragingly, a recent meta-analysis found that just 30 – 40 minutes of MVPA per day was enough to mitigate the harmful association between time spent in SB and premature mortality (Ekelund *et al.*, 2020). These data are encouraging as in the modern Western world, spending long times in SB can be unavoidable due to sedentary occupations and motorised methods of transport.

2.2.3 PA guidelines and prevalence

Physical inactivity is defined as not meeting the global or country-specific recommended PA guidelines and is one of the world's leading risk factors for mortality (Blair, 2009; Lee et al., 2012). The WHO 2010 global PA recommendations for adults were to obtain at least 150

minutes of moderate-intensity or at least 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic PA throughout the week or an equivalent amount of MVPA activity, performed in bouts of at least 10 minutes. They also recommended that for additional health benefits, adults should increase their moderate- and vigorous-intensity aerobic PA to 300 or 150 minutes per week, respectively, or an equivalent amount of MVPA. Muscle-strengthening activities involving major muscle groups were also recommended for 2 or more days per week (World Health Organization, 2010). In 2016, more than a quarter of adults (27.5%) worldwide did not meet the WHO 2010 aerobic PA recommendations, with women being less active than men (31.7% vs. 23.4%) (Guthold *et al.*, 2018).

In 2020, the WHO updated their global PA guidelines (World Health Organization, 2020b), removing the requirement of PA to be performed in bouts of at least 10 minutes because of the amount of research evidencing improved health outcomes and reduction of all-cause mortality at any bout duration (Jakicic *et al.*, 2019). They also now provide a target range for aerobic activity, 150-300 minutes of moderate-intensity or 75-150 minutes of vigorous-intensity. Additionally, the 2020 guidelines state that adults should limit SB and that doing *some* PA is better than *none*.

The most recent UK PA guidelines for adults released in 2019 are almost identical to the WHO 2020 guidelines. The only difference is that there is no range for moderate or vigorous PA, simply stating that adults should accrue at least 150 minutes of moderate PA or 75 minutes of vigorous PA (Chief Medical Officers, 2019). In 2022, 35% of Scottish adults did not meet the UK PA guidelines for MVPA, with men being more likely to meet them than women (70% vs. 60%, respectively). Only 28% of adults followed the combined MVPA and muscle-

strengthening guidelines. Again, men were more likely to adhere to both guidelines than women (32% vs. 25%, respectively). It was also found that where you live plays an important role in meeting the PA guidelines, with only 57% of those living in the most deprived areas meeting the MVPA guidelines, compared to 73% in the least deprived areas (Scottish Government, 2022). However, these findings were gathered as part of the Scottish Health Survey (Scottish Government, 2022), where participants were asked questions based on the Allied Dunbar National Fitness Survey, a large-scale study conducted in 1990 on PA among adults in England (Activity and Health Research, 1992). As a result, relying on self-reported PA may have introduced some measurement error.

Owing to the preponderance of evidence of the health benefits of PA, the WHO released a new *Global Action Plan on PA (GAPPA)* in 2018, with the aim of reducing global physical inactivity levels in adults by 15% by 2030 (World Health Organization, 2018). The report included policies to get more people walking and cycling as a mode of transport, and to increase participation in sports, subsequently aiding in bringing communities together. Such policies also can also prevent and manage NCDs, consequently lessening the economic and general burden on the national health systems. In October 2022, the WHO released a *Global Status Report on PA*, stating that there had been little progress towards the GAPPA goal, describing it as ‘slow and uneven’ (World Health Organization, 2022). Within the report, they proposed five actions that could help close the policy-employment gap and thereby improve progress. These actions include strengthening political and government ownership and leadership, integrating PA into applicable policies and assisting implementation with guidance and tools, reinforcing partnerships and involving communities, strengthening monitoring and data systems to track progress, and gaining funding and supporting national policy obligations. It is

projected that these five actions will accelerate the implementation of PA policies, which is fundamental for achieving the GAPP target set for 2030.

Regular and reliable updates on worldwide levels of PA are required to inform progress towards the principle GAPP aim of increasing PA by 15% by 2030. To gather such global data on PA levels, surveys are typically utilised; however, in recent years, research into the measurement of PA with the use of technology has emerged. Wearable devices and smartphones have potential advantages in PA tracking; however, a global consensus is required for their use in global and national monitoring.

2.3 Measurement of adult PA

2.3.1 Overview

The many benefits of PA and the adverse effects of SB have been clearly demonstrated by research. However, the challenge of accurately and reliably measuring PA in research and achieving the research objective can be a hindrance. There are several PA measurement tools, all of which have their strengths and weaknesses. There are subjective methods, such as self-report questionnaires (Craig *et al.*, 2003; Bull, Maslin and Armstrong, 2009), which are commonly used in large-scale studies due to their low cost and ease of administration, however they are prone to recall and response bias (Prince *et al.*, 2008; Sallis and Saelens, 2000). In contrast, objective methods such as using research-grade accelerometers provide detailed and continuous data on movement and have been used in many large-scale epidemiological studies because of their validity (Troiano *et al.*, 2008; Schuna, Johnson and Tudor-Locke, 2013;

Doherty et al., 2017). Although accelerometers are small and can be easily provided to participants for the duration of a research study (Doherty *et al.*, 2017), they are not as useful when the investigation of PA levels warrants retrospection. In such instances, commercially available PA tracking wearables, such as a Fitbit, can be used. These Fitbit devices are worn on the wrist, and PA is measured using a tri-axial accelerometer as well as a HR sensor if the model is HR-enabled. Fitbit proprietary algorithms are used to provide an estimation of several variables: step count; EE; active minutes; steps climbed; distance travelled; and sleep duration/sleep 'score'. Consumer adoption of such PA-tracking wearables, as well as their utilisation in research, has increased exponentially in recent years (Ferreira *et al.*, 2021). Another method for measuring PA involves the use of smartphones. Most newer smartphones, such as iPhones, contain a motion coprocessor that uses data from an in-built accelerometer, global positioning system (GPS), gyroscope, and barometer to estimate, for example, step count, distance travelled, and flights of stairs climbed. This data can be viewed via the 'Health' app which comes pre-installed on iPhones or through a third-party app which can be downloaded from the App Store, also allowing for extra functionality. The ubiquitous nature of smartphones permits population-based PA measurement without the need to supply an accelerometer to participants and subsequently relying upon the safe return of the device. Smartphones also allow for the simple remote sharing of data via apps and online cloud-based platforms. In sections 2.3.2 - 2.3.3.2, the validity and reliability of each PA measurement method is discussed, as well as the strengths and limitations of the use of each method in population level research.

2.3.2 Accelerometry

The method of counting steps to measure ambulatory PA started in the mid-1900s using wearable mechanical pedometers that measured motion in the vertical plane (Stunkard, 1960). The first electronic pedometer, named “manpo-kei”, meaning “10,000 steps meter” was developed in Japan. The popular target of 10,000 steps/day is said to have come from Japanese walking clubs and a business slogan from ~50 years ago (Tudor-Locke and Bassett, 2004; Kang *et al.*, 2009). Pedometers are readily used in PA promotion as they are inexpensive and provide users with instant feedback in the form of steps per day (Hodkinson *et al.*, 2019). However, pedometers are limited to merely measuring steps and, therefore, do not provide a wider reflection of daily PA (Freedson and Miller, 2000).

On the other hand, an accelerometer is a similar wearable device that measures acceleration and allows for unprecedented insights into intensity, frequency, amount and duration of PA (Troiano *et al.*, 2014). In addition, accelerometers can capture nearly complete accounts of human movements, including activity type and postural classification (Skotte *et al.*, 2014). Accelerometers have been used in numerous large population studies to investigate measured PA and future health risks (Troiano *et al.*, 2008; O’Donovan *et al.*, 2013; Doherty *et al.*, 2017; Strain *et al.*, 2020). Another benefit of using a wearable device such as an accelerometer is that it can capture VILPA, a type of brief movement pattern that occurs at random in everyday life, such as running for a bus or chasing after a toddler. As mentioned previously, VILPA has been shown to be effective in reducing overall mortality risk (Stamatakis *et al.*, 2022); however, it is probable that this type of PA would be less likely to be recalled accurately within qualitative methods of data collection, such as questionnaires or interviews. One significant downside of the accelerometer is that it does not provide the user with feedback, instead requiring specialist software and expert knowledge to download, analyse, and interpret the data.

ActiGraph (Pensacola, FL, USA) accelerometers are the most prevalent accelerometers in research studies, appearing in 51% of published adult accelerometer-based studies before 2015 (Wijndaele *et al.*, 2015) and 46.4% before 2019 (Evenson *et al.*, 2022). The raw acceleration signal from an ActiGraph accelerometer is processed to produce the output of ‘activity counts’ (AC). AC are generated based on several specifications, such as sampling frequency, epoch length (time interval), and proprietary signal-filtering algorithms. With the use of validation methods such as indirect calorimetry (IC), regression equation models can be developed, which allow for the prediction of EE and for AC-derived ‘cut-points’ to be defined. Subsequently, the amount and intensity of PA, EE, SB, and sleep can be obtained from the AC. Epidemiologic studies most commonly utilise the method of cut-points to evaluate and categorise free living PA. However, one issue with using accelerometers to measure PA is that the numerous researcher-developed cut-points and algorithms are specific to the selected data-collection and data-processing criteria. Furthermore, older accelerometer models are typically uni-lateral, measuring only the acceleration in the vertical plane, similar to the pedometer. However, newer tri-axial models measure acceleration in three axes: vertical (Y), medio-lateral (X), and antero-posterior (Z). Subsequently, cut-points developed for uni-lateral accelerometers cannot be used interchangeably with tri-axial accelerometers. Similarly, cut-points vary depending on the specific accelerometer model used and the age of the participants recruited in the study that developed the cut-points. For example, cut-points developed with older adult participants can technically be used to investigate adolescent PA, however, the results will likely be flawed.

There are numerous established cut-points, although research suggests that estimates of PA intensity can vary widely depending on the cut-points utilised (Migueles *et al.*, 2019). Another

complication of measuring PA with an accelerometer is the amount of variation between research analysis protocols, such as the length of epochs, sampling frequency used, differing bout durations, and studies failing to report all criteria, making it difficult for comparisons and to draw conclusions (Migueles et al., 2017; Brady et al., 2022). Another challenge associated with using accelerometers to estimate PA is the array of exclusion/inclusion criteria used to determine whether participants' data will be included in the analyses. This is critical, as different PA estimates arise from different wear-time and non-wear criteria (Brady *et al.*, 2022).

In 2009, ActiGraph released the GT3X, a triaxial accelerometer that provides access to the raw acceleration signal. Recently, several studies have estimated PA from this raw acceleration signal, expressed as a gravitational equivalent referred to as the Euclidian norm minus one (ENMO) (Hildebrand *et al.*, 2014; Fairclough *et al.*, 2016; Bammann *et al.*, 2021). However, there is a requirement for a consensus on how to evaluate the validity of data collection/processing methods and emerging technologies owing to their rapid and relentless proliferation. A review of accelerometer methods in youth PA studies from 2005 to 2010 resulted in 6 different epoch lengths and non-wear definitions, 13 different valid day definitions, 8 different thresholds for the minimum number of wear days, 12 different moderate-intensity PA cut-points, and 11 different SB cut-points (Cain *et al.*, 2013). Several research groups have recently proposed frameworks and collaborative research platforms for evaluating accelerometers (Montoye, Moore, *et al.*, 2018; Keadle *et al.*, 2019; Stamatakis *et al.*, 2020). Keadle *et al.*, (2019) developed a phase-based framework that utilises the raw acceleration signal. The phases progress from mechanical testing in a controlled and artificial setting to assess the reliability of the device output, to a realistic validation in real-world environments. They ultimately believe that a processing method or device must have been

compared with a criterion measure in a free-living environment before it can be considered validated for use in a study.

One area of enthusiastic debate regarding the use of accelerometers is their placement on the body, with the purpose of maximising feasibility as well as the range and depth of data. The placement in which the accelerometer is worn on the body can affect the validity of accelerometers in measuring PA. Initially, studies adopted accelerometer placement at the hip, secured with an elastic belt (Troiano *et al.*, 2008); however, this placement interfered with clothing and sleep, subsequently deeming it suitable only for waking hours. More recently, studies using wrist placement have been increasing, with the accelerometer attached to the wrist on a watch-like strap, as there is evidence to suggest that wear-time compliance is greater with wrist placement (Liu, Wanigatunga and Schrack, 2021). A recent scoping review found that between 1999 and 2019, 48.4% of observational studies of adults utilised hip placement of an accelerometer, compared to 22.3% with wrist placement (Evenson *et al.*, 2022). A recent systematic review summarised that a simple wrist-watch-like placement of accelerometers is associated with higher participant wear-time because it is less burdensome (Pulsford *et al.*, 2023). In contrast, a recent systematic review found that similar compliance can be achieved for both hip and wrist placements in adults (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). However, the same systematic review found that hip placement resulted in more accurate estimates of EE, SB time, and PA intensity classification (Migueles *et al.*, 2017). A laboratory-based study comparing raw acceleration outputs from accelerometers worn concurrently on the hip and wrist found that, in some participants, the output from the wrist monitor was 200% higher than that from the hip monitor (Hildebrand *et al.*, 2014).

Another emerging placement location for accelerometers is the thigh (Stamatakis *et al.*, 2020). The accelerometer is usually taped to the front of the thigh and can be worn continuously under clothing for several days (Dall *et al.*, 2018; Hartley *et al.*, 2018). The benefit of this placement location is its ability to measure postural SB. The activPAL3 (PAL Technologies Limited, Glasgow, UK) is a tri-axial accelerometer that delivers a gold standard measure of postural SB when worn on the thigh, accurately determining sitting/lying and upright postures (Sellers *et al.*, 2016). This allows for an accurate distinction between SB and PA. A key benefit of thigh placement is that a continuous 24-hour assessment is feasible. This allows for the monitoring of a complete 24-hour activity cycle, with the potential for integrated public health guidance for sleep, SB, light-intensity PA, and MVPA (Rosenberger *et al.*, 2019). A research group has created a research collaboration platform called: the Prospective PA, Sitting, and Sleep consortium (ProPASS). With ProPASS, they aim to collate future and existing observational studies of thigh-worn accelerometry and to produce evidence on how long-term health outcomes and longevity are associated with sleep, sitting, and PA (Stamatakis *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, standardised protocols are being developed for the collection of accelerometry and health outcome data (Stevens *et al.*, 2020).

Future work is required to process and harmonise raw accelerometer data across device placement location, data collection/processing protocols, and device brands. Harmonisation of retrospective and prospective individual participant data is particularly useful as it can overcome heterogeneity, a prominent obstacle in evidence synthesis (Ioannidis, 2017). In addition, because PA and health are fundamentally connected, harmonisation of data across large-scale epidemiological studies would facilitate PA-based health research and therefore refine and improve public health recommendations, as well as intervention efforts. Furthermore, validation of activity-type classification and posture methods with more

representative samples in free-living conditions are required to advance the understanding of the utility of these novel methods in research, as they have substantial potential for progressing PA science (Liu, Wanigatunga and Schrack, 2021). Finally, although the standardisation of accelerometer study protocols has the potential to advance the comparability of study findings, it is imperative that this does not discourage researchers from investigating novel approaches to analysing accelerometer data that could potentially advance the field.

2.3.3 Consumer wearable devices

‘Consumer wearable devices’ is a term covering any device worn on the person that is available for purchase to the general public, including both activity monitors (usually in the form of a wristwatch) and smartphones, and provides the user with feedback on their PA (Strain et al., 2022a). These devices nearly always use an accelerometer sensor to detect movement, however they can also include barometers, gyroscopes, optical sensors (photoplethysmography) and GPS to enhance the inference of PA levels or provide supplementary PA metrics. These devices have enabled convenient, accessible and automated PA tracking with the elimination of recall bias. To differentiate between the two types of PA consumer wearable devices, in this literature review they will be referred to as ‘consumer activity trackers’ and ‘smartphones’.

Most consumer activity trackers come in the form of a wristwatch but also include armbands, rings, pendants and other accessories, and store PA data prior to sharing to linked apps on devices such as smartphones, computers and tablets via Bluetooth connectivity. When data are shared with these devices, the user can then review their PA log and potentially make PA

behaviour changes towards a healthier lifestyle based on this feedback. Most smartphones today come with a preinstalled app for tracking PA although third-party apps can also be downloaded onto the phone to track PA. Research investigating these consumer wearable devices is linked to various labels, such as mobile health (mHealth) (Lupton, 2013) and Quantified Self (Swan, 2013). Exploring the research potential of extending the ‘quantified self’ concept, where individuals track their own biological, physical, behavioural and environmental data – to the collaborative sharing of consumer wearable device data in PA surveillance is highly appealing.

However, in a recent commentary, Strain et al., (2022a) discussed four key issues pertinent to population surveillance of PA with the use of consumer wearable devices: representative sampling, representative wear-time, validity and reliability, and compatibility between consumer devices. Representative sampling refers to epidemiological study participants being representative of the target population. Therefore, to make inferences about population level PA, the study sample must be representative of the population. One issue with consumer wearable devices is that being younger and more affluent are characteristics associated with device ownership and use, in comparison to older, less affluent individuals (Bietz et al., 2016; Strain, Wijndaele and Brage, 2019; Pontin et al., 2021). Therefore, if a random sample was taken from existing owners of consumer wearable devices, then PA prevalence estimations may not be generalisable outside that sample. Furthermore, the data set won’t represent all device owners, only those prepared to share their device data (Turner *et al.*, 2021).

Like representative sampling, representative wear-time is also important. As is the case with research-grade accelerometers as well as consumer wearable devices, between-person and within-person differences in when the device is worn can be an issue. While consumer wearable devices are designed and marketed as continuous wear devices, studies have shown that users tend to wear them while they are being active (Hendker et al., 2020). Therefore, periods of non-wear-time cannot necessarily be assumed to be random and activity captured may not be reflective of habitual behaviour.

As previously mentioned, the validity and reliability of PA measuring devices is vital. The issue with consumer wearable devices is that there are constantly new devices being released to the market. Not only that but firmware and software updates can occur without the user's knowledge, potentially influencing its ability to measure PA variables positively or negatively. These updates can be helpful to the user as they can add features to the device or fix problems, however, changes to the device can make it no longer comparable to previously published work (Evenson, Goto and Furberg, 2015).

With the rapidly evolving consumer wearable devices market, another problem arises – compatibility between consumer devices. Ferguson et al., (2015) found in free-living conditions that PA estimates from seven activity trackers varied widely. For example, the Misfit Shine (Misfit, San Francisco, CA, US) underestimated MVPA by 26% or 15 minutes per day, whereas the Striiv Smart Pedometer (Striiv, Inc. Redwood City, CA, US) overestimated by 325% or 190 minutes per day. However, when looking at step count the differences between the devices were less stark (Ferguson *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, researchers

cannot just accept PA data from any of the countless consumer wearable devices available today. Nor can they decide to just use one brand and model as that would negate efforts of gaining a representative study sample. Furthermore, providing participants with a device for the purpose of the study would mean missing out on retrospective data, a key benefit of utilising consumer wearable devices in PA surveillance (Strain et al., 2022a).

Further to these issues, there is a lack of consensus on the reporting of adherence, wear-time, and what type of PA is measured in free living consumer activity tracker studies, therefore performing systematic reviews and meta-analyses is challenging. Subsequently, Chan et al., (2022) have recently recommended a minimum reporting threshold on these three components. They suggest reporting at least one measure of adherence (for example, percentage of days the wearable was worn), ensuring and reporting whether participants met the wear-time criteria (per day and per week), and reporting multiple PA measures instead of just one or two (Chan *et al.*, 2022). This should enhance the quality of consumer activity tracker studies and bring the field closer to a standardisation for the analysis and reporting of data measured by consumer activity trackers.

2.3.3.1 Consumer activity trackers

Consumer activity trackers for quantifying human movement have been a leading health and fitness trend since 2016. It came in at number one every year (2016 – 2023) in a worldwide survey of fitness trends conducted by the American College of Sports Medicine, except 2018 and 2021, where it was number 3 and number 2, respectively (Thompson, 2015, 2016, 2017,

2018, 2019, 2021, 2022, 2023). In 2022, 101 million consumer grade fitness tracker units were sold globally, and the wrist-based tracker market had a revenue of US\$17.3 billion (Statista, 2023b). Despite their popularity, research is ambiguous regarding whether these commercially available wearable devices provide valid and reliable estimates of PA, including EE, HR and steps. Additionally, it is impossible for validation studies to keep up with the relentless speed in which new devices are released, consequently limiting literature from keeping pace with the marketplace. Therefore, their use within population surveillance of PA studies is limited regardless of their ability to reach millions of people. Furthermore, publications on specific tracker models become almost redundant once that model is no longer for sale. For example, there are over 100 publications available (May 2023) on PubMed® mentioning the ‘Fitbit Flex’ models, the original Fitbit Flex was released in 2013 and was replaced by Fitbit Flex 2 in 2016, however this newer model has also been off the market for 4 years now. Moreover, over 50 of those publications were published after the Fitbit Flex 2 was discontinued in early 2019, highlighting that the delay in the scientific process is such that it renders the research itself, at least partially, superfluous.

Fitbit (Fitbit, San Francisco, CA, USA), founded in 2007, is one of the most popular and successful consumer electronics company producing commercially available activity trackers. The Classic model, released in 2009 and also referred to as the Fitbit and the Fitbit Tracker, was a small device that could be clipped onto clothing. Between 2011 and 2012, three additional clip-on devices were launched: the Ultra, Zip, and One. In 2013, Fitbit introduced its first wristband tracker, the Flex. Since then, Fitbit has released more than 20 products in the wristband tracker and smartwatch market. The main difference between a wristband tracker

and a smartwatch is that a smartwatch typically has the same features as a wristband tracker but with the addition of supported apps, more like an extension of a smartphone.

All Fitbit devices available today are worn on the wrist and measure PA using a tri-axial accelerometer. Most models now also contain a photoplethysmography (PPG) optical sensor that uses light to measure the volumetric variations of blood circulation, and therefore provide an estimate of HR. Newer models, such as the Sense 2, also include an altimeter, red and infrared sensors for oxygen saturation (SpO₂) monitoring, GPS, and a skin temperature sensor. Fitbit proprietary algorithms are used to provide an estimation of several variables including step count; EE; active minutes; steps climbed; distance travelled; and sleep duration and 'score'. Measurement accuracy of Fitbit devices is important as they are being used as an outcome measurement tool in research and to inform healthcare decisions (Rezaei and Grandner, 2021; Feehan et al., 2018).

With the variety of Fitbit models and features that are offered to consumers, there are several considerations that are important for device selection, including validity. Using an activity tracker which accurately measures PA while also quantifying it in a way that consumers understand, may lead to increased consumer satisfaction (Aroganam, Manivannan and Harrison, 2019). Moreover, users are less likely to abandon their activity tracker if they deem the output measures as accurate (Attig and Franke, 2022).

Most studies investigating the validity of consumer activity trackers have explored this within a laboratory setting and utilised a criterion measure for counting steps: manual step counting/accelerometers. A systematic review investigating the validity and reliability of the Classic, Ultra, One, Zip and Flex Fitbit models as well as the UP and UP24 Jawbone models (Jawbone, San Francisco, CA, USA) found an almost perfect correlation between consumer activity tracker steps and manually counted/accelerometer steps (Pearson or intraclass correlation coefficients (CC) > 0.8) during laboratory treadmill tests (Evenson, Goto and Furberg, 2015). High errors tended to be in the direction of underestimation of steps by the trackers. Inter-device reliability of the Fitbit devices (there were no Jawbone studies on reliability at the time the systematic review was conducted) was found to be high, with CC ranging from substantial to almost perfect for both step count and EE. However, correlations varied widely between tracker estimated EE and the criterion measures (predominantly IC), with CC ranging from moderate to substantial agreement (CC = 0.4 – 0.8), again the errors generally tended to be an underestimation of EE by the trackers. Similarly, Montoye et al., (2018) found that five different Fitbit models, three of which measured HR (Blaze, Charge HR, Alta HR), two did not (Alta, Flex), all had similarly poor EE prediction accuracies when compared to criterion measures. They did however deduce that Fitbit models that measure HR do in fact utilise HR measurements in their EE predictions, as the HR measuring Fitbits had significantly higher EE estimations (10.5 – 23.8%, $p < .05$) during laboratory treadmill walking and jogging activities carried out at an incline (10% and 3%, respectively) than the non-HR measuring Fitbits. However, this did not improve the accuracy as mean absolute percentage errors (MAPE) for EE predictions for Fitbits measuring HR were 33.7 – 38.3%, compared to 32.4 – 36.6% for non-HR measuring Fitbits.

A recent meta-analysis conducted by Leung and colleagues (2021) looked at the validity of 12 different brands of consumer activity trackers: Apple, Basis, Epson, Fitbit, Garmin, Jawbone, Misfit, Nike, Omron, Samsung, Tanita, and Withings. They determined that Omron had the highest validity, with a 95% confidence interval (95% CI) of 0.82 – 0.95, while Garmin had the lowest (95% CI 0.25 – 0.64). Fitbit was ranked no.7 (95% 0.66 – 0.78). However, it is important to note that only 2 Omron validity studies were included, whereas 37 Fitbit studies were included. Interestingly, the authors found no differences between devices released before and after 2015, meaning the accuracy of these devices has not improved over time, when compared to criterion methods. One would expect that the quality and accuracy of these devices would improve with newer models released, however, perhaps what the companies deem an enhancement to the device, isn't necessarily the accuracy of the measurements it provides, but possibly the addition of new features, or how it looks. Based on this meta-analysis, it can be concluded that consumer activity trackers vary in their performance, and newer, more advanced models do not necessarily outperform older ones. The same research team later carried out another meta-analysis, this time solely looking at the validity evidence of different Fitbit models (Leung *et al.*, 2022). The authors reported a summarised validity coefficient of $r = .64$, between Fitbit device and criterion method, which is indicative of validity problems (Post, 2016), concluding that the validity evidence of Fitbit devices is inconclusive.

One issue with the focus of validity studies being laboratory-based is that they are only testing the devices over a very short period of time, therefore lacking longitudinal perspective. Also, the strict nature of laboratory experiments prohibits embracing the nuance of users' PA in natural settings. Furthermore, while users' activity may be more multifaceted during free living, the consumer activity tracker they use can also undergo transformations in technological

capabilities over time. Therefore, longitudinal studies on the accuracy of these devices during free living, taking into consideration the automatic/manual firmware updates that occur would be beneficial (Shin *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, a productive course for future research could lie at the intersection of validation studies and consumer activity tracker adoption/abandonment studies. This may clarify whether users prioritise accuracy when adopting activity trackers, how their perceptions of accuracy influence continued use, and how they form such perceptions without access to research or the ability to conduct their own scientific study.

Another important question is whether consumer activity trackers elicit positive behaviour change. These devices can aid in integrating regular exercise into users' lives by delivering extrinsic motivation through quantified behavioural feedback. This quantification of self can strengthen motivation and goal focus (Pettinico and Milne, 2017). This may be particularly useful for users' who lack intrinsic motivation for exercising, however prolonged use of the tracker is therefore vital for achieving health benefits (Hermsen *et al.*, 2016; Hancı *et al.*, 2020). However, Hendker *et al.*, (2020) found that in a cohort of participants who had not used an activity tracker before and were not told that they would be provided with an activity tracker as part of the study therefore representing a 'normal' interest in activity trackers, participants used the device less over time, indicating an initial motivational boost upon being given the device which wanes over time. This decline in usage over time was similarly found in previous studies (Alley *et al.*, 2016; Hermsen *et al.*, 2016, 2017). The reasons commonly cited for activity tracker abandonment are losing the device (Hermsen *et al.*, 2017; Hartman *et al.*, 2022), the device breaking (Maher *et al.*, 2017; Hartman *et al.*, 2022), feeling like they had already learned everything they could from their activity tracker and that their activity tracker was not helping them achieve their goals (Maher *et al.*, 2017). While initial increases in PA levels have

been reported, this increase seems to be transient, with users stating that their activity levels subsequently returned to baseline (Maher *et al.*, 2017). In a cohort of 75 female breast cancer survivors (aged 21 – 85 years), Hartman *et al.*, (2022) found that PA levels, as measured by a Fitbit One, increased during a 12-week PA randomised controlled trial. However, these levels had reduced again when participants were followed up over the subsequent two years. Interestingly, participants were divided into two groups: ‘full intervention’ and ‘light intervention’. The full intervention group participated in a 30-to-45-minute face-to-face meeting, which included a 10-minute moderate-intensity walk. During this session, participants also worked with a researcher trained in motivational interviewing to set personalised PA goals. Participants were also made aware that their Fitbit data was being reviewed by a health coach and that they would receive feedback on it during scheduled phone calls. Whereas the light intervention group had a much shorter meeting (with no walk) with a research assistant not skilled in motivational interviewing and were not explicitly told that a health coach would see and provide feedback on their Fitbit data. Furthermore, the participants in the light intervention were also offered scheduled phone calls however these were presented as optional. Both groups were sent automated emails every three days. The authors found that adherence to wearing the activity tracker was significantly higher in the full intervention group, compared to the light intervention group (85% vs 60%). Not only that, but device measured MVPA was also higher in those in the full intervention (27.89 minutes/day vs 18.35 minutes/day). Furthermore, those in the light intervention group had steeper declines in device adherence following completion of the 12-weeks. This suggests that for prolonged use of an activity tracker, comprehensive feedback and/or external accountability may be a valuable addition.

2.3.3.2 Smartphone apps

A smartphone is a mobile phone that has access to the internet and apps. A median of 43% of adults worldwide report owning a smartphone, with higher-income countries having higher rates than lower-income countries (Poushter, 2016). With the increasing prevalence and usage of smartphones in modern society, as well as the advances in smartphone technology, there has been a growing interest in utilising these devices as a means of measuring PA as well as delivering PA interventions.

Smartphones include a motion coprocessor which analyses sensor data from an in-built tri-axial accelerometer, gyroscope and GPS. With the use of proprietary algorithms, these data can be integrated to estimate markers of PA. Users can view their data in the smartphones' first-party app, which typically comes pre-installed, such as the iPhone's 'Health' app. There is also an abundance of third-party apps that users can install which provide additional functionality, including additional PA metrics, PA goal setting, and updates on daily progress. In 2018, there were 102,962 apps associated with health and fitness in the Google Play store and 97,844 in Apple's App Store (Silva *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, there is a huge potential for the promotion of PA with the use of smartphones.

There are several potential benefits of using smartphones in PA research. One advantage is the portability and convenience of these devices. They allow for continuous monitoring of PA throughout the day without requiring additional equipment (such as a consumer activity tracker) or specialised training to interpret the data, as is the case with research-grade accelerometers. Additionally, like consumer activity trackers, smartphone-based apps can

provide real-time feedback on PA levels, allowing individuals to track their progress towards fitness goals and adjust their training as needed. These features, as well as how ubiquitous smartphones are, make them an appealing tool for use in a research setting (Domin *et al.*, 2021). There is no need to purchase and hand out devices such as accelerometers for research studies, which keeps research costs low and avoids the inevitable outcome of not receiving all the devices back. Furthermore, smartphones enable the straightforward sharing of data via apps and cloud-based platforms, allowing researchers to remotely view and download the data. They also offer the unobtrusive collection of naturalistic behavioural data (Harari *et al.*, 2016). As researchers have implemented the smartphone as a PA monitor in research studies (Althoff *et al.*, 2017), it is essential that the validity of these devices is understood. Many studies have shown smartphones to be accurate at estimating step count within a laboratory setting (Höchsmann *et al.*, 2018; Johnson *et al.*, 2016), however they can tend to underestimate step count during free living (Duncan *et al.*, 2018; Amagasa *et al.*, 2019).

Despite the potential benefits there are several limitations and challenges associated with using smartphones for PA measurement. While smartphone fitness apps are downloaded at a high rate, they are also abandoned and uninstalled at a high rate, due to loss of interest and hidden costs (Krebs and Duncan, 2015). Vinnikova *et al.*, (2020) found that perceived usefulness and ease-of-use of smartphone apps significantly positively affects usage behaviour. One major challenge is the variability in measurement quality among different smartphone models from various manufacturers. Other factors such as operating system settings and third-party app usage may also affect the accuracy of data collection. Moreover, the handling of smartphones by participants and their effect on measurements is a significant issue (Morales and Akopian, 2017).

Researchers have also investigated the impact of using smartphone-based PA tracking on health outcomes such as weight loss and BP, with some studies reporting improvements in these areas (Vinnikova *et al.*, 2020; Bort-roig *et al.*, 2014). A recent meta-analysis of 12 studies investigating smartphone app-based PA interventions for weight loss found a small-to-moderate effect on the reduction of body weight (Yen, Jin and Chiu, 2023). The authors specified that studies with a longer intervention duration saw greater effects on BMI (Yen, Jin and Chiu, 2023). In a recent systematic review with meta-analysis, Silva *et al.*, (2020) found interventions solely using smartphone apps, as well as interventions using apps as an adjunct to traditional interventions (e.g. face-to-face), had a small but positive effect on step count in the short-term when compared to no intervention or solely traditional interventions. However, the systematic review only included 11 studies, the majority of which were deemed to be low quality.

2.4 Digital and mobile health

In recent decades, the rapid development and advancement of digital technology has driven transformative changes in nearly every area of human activity. Therefore, digital health has emerged as a prominent field of research, “associated with the development and use of digital technologies to improve health” (World Health Organization, 2021). Digital health encompasses a wide range of technologies and innovations that aim to revolutionise healthcare delivery and improve patient outcomes (McGinnis, Fineberg and Dzau, 2021). Mobile health (mHealth) falls under the umbrella term of digital health and while there is no agreed upon definition of mHealth, it is defined by the World Health Organisation as the “medical and

public health practice supported by mobile devices, such as mobile phones, patient-monitoring devices, personal digital assistants, and other wireless devices” (World Health Organization, 2011). With the development of mHealth has come the empowerment of patients to self-record and self-monitor their own health metrics with the use of a smartphone. This allows patients to consult with HCPs remotely, which in turn can potentially lead to the earlier detection of health problems as well as improving patient engagement with their care (Hollis *et al.*, 2015). mHealth apps and wearable devices encourage patients to take an active role in managing their health. Incorporating self-management into treatment programs for patients with chronic conditions has been previously found to have modest but clinically meaningful improvements in health outcomes, health behaviours and quality of life (Allegrante, Wells and Peterson, 2019). Furthermore, decreases in unnecessary healthcare usage, healthcare costs and hospital admissions have also been reported (Allegrante, Wells and Peterson, 2019). The value in this type of healthcare was made especially evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, where mHealth services became vital for maintaining patient care while minimising exposure risks.

As digital health continues to grow, the WHO describe the "digital determinants of health", including skills in information and communication technologies as well as access to devices, broadband and the internet, as being increasingly vital (World Health Organization, 2021). They have proposed a global strategy to enhance health systems through the implementation of digital health by HCPs, consumers and industry by 2025. This approach seeks to empower patients and fulfil the vision of accessible healthcare for everyone. Their global strategy highlights the importance of establishing strong digital foundations within national strategies and stresses the necessity of collaboration across various sectors and stakeholders at all levels (World Health Organization, 2021). These digital determinants of health have also been described as the “super social determinants of health” as they address the social determinants

of health, as can be seen in Figure 2-2. For instance, applications for housing and employment, both of which impacts a person's health, are often exclusively available online. The cost of enabling someone to access and use the internet is significantly lower than the cost of treating health conditions, and the long-term benefits are substantial (Sieck *et al.*, 2021).

However, the swift digital transformation in healthcare has the potential to exacerbate health inequality (Sieck *et al.*, 2021; Richardson *et al.*, 2022). Health interventions can create disparities, as they are often adopted unevenly, leaving disadvantaged populations behind. Digital health is especially at risk, as these interventions are likely to disproportionately advantage individuals with greater access to resources, knowledge and power. For example, according to the American Community Survey in 2018, 15% of American households did not have broadband internet, this figure increased to 38% when annual household earnings were less than \$20,000 (Tomer *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, there is a disparity between levels of fixed-broadband subscription in high- and low-income countries. In low-income countries, only one person out of every hundred has a fixed-broadband subscription, primarily because of high costs and inadequate infrastructure (International Telecommunication Union, 2023). It is therefore crucial for leaders and developers in healthcare, academia and industry to recognise the digital determinants of health and understand their roles in ensuring that technology use does not further widen these gaps (Richardson *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 2-2: Illustration of how digital literacy and access relate to the domains of social determinants of health (Sieck *et al.*, 2021). Reprinted under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2.4.1 Remote monitoring of health

The advancements in wearable and remote monitoring devices are progressing at an exponential rate. These technologies will enable more precise measurements of physical and physiological parameters in more expedient ways, and are poised to impact various aspects of healthcare, from prevention (such as tracking activity, eating habits, stress levels etc.) to diagnosis (e.g., early detection) and disease management (e.g., monitoring drug doses and providing reminders) (Liao *et al.*, 2019).

mHealth technologies have empowered patients to independently and continuously track their health metrics and review the data through mobile apps or web-based platforms. Many platforms allow users to see comprehensive information about their health over time, providing a visual representation of how lifestyle changes affect key health indicators (Majumder, Mondal and Deen, 2017). This enables individuals to take control of their health and confidently monitor it themselves (Jones *et al.*, 2012). For instance, Bluetooth-enabled BP monitors allow wireless tracking of a key cardiovascular health marker, with data recorded through a connected app. Studies have shown that home BP self-monitoring is reliable (Stergiou *et al.*, 2007), helps reduce the occurrence of "white coat hypertension," (Padwal *et al.*, 2007) and lowers healthcare costs related to the treatment of hypertension and associated complications (Ohkubo *et al.*, 2004; Imai *et al.*, 1993).

HCPs have expressed that home monitoring of key clinical outcomes, such as BP, may result in quicker or more aggressive treatment (Agarwal *et al.*, 2011). However, HCPs have also raised concerns about remote monitoring, including increased workload, cost, and the shift

away from traditional face-to-face care (Wild *et al.*, 2015). On the other hand, a recent randomised controlled trial found that many patients preferred a virtual clinic over attending a conventional outpatient clinic for routine post-surgical follow-up (Healy *et al.*, 2018). The study concluded that follow-up visits for most general surgical conditions are often unnecessary and may even delay HCPs from seeing new patients. McCartney (2017) has previously emphasised the importance of thoroughly testing health platforms and apps before they are rolled out. Therefore, before integrating a DHP into healthcare systems worldwide, it is essential to evaluate its usability, feasibility, and acceptability.

2.5 Study aims and objectives

The primary objective of this PhD research was to determine validity and user experience of wearable technology to measure PA etc. Furthermore, the research explored HCPs perceptions of wearable technology and a novel DHP. Finally, the research utilised data from wearable technology to explore changes in PA and SB following the implementation of the COVID lockdown.

2.5.1 Study 1 (chapter 4)

Aim 1: Assess the validity of the iPhone M7 motion coprocessor for estimating step count and subsequently estimating EE (with the use of the ActivityTracker app) during treadmill walking, jogging, running, stationary cycling, and an aerobics session.

Aim 2: Compare measurements of step count between the iPhone and GT3X+ during a two-week period of free-living.

2.5.2 Study 2 (chapter 5)

Aim 1: Evaluate the convergent validity of a user's own iPhone for measuring daily step count by comparing to both an iPhone and GT3X+ accelerometer that were continuously worn around the waist in healthy adults.

Aim 2: Explore, using a qualitative approach, the habits of each user with their mobile device during the monitoring period, their previous experience with wearable technologies for PA monitoring, and their perception on the use of smartphones to measure PA and SB.

2.5.3 Study 3 (chapter 6)

Aim 1: Determine the usability of a novel DHP (the Lenus Health Platform) and associated apps in a sample of healthy adults fulfilling the role of secondary care patients (mock patients).

Aim 2: Determine the usability of a novel DHP (the Lenus Health Platform) in a sample of HCPs currently working in the UK's publicly funded healthcare system, the NHS.

2.5.4 Study 4 (chapter 7)

Aim 1: Investigate the difference in adult PA behaviours, prior-to, during and after a national lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Aim 2: Explore, qualitatively, how and why PA behaviours changed during and post-lockdown.

CHAPTER 3: General Methodologies

3.1 Overview

Many of the experimental chapters in this thesis employ shared procedures and analytical approaches. Common methods used across multiple studies will be outlined in this chapter, while procedures specific to individual experiments are detailed within their respective chapters (chapters 4 – 7).

3.2 Ethics

All studies were approved by the School of Science and Sport Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland (approval numbers: chapter 4 – 2017-0955-856; chapter 5 – 2018-4847-3551; chapter 6 – 2017-0955-856; chapter 7 – 2020-10938-9234) and were conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013). Each participant received a written information sheet outlining the study details. Written informed consent was obtained from participants and they were made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without explanation.

3.3 Contributions

In this section, details of contributions towards each study will be detailed. Dr Lauren McMichan was employed as a Post-Doctoral Research Fellow for studies 1 and 3. Professor Chris Easton and Dr Eilidh Macrae were lead supervisor and supervisor, respectively.

3.3.1 Study 1 (chapter 4)

Conceptualisation: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Data curation: Nicola Thomson, Lauren McMichan.

Formal analysis: Nicola Thomson.

Funding acquisition: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Investigation: Nicola Thomson, Lauren McMichan.

Methodology: Chris Easton, Nicola Thomson, Lauren McMichan.

Supervision: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Writing – original draft: Nicola Thomson.

Writing – review & editing: Lauren McMichan, Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

3.3.2 Study 2 (chapter 5)

Conceptualisation: Chris Easton, Nicola Thomson, Eilidh Macrae.

Data curation: Nicola Thomson.

Formal analysis: Nicola Thomson.

Funding acquisition: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Investigation: Nicola Thomson.

Methodology: Chris Easton, Nicola Thomson, Eilidh Macrae.

Supervision: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Writing – original draft: Nicola Thomson.

Writing – review & editing: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

3.3.3 Study 3 (chapter 6)

Conceptualisation: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae, Nicola Thomson, Lauren McMichan

Data curation: Nicola Thomson, Lauren McMichan.

Formal analysis: Nicola Thomson, Lauren McMichan.

Funding acquisition: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Investigation: Lauren McMichan, Nicola Thomson.

Methodology: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae, Lauren McMichan, Nicola Thomson.

Supervision: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Writing – original draft: Nicola Thomson.

Writing – review & editing: Lauren McMichan, Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

3.3.4 Study 4 (chapter 7)

Conceptualisation: Chris Easton, Nicola Thomson, Eilidh Macrae.

Data curation: Nicola Thomson.

Formal analysis: Nicola Thomson.

Funding acquisition: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Investigation: Nicola Thomson.

Methodology: Chris Easton, Nicola Thomson, Eilidh Macrae.

Supervision: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

Writing – original draft: Nicola Thomson.

Writing – review & editing: Chris Easton, Eilidh Macrae.

3.4 Measurement procedures

3.4.1 Anthropometric measurements

At the start of each study, the age of each participant was recorded, and for studies 1 and 2 stature and body mass (BM) were also recorded.

3.4.2 Step count and EE

Step count alone or step count and EE were selected as primary outcome measures in chapters 4, 5 and 7 due to their widespread use in both personal PA monitoring and research, as well as their clinical relevance. Step count is a simple behavioural metric that correlates strongly with health outcomes, including reduced risk of cardiovascular disease and all-cause mortality (Tudor-Locke et al., 2011). EE provides a physiological estimate of total activity volume and intensity, offering additional insight into energy balance and lifestyle-related health outcomes (Strath et al., 2013). Together, these metrics capture both the quantity and energetic cost of movement, making them suitable for evaluating PA patterns in both structured and free-living conditions.

3.4.3 iPhone 5S

In chapters 4-6, participants (excluding HCPs) were given an iPhone 5S for the duration of the trial for the collection of step count data. The iPhones were reset to factory settings and fully charged. Participants' anthropometric details were entered into the 'Health' app prior to trial commencement. The iPhone estimates step count using unpublished proprietary algorithms.

These algorithms integrate data from the Apple's inbuilt accelerometer - which detects ambulatory data across vertical, mediolateral, and anteroposterior axes - along with input from the gyroscope and GPS. Estimates are relative to the participants' stature and BM. The total daily and hourly step count data can then be viewed in the 'Health' app.

3.4.4 GT3X+

In chapters 4 and 5, triaxial GT3X+ accelerometers (ActiGraph, Pensacola, FL, USA) were utilised. The GT3X+ was selected over alternative devices as it is the most established and most validated method for measuring free-living PA (Giurgiu *et al.*, 2023; Boudreaux *et al.*, 2024). The GT3X+ has been extensively validated against gold-standard measures for step count and EE across a range of intensities (Sasaki *et al.*, 2011; Santos-Lozano *et al.*, 2012).

Before each triaxial GT3X+ accelerometer (ActiGraph LLC) was initialised to record data at a sampling frequency of 30 Hz in three axes: vertical, mediolateral and anteroposterior, using ActiLife software (version 6.13.3, Lite Edition; ActiGraph LLC). The ActiGraph GT3X+ accelerometer was selected for use in studies 4 and 5 as it has been previously shown, when worn on the waist, to: accurately assess step count in laboratory studies (Mcminn *et al.*, 2013; Tudor-Locke, Barreira and Schuna, 2015); have high inter-instrument reliability during activities of daily living (Ozemek *et al.*, 2014) and under free-living conditions (Jarrett, Fitzgerald and Routen, 2015; Aadland and Ylvisåker, 2015). The GT3X+ is also the most commonly used accelerometer by researchers in laboratory and free-living settings (Wijndaele *et al.*, 2015; Migueles *et al.*, 2017; Reid *et al.*, 2017). When downloading the GT3X+ data using the ActiLife software, the manufacturer's default filter and ActiGraph's proprietary algorithm for step count were used.

3.5 Mixed methods

A mixed methods approach was utilised for chapters 5 and 7. A mixed methods approach was adopted in recognition of the complex nature of health-related behaviours and the need to capture both measurable outcomes and contextual experiences. Mixed methods research enables researchers to draw upon the complementary strengths of both qualitative and quantitative paradigms. This enabled a deeper understanding of participant behaviours and experiences that would not have been accessible through quantitative enquiry alone. In the context of PA monitoring, it was essential not only to quantify outcomes such as step count or EE but also to understand how individuals experienced and interacted with these technologies in their everyday lives. The approach was determined *a priori* and aligns with guidance from Gaglio *et al.*, (2020), who highlight that rigorous mixed methods designs integrate both strands throughout the research process to address overarching questions effectively.

Chapters 5 and 7 adopt a critical realist philosophical underpinning (Ryba *et al.*, 2022), recognising that while PA can be objectively measured through wearables and smartphones, these measurements are mediated by user behaviour, technological limitations, and social context. A mixed methods design was employed to access both the empirical data (device-recorded PA) and the actual and real domains (participant habits, motivations, and structural barriers), in order to better understand the complexity of PA behaviour in real-world conditions.

3.6 Qualitative data

To enhance the credibility of the qualitative components in chapters 5 and 7, a range of strategies were employed. Participants were selected from within the quantitative study sample

to ensure their experiences were directly relevant to the phenomena under investigation, supporting internal coherence between data strands (Gaglio *et al.*, 2020). Credibility was further supported by triangulation: key qualitative insights (e.g. reduced PA during lockdown or the inconsistent smartphone carry behaviour) mirrored patterns in the quantitative data, strengthening confidence in the findings. Thus, the qualitative data were not ancillary but central to contextualising and deepening the interpretation of quantitative trends, and to proposing real-world applications (Tovin and Wormley, 2023).

Verbatim transcription of all semi-structured interviews (chapters 5, 6 and 7), careful attention to context, and an inductive coding approach enabled the emergence of authentic, participant-led themes. Reflexive awareness was maintained throughout, with analytic decisions guided directly by the participants' accounts rather than by any pre-existing assumptions or theoretical frameworks (Gaglio *et al.*, 2020).

3.7 Qualitative data collection and analysis

All interviews (chapters 5, 6 and 7) were conducted using a semi-structured interview schedule generated by the research team after consultation with existing literature and in line with the study aims. Before the study commenced, each interview schedule was pilot-tested and subsequently refined to enhance clarity, coherence and the overall flow of questioning. I, myself, conducted all interviews in chapters 5 and 7. In chapter 6, Dr Lauren McMichan, who was employed as a Post-Doctoral Research Fellow, conducted all the interviews.

Interviews were held either at the university, the participant's workplace/home, or via video conferencing. In chapter 5, all interviews took place at the university, and a time-series graph displaying each participant's step count data was presented during the interview to stimulate discussion around factors that may have influenced their engagement or non-engagement with PA.

All interviews were recorded with participant consent using a Dictaphone and transcribed verbatim before being uploaded onto Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS), NVivo (NVivo 12, QSR International). Analysis was carried out using Braun and Clarke's (Braun and Clarke, 2006) six-phase thematic model: data familiarisation; initial code generation; search for themes; review themes; define themes; and write-up. I, myself, analysed all interviews in chapters 5 and 7, while myself and Dr Lauren McMichan analysed interviews from chapter 6. Initially, transcripts were open coded to identify all relevant content related to the research questions. Using a process of constant comparison, related codes were grouped into subthemes, which were then further refined and abstracted into overarching themes. These themes were then reviewed and refined, taking into account relevant existing literature. Anonymised quotations from interview transcripts were utilised to provide a variety of participant perspectives. In chapters 5 and 7, integration of quantitative and qualitative findings was achieved through an embedded design, with qualitative insights used to contextualise and interpret quantitative patterns (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2003). This integration is presented throughout the discussion section of chapters 5 and 7.

3.8 Data processing and analysis

Daily steps from the GT3X+ were only included in the analysis in chapters 4 and 5 if wear-time was ≥ 10 hours per day (Van Dyck *et al.*, 2015). Non-wear-time was defined as ≥ 60 min of consecutive zeros (Van Dyck *et al.*, 2015). Days with <1000 steps were excluded from further analysis (Barreira *et al.*, 2013).

Bland and Altman (1986) analysis was used to express agreement between methods in chapters 4 and 5. The 95% limits of agreement (LOA) were calculated as mean bias $\pm (1.96 \times$ standard deviation). In chapters 4, 5 and 7, statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$ and all statistical procedures were carried out using Jamovi project (2018; version 0.9.5.12; retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>, open source).

3.9 Chapter 6 planned progression

In Chapter 6, mock patient and clinician user experiences of a novel DHP were explored. The planned progression of this work was to conduct a similar study with a cohort of secondary care patients at NHS Highlands. Twenty cardiac patients aged over 18 years, who were under review at the NHS Fort William Health Centre, were to be recruited. Participants were asked to record measurements of BP, PA, and BM using designated apps and provided hardware (iPhone 6S, Bluetooth-enabled BP monitor, and digital body weight scales), uploading these data to the Lenus Health Platform over an 8-week period. Participants would also have the option to track dietary intake using third-party apps integrated with the platform. During this time, the research team would monitor compliance and send reminders where necessary.

Clinicians were to be interviewed after having had the opportunity to view patient-generated data within the Lenus Health Platform. The purpose of these interviews was to collect qualitative data regarding the usability of the platform and associated applications, and to explore perceptions of data management and confidentiality. All qualitative data would have been transcribed and analysed using thematic analysis.

Unfortunately, although NHS ethical approval to commence data collection was granted in February 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic made it impossible to proceed with the study.

CHAPTER 4: Study 1 - Validity of the iPhone M7 Motion Coprocessor to Estimate PA during Structured and Free-Living Activities in Healthy Adults

A version of this chapter has been published in the following journal:

Thomson, N.K. et al. (2021) ‘Validity of the iPhone M7 Motion Coprocessor to Estimate Physical Activity during Structured and Free-Living Activities in Healthy Adults’, *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 4(3), pp. 1–9.

4.1 Introduction

Measuring levels of PA is becoming increasingly important given the well-defined relationships with health, disease, and mortality (Antero Kesaniemi et al., 2001). Measuring PA, however, can be notoriously challenging in a large number of individuals. While indirect methods such as self-report questionnaires are easy to implement, they lack objectivity and accuracy (Prince et al., 2008; Dyrstad et al., 2014). On the other hand, accelerometers can be worn around the waist or the wrist to provide more objective and accurate estimates of the frequency, intensity, and duration of PA during periods of free-living (Aadland & Ylvisåker, 2015; Lee et al., 2015). Triaxial accelerometers such as the Actigraph GT3X+ (ActiGraph, FL, USA) are commonly used in research and large national PA surveys such as the 2013 – 2014 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. However, to gain meaningful data, participants are required to wear the accelerometer > 10 hours/day for at least four days/week, (Troiano et al., 2008) which some individuals find to be burdensome (O'Brien *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, accelerometers can be costly, require expertise in analysing the output data as well as lacking real-world transferability.

Nowadays, the majority of adults carry a smartphone that already contains the hardware that can measure locomotion, with 76% of the UK's population reporting to own a smartphone in 2018 (Taylor & Silver, 2019). For example, the iPhone 5S's M7 motion coprocessor (Apple Inc., Cupertino, CA, USA) collects sensor data from an integrated accelerometer which can estimate step count and PA. A range of downloadable apps can then integrate these data with the user's stature, BM, and gender to generate estimates of EE using bespoke algorithms. One such app is 'ActivityTracker' (V2.6, Bits&Coffee, Romania) which provides instantaneous and

cumulative measurements of step count and EE. Given the common usage of smartphones, this may reduce the participant burden and costliness associated with objective methods of PA monitoring as there is no additional wearable required. There is the added advantage that researchers would have continuous remote access to the measurements via data sharing platforms. However, the validity of the smartphone technology to measure parameters of PA needs to be further established. A recent study compared the iPhone 5S to manually counted (MC) steps (Major & Alford, 2016) and found good correlation between methods at fast walking speeds (4.68 and 6.48 km·h⁻¹) but not at the slowest walking speed of 3.6 km·h⁻¹. This study did not, however, explore the accuracy of iPhone mobile apps to estimate EE. Of further interest is the impact of user behaviour with mobile devices in a free-living environment and how this influences the accuracy of PA measurements.

To the authors' knowledge, no study has compared estimations of both step count and EE from the iPhone 5S with laboratory-based gold standards during a variety of different physical activities. Therefore, the primary purpose of this study was to assess the validity of the iPhone M7 motion coprocessor, for estimating step count and subsequently estimating EE (with the use of the 'ActivityTracker' app) during treadmill walking, jogging, running, stationary cycling, and an aerobics session. A further aim was to compare measurements of step count between the iPhone and GT3X+ during a two-week period of free living.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Study design

The current study consisted of two distinct phases. The first phase comprised a single experimental trial conducted in the laboratory to determine the validity of iPhone estimates of step count and EE in comparison to gold standard measures (step count = MC, EE = IC). The second phase was a two-week observational period during which free living PA data was concurrently monitored using the iPhone and the GT3X+ accelerometer.

4.2.2 Phase 1: Laboratory

4.2.2.1 Participants

Twenty healthy adults, twelve females and eight males (mean \pm SD: age 28 ± 5 years, stature 168 ± 8 cm and BM 72.0 ± 12.7 kg), volunteered to take part in the current study. The health status of the participants was established by the completion of a self-declared medical questionnaire which excluded participants with a history of cardiorespiratory or neurological disease.

4.2.2.2 Procedures

Upon arrival at the laboratory, participants were briefed on the protocol before anthropometric variables were measured using conventional techniques. A Polar H7 monitor (Polar Electro Oy, Kempele, Finland) was attached to the participant's chest to continuously monitor HR. A triaxial GT3X+ accelerometer was attached to the right hip of participants in a pouch that also held an iPhone 5S. Breath-by-breath pulmonary gas exchange was measured continuously throughout the experiment using a metabolic cart (Ultima CPX, MedGraphics, MN, USA). The

metabolic cart was calibrated as per the manufacturer's guidelines. EE ($\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) was calculated by IC using the Weir equation $(\dot{V}\text{O}_2 \times 3.941) + (\dot{V}\text{CO}_2 \times 1.1)$ (Weir, 1949) - and the mean value from the final 2 min of each bout of exercise or activity was used in later analyses.

The first component required participants to walk and jog on a treadmill at light, moderate and vigorous intensities based on their HR reserve (HRR) for a total of 15 min (5 min at each intensity). Resting HR (RHR) was recorded and age-predicted maximal HR (MHR) was calculated as $(208 - (0.7 \times \text{AGE}))$ (Tanaka, Monahan, & Seals, 2001). The Karvonen formula ($\% \text{ target intensity (MHR} - \text{RHR) + RHR}$) (Ewing *et al.*, 1998) was used to determine the treadmill speed associated with each target intensity range. The treadmill speed began at $3 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and was increased until the participant's HR was in the desired range: Light (30-39% HRR); Moderate (40-59% HRR); and Vigorous (60-89% HRR) (ACSM, 2017). The second component consisted of cycling on a stationary ergometer at a fixed power of 50 W for 5 min. The last component required the participant to complete a 5 min aerobics session by following a YouTube video. Throughout all activities, measurements of accelerometry, HR, iPhone step count, and EE from the 'ActivityTracker' app were continuously recorded. The treadmill component was also video recorded in order to manually count steps, video footage was reviewed, and manual steps were counted for each intensity with the use of a hand tally counter. Two members of the research team separately watched and counted each video 3 times and recorded the values. These values were then compared and when discrepancies were noted, the researchers reanalysed the videos until agreement was reached.

In order to assess the validity of the iPhone during the laboratory trials, iPhone estimates of step count and EE were compared to the gold standards (MC and IC, respectively). For all activities, step count is reported as the number of measured steps for that component.

Component 1: Treadmill walking and jogging

Participants were instructed to step onto the motorised treadmill (PPS Med, Woodway, Waukesha, WI) on which the incline was increased to 1% to mimic the metabolic cost of outdoor walking (Jones & Doust, 1996). After finding the speed which elicited the desired HR range, participants were asked to straddle the treadmill in order to record iPhone step count and EE from the 'ActivityTracker' app before recommencing walking. This was repeated for light ($5.4 \pm 1.0 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$; $9 \pm 2 \text{ RPE}$), moderate ($6.5 \pm 0.9 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$; $11 \pm 2 \text{ RPE}$) and vigorous ($8.0 \pm 1.1 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$; $13 \pm 2 \text{ RPE}$) intensities. Between each stage, participants were again asked to straddle the treadmill and to stand motionless so the iPhone step count and EE could be recorded from the 'ActivityTracker' app.

Components 2 and 3: Cycling and aerobics

Participants carried out 5 min of cycling on an electronically-braked ergometer (Lode Excalibur Sport; Lode Medical Technology, Groningen, The Netherlands) with a constant external power output of 50 W. Participants were instructed to cycle at a comfortable cadence as they would on a leisurely cycle. Following this, participants followed a 5 min segment of a YouTube aerobics-style cardiovascular workout video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=istOU9nxhm8>). The iPhone EE from the 'ActivityTracker' app was recorded at the beginning and end of each activity.

iPhone 5S

The iPhone app 'ActivityTracker' was downloaded onto the iPhone 5S from the Apple store. This app was selected as it provided a live reading of daily total steps and estimates of EE. The 'ActivityTracker' app is reported by the developer to collect step count directly from the iPhones' Health Kit and uses a bespoke algorithm based on step count, gender, stature and BM to estimate EE.

GT3X+

The GT3X+'s were initialised, and the data was downloaded as per section 3.4.4 in chapter 3. EE was estimated using the Freedson VM3 equation (Sasaki, John, & Freedson, 2011) ($0.001064 \times \text{vector magnitude} + 0.087512 (\text{BM}) - 5.500229$).

4.2.2.3 Data analysis

For MC steps, a step was recorded each time the participant's foot touched the treadmill. Reproducibility was evaluated using the concordance correlation coefficient of Lin (CCC) (Lin, 1989) with the thresholds: almost perfect > 0.90 ; substantial $> 0.8 - 0.9$; moderate $0.65 - 0.8$; poor < 0.65 . Bland and Altman (1986) analysis was used to express agreement between methods of measuring step count and EE. Log-transformation of EE data was attempted as the difference between measurement methods increased as EE increased. However, this did not reduce the linear change of the data, so the original, non-log scaled data were used. The mean percentage error (MPE) was computed as $(\text{steps detected} - \text{observed steps (MC)}) / \text{observed}$

steps (MC) \times 100, for step count and (estimated EE – measured EE (IC))/ measured EE (IC) \times 100, for EE. The MAPE was also computed using the same formulas, with the exception that negative values were converted to positive values. Calculating both MPE and MAPE allows for a true representation of the direction and magnitude of difference between methods to be established (Le Masurier, Lee, & Tudor-Locke, 2004). A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess differences between measurement methods (iPhone, GT3X+, and criterion methods).

4.2.3 Phase 2: Free living

4.2.3.1 Participants

Twenty adults volunteered to take part in the second phase of the study. Two participants withdrew (reasons undisclosed), one participant did not have sufficient wear-time of the GT3X+ accelerometer, and the iPhone app malfunctioned for another participant. Therefore, sixteen participants, ten female and six males (mean \pm SD: 42 \pm 17 years old), completed phase 2 of the study.

4.2.3.2 Experimental design and procedures

Participants were monitored for a total period of 14 days. Participants were given an iPhone 5S and were asked to carry the iPhone with them as they would their own mobile phone. Step count data from the iPhone were automatically uploaded to a bespoke online DHP (Lenus, StormID, Edinburgh, UK) which enabled continuous data exchange between the user and the

researcher. The user experience of the Lenus Health Platform was evaluated as a separate component of this study and is reported in chapter 6. Participants were also given a GT3X+ accelerometer which was attached to an elastic waistband. Participants were instructed to wear the GT3X+ all day, every day on the right anterior-superior iliac spine, removing only for sleep and showering/swimming. The accelerometers were initialised, and the data was downloaded as per section 3.4.4 in chapter 3.

4.2.3.3 Data analysis

Daily steps from the GT3X+ were only included in the analysis as per section 3.8 in chapter 3. Reproducibility was evaluated using the CCC (Lin, 1989) with the thresholds: almost perfect > 0.90; substantial > 0.8 – 0.9; moderate 0.65 – 0.8; poor < 0.65. Bland and Altman analysis (Bland and Altman, 1986) was used to assess agreement between step count estimates from the iPhone and the GT3X+ as previously described. Paired T-tests were used to determine whether there was a difference in step count between measurement methods.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Phase 1: Laboratory

4.3.1.1 Treadmill walking, jogging and running

Step count data from the iPhone, GT3X+, and criterion method during the treadmill trial are presented in Table 4-1. The agreement in measurements of step count between iPhone and MC was almost perfect (CCC = 0.993; 95% confidence interval (CI) 0.988 to 0.996 steps)

throughout the treadmill trial with a mean difference of 3 steps (95% LOA -19 to 25 steps) (Figure 4-1a) and a MAPE of 1.1%. When comparing the intensities separately, there was almost perfect agreement between the iPhone and criterion methods with a MAPE of < 2 % at each intensity (Table 4-2).

Table 4-1: Mean \pm standard deviations for iPhone, GT3X+ and manually counted (MC) steps during treadmill walking and jogging at light, moderate and vigorous intensities.

Activity	iPhone (Steps)	GT3X+ (Steps)	MC (Steps)
<i>Full Treadmill Trial</i>	703 \pm 97	675 \pm 133	700 \pm 98
<i>Light</i>	613 \pm 46	579 \pm 91	607 \pm 47
<i>Moderate</i>	701 \pm 89	659 \pm 147	700 \pm 88
<i>Vigorous</i>	796 \pm 40	789 \pm 43	794 \pm 42

Figure 4-1: Bland and Altman plots of iPhone and GT3X+ steps versus manually counted (MC) steps during a laboratory-based treadmill trial at light, moderate and vigorous intensities with mean bias (solid line) and 95% limits of agreement (dashed lines): (a) iPhone; (b) GT3X+.

The GT3X+ and MC agreement for the measurement of step count was moderate (CCC = 0.76; 95% CI 0.64 to 0.84 steps) throughout the treadmill trial with a mean difference of -25 steps (95% LOA -179 to 129 steps) (Figure 4-1b) and a MAPE of 4.6%. When comparing the intensities separately there was poor agreement at light and moderate intensities (MAPE > 5%) but substantial agreement during vigorous intensity (MAPE < 2%, Table 4-2).

Table 4-2: Comparison of iPhone and manually counted (MC) step count, and GT3X+ and MC step count during treadmill walking and jogging at light, moderate and vigorous intensities.

Intensity	Mean Bias (Steps)	95% LOA (Steps)	Lin's CCC (95% CI)	P-Value	MPE	MAPE
<i>iPhone vs MC</i>						
Light	6.4	-7.0 to 20.4	0.979 (0.95 to 0.991)	0.651	1.1 %	1.2 %
Moderate	1.3	-31.6 to 34.2	0.982 (0.96 to 0.993)	0.925	0.2 %	1.5 %
Vigorous	2.2	-9.0 to 13.3	0.989 (0.97 to 0.996)	0.895	0.3 %	0.6 %
<i>GT3X+ vs MC</i>						
Light	-27.6	-184.3 to 129.1	0.36 (0.03 to 0.62)	0.549	-4.6 %	5.5 %
Moderate	-40.6	-250.1 to 169.0	0.57 (0.29 to 0.77)	0.417	-6.0 %	6.9 %
Vigorous	-5.3	-46.9 to 36.4	0.87 (0.70 to 0.95)	0.693	-0.6 %	1.2 %

Figure 4-2: Bland and Altman plots of iPhone and GT3X+ estimated EE versus measured EE (IC) during a laboratory-based treadmill trial including light, moderate and vigorous intensities with mean bias (solid line) and 95% limits of agreement (dashed lines): (a) iPhone; (b) GT3X+.

Estimates of EE from the iPhone, GT3X+, and criterion method (IC) during the treadmill trial can be viewed in Table 4-3. The agreement in measurements of EE between iPhone and IC was poor (CCC = 0.48; 95% CI 0.36 to 0.58 kcal·min⁻¹) throughout the treadmill trial with a mean difference of -1.9 kcal·min⁻¹ (95% LOA -5.6 to 1.8 kcal·min⁻¹) (Figure 4-2a) and a MAPE of 23.7%. When comparing the intensities separately there was moderate agreement at the light intensity, while the iPhone estimates of EE were significantly lower than IC with poor agreement at moderate and vigorous intensities (Table 4-4).

Table 4-3: Mean ± standard deviations for iPhone, GT3X+ and IC energy expenditure during treadmill walking and jogging at light, moderate and vigorous intensities.

Activity	iPhone (kcal·min⁻¹)	GT3X+ (kcal·min⁻¹)	IC (kcal·min⁻¹)
Full Treadmill Trial	5.6 ± 1.4	8.0 ± 3.2	7.5 ± 2.9
Light	4.8 ± 1.0	5.4 ± 2.2	4.9 ± 1.0
Moderate	5.5 ± 1.5	7.3 ± 2.4	7.2 ± 2.1
Vigorous	6.4 ± 1.4	11.2 ± 1.9	10.3 ± 2.2

The agreement in measurements of EE between GT3X+ and IC was substantial (CCC = 0.85; 95% CI 0.77 to 0.91 kcal·min⁻¹) throughout the treadmill trial with a mean difference of 0.5 kcal·min⁻¹ (95% LOA -2.5 to 3.6 kcal·min⁻¹) (Figure 4-2b) and a MAPE of 18.3%. When comparing the intensities separately there was moderate agreement at light, substantial at moderate, and poor agreement at vigorous intensity. The CCC, mean bias, 95% LOA, p-value, MPE and MAPE data presented in Table 4-4.

Table 4-4: Comparison of energy expenditure measurements between the iPhone and IC, and GT3X+ and IC during treadmill walking and jogging at light, moderate and vigorous intensities.

Intensity	Mean Bias (kcal·min ⁻¹)	95% LOA (kcal·min ⁻¹)	Lin's CCC (95% CI)	P-Value	MPE	MAPE
<i>iPhone vs IC</i>						
Light	-0.1	-1.4 to 1.1	0.80 (0.56 to 0.92)	0.922	-1.5 %	11.2 %
Moderate	-1.6	-3.7 to 0.4	0.58 (0.36 to 0.74)	0.034*	-21.3 %	22.1 %
Vigorous	-3.9	-6.7 to -1.1	0.20 (0.06 to 0.33)	< 0.001*	-37.8 %	37.8 %
<i>GT3X+ vs IC</i>						
Light	0.5	-2.1 to 3.2	0.67 (0.51 to 0.78)	0.611	6.5 %	23.7 %
Moderate	0.2	-2.5 to 2.8	0.82 (0.60 to 0.92)	0.961	2.3 %	14.0 %
Vigorous	0.9	-2.9 to 4.7	0.49 (0.11 to 0.75)	0.283	11.1 %	18.1 %

* denotes significance between measurement methods.

4.3.1.2 Cycling and aerobics

In comparison to IC (5.3 ± 0.9 kcal·min⁻¹), both the iPhone (3.3 ± 2.1 kcal·min⁻¹) and the GT3X+ (0.4 ± 0.8 kcal·min⁻¹) significantly underestimated EE during stationary cycling trial ($P < 0.001$). There was poor agreement between the criterion method and estimates of EE with the iPhone (CCC = 0.20; 95% CI 0.01 to 0.38 kcal·min⁻¹) and the GT3X+ (CCC = 0.01; 95% CI 0.02 to 0.03 kcal·min⁻¹). The mean bias between iPhone and IC was -2.0 kcal·min⁻¹ (95%

LOA -5.5 to 1.6 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) whereas between GT3X+ and IC the mean bias was -4.8 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (95% LOA -7.2 to -2.5 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$).

The iPhone (3.8 ± 0.8 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) significantly underestimated EE during the aerobics activity in comparison to the criterion method (7.5 ± 1.6 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$). There was no difference between EE estimated by the GT3X+ (8.4 ± 1.3 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and the criterion method ($P = 0.120$). There was poor agreement between the criterion method and estimates of EE with both the iPhone (CCC = 0.10; 95% CI 0.03 to 0.17 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and the GT3X+ (CCC = 0.62; 95% CI 0.33 to 0.80 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$). The mean bias between the iPhone and criterion method was -3.8 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (95% LOA -6.0 to -1.5 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), whereas between GT3X+ and criterion method the mean bias was 0.9 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (95% LOA -1.1 to 2.9 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$).

4.3.2 Phase 2: Free living

The average daily wear-time of the GT3X+ was 731 ± 89 $\text{minutes}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. There was substantial agreement in the measurement of step count between the iPhone (7990 ± 4673 $\text{steps}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) and GT3X+ (9085 ± 4647 $\text{steps}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) (CCC = 0.894; 95% CI 0.86 to 0.92 $\text{steps}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$), with a mean difference of -1095 $\text{steps}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (95% LOA -4780 to 2591 $\text{steps}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) (Figure 4-3). Daily step count measured by the iPhone was significantly lower than the GT3X+ ($P < 0.001$). The Bland and Altman plot (Figure 4-3) shows a large spread, with 10 data points above or below the 95% LOA which have a range of ~ 7000 steps.

Figure 4-3: Bland and Altman plot of daily iPhone steps versus daily GT3X+ steps during a free living study with mean bias (solid line) and 95% limits of agreement (dashed lines).

4.4 Discussion

The primary purpose of this study was to assess the validity of the iPhone 5S for estimating step count and EE during laboratory-based physical activities. We compared step counts from the iPhone 5S and a research-grade accelerometer (GT3X+) to the criterion method. Both devices were found to provide valid estimates of step count during walking and jogging on a treadmill. The GT3X+ was also found to provide accurate estimates of EE during treadmill walking and jogging but the iPhone significantly underestimated EE compared to IC. A further objective was to compare estimates of step count between the iPhone 5S and GT3X+ during a two-week period of free living. We found that the iPhone recorded significantly fewer daily steps compared to the GT3X+.

In the treadmill component of the laboratory trial, the iPhone provided near perfect estimates of step count compared to MC, whereas the GT3X+ provided moderate estimates of step count compared to the criterion method. Both the iPhone and GT3X+ were most accurate at the vigorous ($8.0 \pm 1.1 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) intensity and least accurate at the moderate intensity ($6.5 \pm 0.9 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$). This suggests that the relationship between the accuracy of the GT3X+/iPhone and speed is not linear, as previously reported (Lee et al., 2015; Major and Alford, 2016). However, the difference in accuracy of the iPhone between intensities was very minimal, with MAPEs ranging from 0.6% to 1.5%, whereas the GT3X+ ranged from 1.2% to 6.9%. Contrastingly, the iPhone was least accurate at estimating EE at the vigorous intensity and performed best at light intensity ($5.4 \pm 1.0 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), when compared to the criterion method of IC.

The GT3X+ on average overestimated EE at all speeds and was least accurate at the light intensity, while performing best at moderate intensity when compared to IC. Previous studies comparing the GT3X+ to IC have also found the device to overestimate EE at speeds comparable to those in the current study but to underestimate at faster running speeds, higher intensity activities, and at much slower walking speeds ($2.6 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) (Gastin et al., 2018; McMinn et al., 2013). Despite this apparent systematic bias, novel EE equations that are gender specific or that incorporate other metrics into the prediction equations have previously improved the accuracy of the GT3X+ in comparison to those available in the Actilife software (Santos-Lozano et al., 2013; Howe, Moir, & Easton, 2017).

During stationary cycling, the iPhone and GT3X+ significantly underestimated EE and had poor agreement with IC. The likely reason for the consistent underestimation of EE during stationary cycling is due to the stable position of the trunk where both the iPhone and GT3X+ were located. The adoption of a lower-limb accelerometer placement has previously been shown to improve the accuracy of pedal-revolution count during cycling when compared to waist-placement (Gatti et al., 2016). During aerobics, the iPhone significantly overestimated steps compared to the GT3X+ and underestimated EE compared to IC, with poor agreement for both comparisons. There was poor agreement between the GT3X+ estimations of EE compared to IC, however methods were not significantly different. The poor agreement between the iPhone and GT3X+ compared to IC during the aerobics trial suggests that both methods are unsuitable for monitoring EE during exercise that is not steady-state. The iPhone's overestimation of steps compared to the GT3X+ during aerobics suggests that it may not be suitable for monitoring exercise that requires non-uniform movement patterns.

In the free living component of the study, the agreement in daily step count between the iPhone and GT3X+ devices was substantial although the iPhone, recorded significantly fewer steps (1095 steps·day⁻¹). It is not possible to ascertain the precise reason for this discord although user behaviour with the iPhone devices seems a likely explanation. While participants wore the GT3X+ attached to their waist, they were instructed to carry the iPhone as they would their own personal phone to ensure an ecologically valid measurement method. Depending on the individual, the iPhone may have been regularly left on a surface or carried in a bag. Participants may have been less likely to carry the iPhone on their person as it was additional to their own phone. Unfortunately, there was no way to monitor “wear-time” of the iPhone so this hypothesis remains speculative.

Further research on the validity, reliability, and sensitivity of smartphones to measure PA is clearly warranted. Developing a convenient and widely-used method for monitoring free living PA would facilitate greater understanding of population PA levels and enable data sharing with HCPs using a DHP. However, the daily step count metric does not enable a nuanced interpretation of PA as it lacks information on context, duration, frequency and intensity of the activity. Intensity in particular is important as the NHS’ current PA guidelines recommend that adults should undertake 150 min of moderate intensity exercise or 75 min of vigorous activity per week (UK Chief Medical Officer’s Guidelines, 2011). The development of smartphone-specific algorithms to estimate the intensity of PA from the inbuilt accelerometer would generate a substantially more informative data set. The interpretation of the data may be further enhanced if other metrics such as GPS data, (Gordon, Bruce and Benson, 2016) or HR data can be combined with measurements of acceleration.

There are a few limitations of the current study. Firstly, the iPhone 5S model was used which utilises the M7 motion coprocessor technology whereas the most recent generation of iPhones (iPhone 11, 11 Pro and SE) have M13 co-processors. It is unclear how advancements in the coprocessor technology would influence the measurement of step count and EE. Secondly, estimations of EE from the iPhone were generated by the 'ActivityTracker' app using an algorithm based on acceleration, gender, BM and stature. The algorithm itself is unbeknown to the researchers and is likely to be different to estimates of EE from other apps. Thirdly, the treadmill speeds which corresponded with light, moderate and vigorous intensities ranged from 5.4 ± 1.0 to 8 ± 1.1 km·h⁻¹ based on measurements of HRR. Future studies should incorporate slower and faster speeds in more homogenous groups of participants. Lastly, while the iPhone significantly underestimated steps during free living compared to the GT3X+, the GT3X+ itself is not a gold-standard method for measuring free living PA. Moreover, as no gold-standard methods exist for this type of PA monitoring, the concurrent validation of one measure against another will inevitably involve a degree of uncertainty.

4.5 Conclusion

The iPhone 5S is a suitable method of measuring step count but not EE during walking and jogging. In the free living phase of the study, the iPhone significantly underestimated daily step count compared to an accelerometer worn continuously around the waist. This is likely because the phone was not carried on the person as frequently as the accelerometer. Further optimisation of the prediction algorithms in the mobile apps to incorporate measurements of HR and/or GPS data may enhance iPhone estimates of EE (Howe, Moir and Easton, 2017) and provide a more accurate and informative data set on PA and SB patterns. Finally, when using smartphones

such as the iPhone 5S to measure step count, users should be cognisant that there may be a significant underestimation of daily steps.

CHAPTER 5: Study 2 - A Mixed-Methods Study to Explore the Use of Smartphones in Estimating Physical Activity during Free Living

5.1 Introduction

PA greatly reduces the risk of non-communicable and age-related disease (Reiner *et al.*, 2013) as well as mortality (Blair *et al.*, 1989); therefore, accurate and pragmatic methods to measure PA are of immense value to consumers, researchers and health professionals alike. Subjective self-report methods are cost-effective and are typically used to gather data on population levels of PA (Hallal *et al.*, 2012). Conversely, several large-scale studies have utilised accelerometers in an attempt to obtain more objective assessments of PA and SB (Doherty *et al.*, 2017; Shiroma *et al.*, 2013). These unobtrusive devices enable continuous measurements of body movement which can be further analysed to estimate the frequency, intensity and duration of PA. While accelerometers have been shown to have good validity and reliability (Tudor-Locke, Barreira and Schuna, 2015; Jarrett, Fitzgerald and Routen, 2015), they are primarily designed for research studies and require costly software and research expertise to analyse PA data.

On the other hand, smartphones such as the iPhone 5S (Apple Inc., Cupertino, CA) are purposefully designed for the consumer market. These devices include a motion coprocessor which analyses sensor data from an in-built tri-axial accelerometer, gyroscope, GPS, and barometer (recent models only). With the use of proprietary algorithms, these data can be integrated to estimate markers of PA, including the number of steps taken each day (step count), distance travelled, and flights of stairs climbed. Users can view their PA metrics within the first-party iPhone 'Health' app which is pre-installed on iPhones or available to download from the App store. Users can also install a range of third-party apps which provide additional functionality, including PA goal setting, updates on daily progress, and the setting of reminders and notifications. Given that smartphones are owned by the vast majority of adults, there is

potential to utilise this technology for population-based measurements of PA and SB. Furthermore, smartphones also enable straightforward sharing of data via apps or cloud-based platforms which could then be monitored by a healthcare professional or researcher. As studies are already adopting the smartphone as a PA monitor (Althoff *et al.*, 2017) and walking is the main type of PA undertaken by the global population (Hulteen *et al.*, 2017) with multifarious benefits to health (Morris and Hardman, 1997), it is important that we understand the validity and limitations of estimated step count from smartphones.

The iPhone 5S was previously found, when worn in a pouch around the waist, to be almost perfect at counting steps during treadmill walking and jogging at various speeds when compared to the criterion method (Thomson *et al.*, 2021). In a free-living setting, however, the iPhone 5S measured significantly fewer steps than a research-grade accelerometer (ActiGraph GT3X+, ActiGraph LLC, Pensacola, FL), 7990 ± 4673 steps·day⁻¹ vs 9085 ± 4647 steps·day⁻¹, respectively (Thomson *et al.*, 2021). It is unclear at present whether this disagreement was due to technological differences in the hardware and/or software between the devices or was instead a consequence of smartphone user behaviours. In this study, the GT3X+ was worn continuously around the waist whereas participants were asked to carry the iPhone as they normally would their personal phone (Thomson *et al.*, 2021). It is quite possible that the storage location of the smartphone during rest and locomotion (e.g. inside a pocket or a bag) may have influenced these outcomes. Moreover, the smartphone may not have been carried on the person at all during movement indoors or during participation in sport or other PA. Another study compared participant's own, naturally used, iPhone to a GT3X+ worn on the right hip over 3 days and also found that the iPhone on average significantly undercounted steps compared to the GT3X+ (Duncan *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, the iPhone (5S or newer) was tested when used naturally during free living against a pedometer (Kenz Lifecorder Ex; Suzuken Co. Ltd., Nagoya, Japan)

and, again, was found to significantly underestimate daily step count (Amagasa *et al.*, 2019). However, both these studies did not objectively determine a measurement of iPhone wear-time, instead utilising self-report diaries/questionnaires for participants to state how often they had the phone with them.

Several other studies have shown that smartphones can provide accurate measures of step count within a controlled, laboratory setting regardless of placement on the body (Höchsmann *et al.*, 2018; Johnson *et al.*, 2016). Under free-living conditions, an Android smartphone (Google Nexus One) was found to provide comparable estimates of daily PA compared to the ActiGraph GT3X+ (Hekler *et al.*, 2015). However, participants were specifically instructed to continuously carry the smartphone, either on their hip along with the GT3X+ or in their pocket. Another study tested the iPhone SE worn in the front trouser pocket under free-living conditions and found it systematically underestimated daily steps compared to their criterion method - StepWatch™ 3 (Modus Health, LLC, Edmonds, WA, USA), worn on the ankle (Höchsmann *et al.*, 2020). It is still uncertain, therefore, whether habitual use of a smartphone can provide an accurate measurement of PA. Consequently, the primary aim of this study was to evaluate the convergent validity of a user's own iPhone for measuring daily step count by comparing to both an iPhone and GT3X+ accelerometer that were continuously worn around the waist in healthy adults. We hypothesised that the user's own device would record fewer steps compared to both other devices. In line with the confirmatory nature of this investigation, the study protocol was established a priori. A secondary aim was to explore, using a qualitative approach, the habits of each user with their mobile device during the monitoring period, their previous experience with wearable technologies for PA monitoring, and their perception on the use of smartphones to measure PA and SB.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Participants

Fifteen adults volunteered to take part: ten females and five males (mean \pm SD: age 31 ± 9 years, stature 169 ± 8 cm and BM 75.7 ± 13.8 kg). Inclusion criteria consisted of participants being ≥ 18 years and using an iPhone 5S or newer as their current personal phone (Table 5-1).

Table 5-1: Personal iPhone used by participants.

iPhone Model	No. of Participants
<i>iPhone 6</i>	1
<i>iPhone 6S</i>	3
<i>iPhone SE</i>	2
<i>iPhone 7</i>	2
<i>iPhone 8</i>	1
<i>iPhone 8 Plus</i>	3
<i>iPhone X</i>	1
<i>iPhone XS Max</i>	1

5.2.2 Procedures

Participants attended the laboratory to enable measurement of stature (cm) and BM (kg) and to verify their personal iPhone was fully operational. To ensure the step count function was enabled and collating data within the 'Health' app, the lead researcher walked around the laboratory while holding the participant's phone. Participants were given an iPhone 5S (waist iPhone) and a GT3X+ accelerometer (ActiGraph LLC) and asked to wear both around the waist in a neoprene pouch (Figure 5-1), for seven days. They were instructed to ensure the devices sat on the anterior-superior iliac spine of the right hip and were removed only for sleep, bathing, or swimming. Participants were also given a diary to record extended periods of non-wear-time. Participants were asked to use their personal iPhone as they normally would over the 7-day period.

Figure 5-1: Front view of the iPhone and GT3X+ worn around the waist in a neoprene pouch.

5.2.3 Instruments

iPhone 5S and GT3X+'s were utilised to concurrently measure step count. More details on both can be found in section 3.4 in chapter 3.

5.2.4 Data Processing

Data were processed as per section 3.8 in chapter 3. The iPhone does not give a direct measurement of wear-time and, to the authors' knowledge, there are no established methods to calculate this outcome. Consequently, waist and personal iPhone daily wear-time was estimated as the number of hours that had at least one recorded step. In order to compare daily wear-time across devices, GT3X+ wear-time is reported as hours (to the nearest hour).

5.2.5 Interviews

After the 7-day period, twelve participants: seven females and five males (mean \pm SD: 30 \pm 8 years old) took part in a short semi-structured interview. This included focused and specific questions regarding the participant's previous experience of personal PA monitoring using mobile devices, wear-time of the study instruments and personal habits with their own iPhone. Prior to the interview, the hourly step count data from both the waist iPhone and personal iPhones were collated in a spreadsheet to inform the interview questions about wear-time and personal habits. The mean duration of the interviews was 10 minutes (range 4 to 18 min). Interviews were conducted as per section 3.7 in chapter 3.

5.2.6 Data Analysis

All data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Bland and Altman analysis (Bland and Altman, 1986) was used to assess the agreement between step count estimates from the waist iPhone, GT3X+ and personal iPhone. Step count data were not normally distributed; therefore, a Friedman test was run to determine whether there was a difference in step count between

measurement methods. Pairwise comparisons were performed with a Durbin-Conover correction for multiple comparisons. Wear-time data was normally distributed; therefore, a one-way repeated measures ANOVA was run to determine if there was a difference in wear-time between measurement methods. Post hoc analysis was performed with a Tukey adjustment for multiple comparisons.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 *Wear-time and step count*

For reasons unknown, no data was collected on the waist iPhone for one participant. Therefore, data from fourteen participants were analysed (nine females and five males). The wear-time of the personal iPhone (12 ± 2 hours·day⁻¹) was significantly less than both the waist worn devices: waist iPhone (14 ± 2 hours·day⁻¹; $P = 0.01$) and GT3X+ (13 ± 1 hours·day⁻¹; $P = 0.02$). There was no significant difference between waist iPhone and GT3X+ ($P = 0.97$). Participants recorded an average of 6 ± 1 days of valid data (range 4 – 7 days).

Step count data from each device are presented in Figure 5-2. The waist iPhone recorded significantly more steps than the personal iPhone ($P < 0.001$), with a mean difference of 1284 steps·day⁻¹ (95% LOA -2869 to 5436 steps·day⁻¹). The difference between waist iPhone and the GT3X+ daily step count was not significant ($P = 0.399$), with a mean difference of 371 steps·day⁻¹ (95% LOA -3099 to 3842 steps·day⁻¹). The personal iPhone recorded significantly fewer steps than the GT3X+ ($P = 0.03$), with a mean difference of -882 steps·day⁻¹ (-5825 to 4060 steps·day⁻¹). Bland and Altman plots of all comparisons, expressing the mean bias and

LOA, can be viewed in Figure 5-3. Individual participant examples of daily step count data demonstrating poor agreement (a) and good agreement (b) between instruments can be viewed in Figure 5-4.

Figure 5-2: Mean (SD) daily step count of GT3X+, participants' personal iPhone and waist-worn iPhone (Waist iPhone). * denotes statistical significance between instruments.

Figure 5-3: Bland and Altman plots of: (a) participants' personal iPhone and waist-worn iPhone (waist iPhone) daily step count; (b) waist iPhone and GT3X+ daily step count and (c) personal iPhone and GT3X+ daily step count during a 7-day free living period with mean bias (solid line) and 95% limits of agreement (dashed lines).

Figure 5-4: Daily step count of GT3X+, participants' personal iPhone and waist-worn iPhone (Waist iPhone) for two individual participants: (a) participant 14 (b) participant 7. For participant 14 (a), wear-time of the GT3X+, personal iPhone and waist iPhone was 13, 8 and 15 hours·day⁻¹ respectively. For participant 7 (b), wear-time of the GT3X+, personal iPhone and waist iPhone was 15, 14 and 15 hours·day⁻¹ respectively.

5.3.2 Interviews

Themes and subthemes were generated from the thematic analyses of interview transcripts are presented in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2: Themes and sub-themes from thematic analysis of twelve qualitative interviews.

Themes	Subthemes
1 – Physical Activity Monitoring	<i>1.a – Previous physical activity monitoring</i> <i>1.b – Physical activity monitoring in future</i>
2 – Physical Activity	<i>2.a – Being physically active without devices</i> <i>2.b – Reasons for 0 steps counted on iPhones</i>
3 – Wearing Devices	<i>3.a – Comfort</i> <i>3.b – Personal iPhone location</i> <i>3.c – Wear-time</i>

5.3.2.1 PA monitoring

Previous PA monitoring. Almost all participants had self-monitored their PA prior to taking part in the study using either a wearable device or a smartphone app. The experience of prior monitoring ranged from 10 months to 5 years. The devices or apps previously used by participants are detailed in Table 5-3. One participant had taken part in self-monitoring of health outcomes using a pedometer and BP monitor, “*blood (pressure), yes mainly yes, but then*

y’know tied to that was weight and levels of activity” (Participant 7), as instructed by their primary physician (General Practitioner (GP)).

Table 5-3: Wearables and smartphone applications previously used by participants.

Wearables	Mobile Apps	No. of Participants
<i>Fitbit Watch</i>		5
<i>Apple Watch</i>		3
	<i>Nike Plus</i>	1
	<i>Apple Health</i>	1
<i>Suunto Shoe Pod</i>		1
<i>Garmin Watch</i>		1

The reasons for PA monitoring were evenly split between participants with some monitoring only structured exercise “*not necessarily general physical activity*” (Participant 8) such as running and/or swimming. Others were more interested in their daily PA metrics such as steps and HR and to “*track my movement and see how active I was to encourage me to stop sitting around so much*” (Participant 9). All participants who had previously monitored their PA found doing so useful, with several reporting that “*it actually did encourage me to be more active*” (participant 9):

...it gives me a good idea and it's just that little bit of incentive sometimes to see that you're close to reaching a certain amount of steps or reaching your goals for the day (Participant 5).

...I mean it does help when you get the notification that you've been sitting for too long ehm it does prompt you to stand up and walk around and I do get the notifications when I've reached the goals (Participant 10).

Just for monitoring process like if you... it's good for just seeing your improvements in your 5K times or ehm your splits on kilometres ehm so I quite like it for setting goals and monitoring process in the activity as well (Participant 13).

PA monitoring in future. Participants were asked how they would feel, hypothetically, about taking part in the same kind of PA monitoring over an extended period of time in the future, if asked to do so by their general practitioner (GP). All participants described how they would be happy to, with some stipulating that there would need to be a reason – *“I will ask the GP why they want to do this... Yeah if it's for my benefit why not ...”* (Participant 3):

I think it would be fine, I don't think I'd have any problems with it ehm and the GP would obviously have a reason for it and I tend to do what the GP says ehm but yeah no I wouldn't see any problems with it (Participant 4).

Many participants pointed out that if the PA monitoring involved “*just monitoring through my phone as opposed to having additional stuff on me*” (Participant 13) it would be preferable. One participant also mentioned that they would prefer the type of PA monitoring utilised in the current study over other methods such as “*a diary account - that would be worse*” (Participant 6).

5.3.2.2 PA

Being physically active without devices. Participants were asked if they could recollect engaging in any sustained bouts of PA during the monitoring period without wearing the waist-mounted devices. One participant had forgotten they had taken their devices off before going for a dog walk (Participant 1). Another had deliberately removed them to attend a concert and a yoga session (Participant 8). Two participants removed them prior to going swimming and another before they went to the gym (Participant 4).

Reasons for 0 steps counted on iPhones. When the interviewer highlighted specific periods of non-wear-time with the waist-worn iPhone device, most participants stated the reasons as SB – “*...yeah that 2 hour period is related to unfortunately me sitting at a desk doing nothing*” (Participant 10).

Some specified that they had either “*forgotten to wear it*” (Participant 1) or taken it off unusually early for bed “*cause one time I was really tired*” (Participant 3). The most common reason for the recording of non-wear-time on a participant’s personal iPhone was that they had

left the phone sitting on a surface – “...when we’re in the house I don’t carry it around with me ehm so it will either just sit on the worktop or sit on the sofa” (Participant 6).

Participants also highlighted that some of the non-wear-time with their personal iPhone was periods of SB - either “watching a film sitting on the sofa” (Participant 12) or “sat at my desk” (Participant 5).

5.3.2.3 Wearing devices

Comfort. Generally, participants described wearing the accelerometer and waist iPhone around their waist in a pouch to be reasonably comfortable overall, although for some there was a bit of an adjustment period where they “found it uncomfortable to begin with” (Participant 12) or found it to be uncomfortable “depending on what angle it was sitting at if I’d moved I was like oh yeah that’s there and kind’ve just adjusted it so it was sitting comfortably” (Participant 9). One participant described it to be:

...uncomfortable in the car ‘cause it would yeah you had the your seatbelt on it and it would kind’ve be a bit weird, but you could just move it a little to the left or right and it would be... Yeah, not crazy uncomfortable, bit of a faff getting like changed or something and having to like move it around (Participant 8).

Another felt that when the weather was “really warm it was a bit uncomfortable at times” (Participant 1).

Personal phone location. Almost all of the participants reported that they usually keep their phone within a pocket of their clothes (trouser or hooded sweatshirt/jacket pocket), with one participant stating they typically have theirs “*in my hand, ehm if I’m at the weekend it would’ve been in my bag which it would’ve been normally on my right shoulder*” (Participant 2). Some reported that if they are “*in the office I put it on the desk*” (Participant 8) or when they’re “*at home it just sits on the sofa or just sits somewhere*” (Participant 6).

Wear-time. All but one participant reported that they wore the devices around their waist every day and that they mostly wore them “*from when I’d wake up to when I’d go to bed so I’d be like wearing it the whole day*” (Participant 5), with participants generally only removing the devices if they were “*getting changed or going for a shower*” (Participant 12), or for the specific reasons detailed in a previous section. One participant had an issue with the strap of the pouch enclosing the waist iPhone and GT3X+ and therefore did not wear the devices on that particular day, subsequently reporting:

It did make me a little bit more like ugh can’t be bothered wearing this but yeah I think part of being in a study was the commitment to it but I do think that if this was me just wearing it in my own personal life that I would have disengaged from it quite quickly and I would have just left it and I wouldn’t have bothered if I’m being honest (Participant 12).

5.4 Discussion

This study sought to determine whether a personal smartphone would provide accurate estimates of PA within an ecologically valid setting. Specifically, we evaluated the convergent validity of a user's own iPhone for measuring daily step count by comparing to both an iPhone and GT3X+ accelerometer that were continuously worn around the waist. The primary finding was that a user's personal iPhone recorded significantly fewer daily steps than an iPhone and GT3X+ accelerometer that were worn continuously around the waist. The analysis of wear-time data confirms that their personal iPhone was carried on their person (e.g. in a pocket) for less time per day than the waist-mounted devices. Participants suggested that, in most cases, this was due to their personal device being left on a surface at work or in their home. These data have important implications when considering the potential of using mobile devices to assess PA and SB in the population.

It has been previously reported that the iPhone 5S recorded significantly fewer steps than a waist-worn GT3X+ accelerometer during two weeks of free living (Thomson *et al.*, 2021). However, it was not clear whether this discordance was due to technological differences between the devices or the location of smartphone storage during daily living. For example, there may be differences in sampling frequency and algorithms for counting steps. The present study confirms that a personal iPhone records significantly fewer steps (12.6%) than a waist-worn GT3X+ and significantly extends these findings by demonstrating that a personal iPhone also records significantly fewer steps (16.8%) than a waist-worn iPhone. This confirms that user habits with their smartphone (including wear-time) is the primary cause for the underestimation of step count by the iPhone 5S. Using established methods for estimating

accelerometer wear-time (Van Dyck *et al.*, 2015), the data suggests that participants had the GT3X+ attached to their person for 13 ± 1 hours·day⁻¹. On the other hand, an hour-by-hour analysis of the waist iPhone and personal iPhone suggests that the waist iPhone was worn around the waist for 14 ± 2 hours·day⁻¹, whereas the personal iPhone was carried on their person for 12 ± 2 hours·day⁻¹, significantly less than both the waist iPhone and GT3X+.

Qualitative data from the semi-structured interviews revealed the likely explanation for this is that participants would not carry their personal iPhone on their person when at work or inside the home. Similarly, in a previously mentioned study participants reported through the use of a diary that they did not take their iPhone to the washroom or other short walking breaks (Duncan *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, the waist-worn devices would record steps during short, but potentially frequent, bouts of walking in these environments but the personal iPhone would not. While the data from most individual participants aligned with the group-level analysis (e.g. consistently lower step counts from the personal iPhone), this was not always the case. Figure 5-4 presents two contrasting participants to illustrate the range of behaviours observed and their influence on measurement validity. Participant 14 (Figure 5-4a) was selected as a representative case of inconsistent smartphone use; their personal iPhone recorded substantially fewer steps than the GT3X+ and waist-worn iPhone across the week. This underestimation aligns with the lower wear-time for the personal iPhone (8 hours·day⁻¹), compared to 13 and 15 hours·day⁻¹, for the GT3X+ and waist iPhone, respectively. In contrast, participant 7 (Figure 5-4b) was chosen to demonstrate high compliance, with similar step counts across all devices and consistent wear-time (14–15 hours·day⁻¹). These examples further exemplify the impact of inter-individual variability in smartphone user habits on the measurement accuracy of the devices.

It may also be suggested that the precise storage location of the personal iPhone when worn on the person may also contribute to the underestimation of step count measurement in comparison with the waist-worn devices. Participants predominantly carried their personal iPhone in a clothing pocket (e.g. jacket/trousers) which, for some individuals, varied according to daily circumstances. However, previous research has shown the iPhone SE provides an accurate measurement of step count during treadmill and free-walking, irrespective of whether it was placed in a trouser pocket, a shoulder bag or a backpack (Höchstmann *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, the iPhone 4S was found to be an accurate step counter compared to MC when worn in two different locations (chest pocket and front trouser pocket) while walking on a hard, flat surface within a controlled-setting (Åkerberg, Söderlund and Lindén, 2016).

In the current study, participant's personal iPhone underestimated daily step count by an average of 1284 steps·day⁻¹, compared to an iPhone worn continuously on the waist. This number of missed steps is potentially clinically relevant. For example, a recent systematic review and meta-analysis concluded that increasing daily steps by increments of 1000 per day corresponded to proportional reductions in arterial stiffness, a key marker of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality (Cavero-Redondo *et al.*, 2019). Increasing daily step count by ~2000 steps·day⁻¹ has also been shown to reduce waist circumference and BMI in both adult men and women (Dwyer *et al.*, 2007). Furthermore, pedometer interventions have been shown to increase step count by, on average, 2000 steps·day⁻¹ (Kang *et al.*, 2009), with subsequent reductions in BM and BP (Bravata *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, an underestimation of daily step count of 1284 steps·day⁻¹ needs to be seriously considered when choosing to use the iPhone as a PA monitor. However, participants in the current study reported that they would prefer to

monitor their PA with their own smartphone rather than having to wear a device on their body. Therefore, if individuals were asked to monitor their PA at home by their medical practitioner, compliance may be higher if they are able to use their own smartphone device. Implementation of the iPhone wear-time calculation method developed in the current study could give a greater sense of the level of accuracy of the individuals' smartphone measurement, as there is a clear relationship between wear-time and step count accuracy.

Almost all participants had done some level of PA monitoring with wearables and/or apps previously, with reasons evenly split between wanting to monitor structured exercise such as running, and more general monitoring of daily PA metrics, e.g. HR and step count. Participants reported perceived benefits from previous PA monitoring such as: facilitated goal setting; notifications and reminders to incentivise meeting goals; and less SB due to prompts to get up and move. These findings are consistent with previous studies investigating the use of PA wearables and/or apps (Middelweerd et al., 2015; Casey et al., 2014), and there has been some evidence of modest health benefits in recent randomised control trials (Stiglbauer, Weber and Batinic, 2019; Glynn et al., 2014). However, more work is needed on whether this type of self-monitoring subsequently promotes long-term behavioural change and improves health markers.

This is the first study, to our knowledge, that has compared daily step counts from an iPhone worn continuously around the waist to participant's own iPhone used normally in daily life. By using a mixed-methods approach, we were able to gain insight on user behaviour with smartphones that would otherwise be missed with a quantitative-only methodology. However, there are some limitations. We compared the iPhone, used naturally over 7 days, to an iPhone

5S and GT3X+ worn around the waist in a pouch. These waist mounted devices also suffer from the same limitations as a personal phone as participants also removed these devices for periods or forgot to wear them. This is a common issue, but it suggests that both methods (waist-worn and personal use) are likely to underestimate true PA levels. Also, the participants had different models of iPhone, the release date of which spanned four-years, as it was not possible to recruit a sufficient number of participants that used an iPhone 5S as their personal smartphone; therefore, it is uncertain whether that could explain the significant difference in daily step count between the iPhones. This limitation was unavoidable, as the primary objective of the study was to evaluate the influence of users' habitual, real-world smartphone use on step count measurement accuracy. Future studies should look to repeat our study in a cohort of participants using the same smartphone model as the one worn on the waist to eliminate this uncertainty. Lastly, almost all participants had some previous experience of PA monitoring with the use of wearables and/or apps, which is not representative of the general population in the UK (Strain, Wijndaele and Brage, 2019). On one hand, not normalising the data for wear-time may be considered a limitation, however the current approach provides novel insight into how an individual's behaviour with their personal smartphone impacted measurements of PA (i.e step count). If the data had been normalised for wear-time, this key insight would be lost.

In conclusion, participants' personal iPhone recorded significantly fewer daily steps than an iPhone and GT3X+ accelerometer worn continuously around the waist for seven days. Therefore, utilising the smartphone as a PA monitoring device should only be considered as an estimate of daily step count. We recommend that users consider this underestimation of objective PA when interpreting their data and be aware that the accuracy of their smartphone to measure habitual PA is directly related to how often they have it with them and on their person.

CHAPTER 6: Study 3 - Evaluation of a DHP: The Usability and Feasibility of the Lenus Health Platform within Healthy Adults and Healthcare Professionals.

6.1 Funding and collaboration

This PhD was funded by the DHI and conducted in collaboration with Lenus Health (Lenus Health Ltd, UK), a UK-based software engineering company formerly part of Storm ID (Storm ID Ltd, UK).

6.2 Introduction

Remote monitoring of health and wellbeing using mobile technology, known as telemonitoring, is a concept that is widely accepted to have major implications for improving the patient experience, as well as reducing demand on primary and secondary care services (Banbury, Roots and Nancarrow, 2014). Mobile health (m-health) technologies are suggested to facilitate healthcare provision in high and low-income countries alike (Hoque and Sorwar, 2017). Digital m-health, or telemonitoring, platforms that enable the remote monitoring of patients' health may reduce the need for face-to-face communication with HCPs, thereby potentially reducing the burden on healthcare systems. With the current COVID-19 pandemic resulting in global societal lockdowns to interrupt further human-to-human transmission (WHO, 2020), the necessity for this type of remote monitoring has never been more evident.

Recent advancements in m-health technologies have empowered patients to self-record their own health metrics and review the data using a mobile app or web-based platform. Some platforms display repeated measurements of data over time which enables patients to gain a visual representation of how certain lifestyle changes influence key health markers (Appel, 2003). This can empower individuals to take ownership and confidently self-monitor their health (Jones *et al.*, 2012). For example, Bluetooth enabled BP monitors enable the wireless

measurement of a key marker of cardiovascular health that can be recorded via an associated app. Self-monitoring of BP at home has been shown to have acceptable reproducibility (Stergiou *et al.*, 2007), reduce the risk of “white coat hypertension” (Padwal *et al.*, 2007), and lower the healthcare costs of the treatment for hypertension and related complications (Ohkubo *et al.*, 2004; Imai *et al.*, 1993).

From the perspective of HCPs, home monitoring of key clinical outcomes such as BP may lead to more rapid or aggressive treatment (Agarwal *et al.*, 2011). However, HCPs have also expressed apprehension over remotely monitoring patients with concerns of increased workload, cost and the move away from the traditional face-to-face approach (Wild *et al.*, 2015). Conversely, a recent randomised controlled trial found that a significant number of patients preferred a virtual clinic in comparison to attending a typical outpatient clinic for a routine follow-up post-surgical discharge (Healy *et al.*, 2018). The authors of this study concluded that follow-up visits for most general surgical conditions are not only unnecessary but could also delay HCPs seeing new patients. McCartney (2017) has previously stressed the need for rigorous testing of health platforms and apps prior to their adoption, particularly when artificial intelligence is involved (McCartney, 2018). Therefore, prior to integrating a DHP within healthcare systems around the world, the usability, feasibility and acceptability of the platform needs to be evaluated.

The Lenus Health Platform is an app programming interface (API) developed by Lenus Health (Lenus Health Ltd, UK), a UK-based software engineering company, formerly part of Storm ID (Storm ID Ltd, UK). The platform provides a consent model that enforces data interoperability and security and is compliant with the general data protection regulation

(GDPR) that harmonises data privacy laws across Europe (Schulz and Hennis-Plasschaert, 2016). The Lenus Health Platform is internet-based and uses integrated mobile apps and m-health devices to enable patients to generate, control and securely share their data through digitally enabled pathways (*Lenus Health*, 2020). By providing HCPs access to this data within a single platform, there is the potential to reduce outpatient waiting times and rehospitalisation rates, empower patients, improve health outcomes, and improve patient access to care.

Despite this, the usability, feasibility and acceptability of the Lenus Health Platform has not been subject to independent evaluation. Therefore, the aims of the current study were firstly to determine the usability of the Lenus Health Platform and associated apps in a sample of healthy adults fulfilling the role of secondary care patients (mock patients). Secondly, to determine the usability of the Lenus Health Platform in a sample of HCPs currently working in the UK's publicly funded healthcare system, the NHS. This study is a necessary first step to demonstrate "proof of concept" prior to evaluation within a live healthcare system.

6.3 Methods

6.3.1 Research design

The study was completed in two distinct parts. In part 1, a convenience sample of healthy adults were provided with a mock healthcare scenario in which they would be required to self-monitor a range of health outcomes and share these data with the research team via the Lenus Health Platform. At the end of the monitoring phase, a semi-structured interview was conducted to discuss their experience. In part 2, a purposive sample of HCPs all currently working within

the NHS were provided with access to the Lenus Health Platform and mock patient data. Following a period of review, the HCPs discussed the usability, feasibility and acceptability of the Lenus Health Platform in a semi-structured interview.

6.3.1.1 Part 1- 'Mock patients'.

Twenty adults volunteered to take part in the study but two withdrew prior to the end of the monitoring period. The eighteen participants who completed the study comprised eleven females and seven males age (mean \pm SD) 42 ± 17 years old (range: 23 – 67). The inclusion criteria stipulated that participants were 18-75 years old, were able to read and write in English, and were without terminal illness.

6.3.1.1.1 Procedures

At the outset of the study, participants met with members of the research team to receive detailed written and verbal instructions. The written instructions set forth a mock healthcare scenario, in which the participant was to fulfil the role of a 'patient'. In this scenario, they were receiving specialist secondary care following an initial referral by their primary healthcare provider (general practitioner). As part of the secondary care process, the patients were asked to self-monitor their BP, BM, and PA as these are primary risk factors for disease risk/mortality (Kannel, 1996; Troiano *et al.*, 1996; Warburton, Nicol and Bredin, 2006). Participants were given an iPhone (iPhone 5S, Apple Inc., USA), a set of electronic weighing scales (Electronic Bathroom Scales, VonHaus, DOMU Brands Ltd, UK), and an upper arm automated BP monitor

with Bluetooth connection (UA-651BLE, A&D Medical, USA) and were shown how to use each device. Participants were directed to contact the research team by phone or email should they have any technical difficulties.

In the subsequent two weeks, participants collected measurements of self-monitored BP, BM and PA using the Lenus Health Platform associated iPhone apps (Figure 6-1): ‘Blood Pressure’ (BP app); ‘Body Composition’ (BC app); and ‘Pedometer’ (pedometer app). Participants were asked to measure their BP once in the morning and once at night by attaching the BP cuff around the upper arm while resting in a seated position, opening the BP app and pressing the ‘start’ button on the BP monitor. Their BP measurement, HR and the date would then appear on the app, communicated via Bluetooth, as a data entry and as part of a graph. Participants were then instructed to press the ‘authorise’ and ‘send measurements’ buttons in order for the measurements to be sent to the cloud-based Lenus Health Platform via an internet connection. Participants were also asked to weigh themselves twice over the fortnight and to manually input the data and subsequently ‘authorise’ and ‘send measurements’ through the BC app. Daily step count data was measured by the iPhone 5S (section 3.4.3, chapter 3). These data were automatically uploaded to the pedometer app and participants were asked to ‘authorise’ and ‘send measurements’ via the app. The step count data was analysed and reported in chapter 4 (Thomson et al., 2021). Both the BC and pedometer apps showed the measurements in a list-form by date.

a

b

Cancel	Manual Measurement	Done
VALUES		
Mass		kg
Fat Percentage (if available)		%
Height (if available)		m
Date and Time		31/08/2017, 13:13

c

4430	26/08/2017	
9798	25/08/2017	
4629	24/08/2017	
3494	23/08/2017	
8929	22/08/2017	
3585	21/08/2017	
Authorize	Deauthorize	Send Measurements

Figure 6-1: Screenshots of the Lenus Health Platform’s associated apps (a) BP app, (b) BC app and (c) Pedometer app.

6.3.1.1.2 Data collection

At the end of the two-week monitoring period, each “patient” participated in a semi-structured interview. The interviews were conducted as per section 3.7 in chapter 3. The interview questions covered the usability of the Lenus Health Platform, broader use of digital health technologies, and data sharing within healthcare systems. The mean length of the interviews was 28 minutes (range 15 to 51 min).

6.3.1.2 Part 2 – HCPs.

Ten HCPs currently working within NHS Scotland volunteered to take part: five females and five males (mean \pm SD: 34 \pm 5 years old). HCPs included general practitioners (n=3), nurses (n=2), consultant anaesthetists (n=2), a consultant radiologist (n=1), an orthopaedic surgeon (n=1) and an obstetrics and gynaecology clinician (n=1). HCPs were given temporary access to the desktop version of the Lenus Health Platform for as long as they required. The HCPs were able to review longitudinal data entries of BP (Figure 6-2), daily step count and BM from three simulated ‘patients’ that had been uploaded by the platform developers. The HCPs were aware the data was not from real patients. When the HCPs informed the research team that they had fully explored the data within the platform, they took part in a semi-structured interview following a similar process as the mock patients. On this occasion, the interview questions covered the usability of the Lenus Health Platform, the potential for implementing the Lenus Health Platform within existing healthcare systems, broader use of digital health technologies, and data sharing. The mean duration of the interviews was 29 minutes (range 20 to 45 min).

Figure 6-2: Screenshot of the Lenus Health Platform.

6.4 Results

Themes and subthemes from thematic analyses are presented in Tables 6-1 and 6-2 and described below, respectively. Anonymised quotations from ‘mock patients’ and HPC interview transcripts are utilised to provide a variety of perspectives.

6.4.1 Part 1 – Mock patients

Table 6-1: Themes and sub-themes from thematic analysis of ‘mock patient’ interviews.

Themes	Subthemes
1 – Data collection and sharing	<i>1.a – Previous wearable/app use</i>
	<i>1.b – Storing and sharing data</i>
	<i>1.c – Data control and privacy</i>
	<i>1.d – Problems with hardware</i>
2 – Usability of the Lenus Health Platform’s apps	<i>2.a – User-friendly</i>
	<i>2.b – What participants liked</i>
	<i>2.c – What participants did not like</i>
	<i>2.d – Motivation</i>
3 – Recommendations	<i>3.a – Adaptations to apps</i>
	<i>3.b – Communication</i>
	<i>3.c – General recommendation</i>
	<i>3.d – Visual representation</i>
4 – Impact on the NHS	<i>4.a – Facilitators</i>
	<i>4.b – Barriers</i>

6.4.1.1 Data collection and sharing

Previous wearable/app use. Most participants had used wearable technology or apps to monitor health previously, with only two participants reporting never to have used either. Wearables previously used by participants included those to measure PA (Fitbit (n=6); Garmin Forerunner (n=1); Microsoft Band (n=1), HR (Polar chest strap (n=1)) or a range of health outcomes (Current Health (n=2)). Participants reported that they used a range of mobile apps, including a non-named pedometer app (PA) (n=3); Strava (PA) (n=1); Pacer pedometer app (PA) (n=1); MyFitnessPal (diet) (n=3) and Flo (Menstrual cycle) (n=1). When asked why they have used a wearable/app for PA monitoring in the past, most participants said they were “*curious to see how many steps I do during the day*” (Participant 9). A few participants liked the motivation aspect of using wearables/apps and felt it was “*quite good just to get a reminder of increasing my steps throughout the day and stuff and trying to get a bit healthier and lose a bit of weight*” (Participant 12). When asked about duration of use, a range of “*about a week*” (Participant 9) to “*about three years*” (Participant 1) was reported, with participants stating that, in regards to wearable fitness trackers, they wore it most days “*unless I forget to charge it*” (Participant 11).

Storing and sharing data. Participants recognised the benefit of their data being collected and subsequently shared with HCPs, “*it’s of most benefit to me and my doctor*” (Participant 9) with some believing “*the more this kind of telemedicine is done the better*” (Participant 6). A large component of the study involved participants sharing their data via the Lenus Health Platform and although HCPs were not actually checking their data, participants understood that this

would be part of the care process if the Lenus Health Platform was implemented within the NHS. Most were content with the process and understood the value of it:

...yes, absolutely fine because although it's BP and things like that it's not too confidential so if anything was to get leaked or somebody hacked into my phone it wouldn't be the end of the world because it's just numbers (Participant 3).

There were some concerns over the trustworthiness of storing and sharing data, specifically: the accuracy of data collection/transference, *"I don't know if I trusted my diastolic BP reading from the monitor but it was reading consistent from the monitor to the app"* (Participant 2); the uncertainty of those who have access to the data, *"whether that (data) is then used by other people that should have access to it in the storage phase, probably less likely to trust that side of things"* (Participant 2) and general human error. However, others reported a lack of concern as the type of data collected and shared was *"nothing personal that I would get upset about somebody seeing"* (Participant 8).

Data control and privacy. Participants felt that they had control over their data *"as long as I know what it's being used for and who it's shared with, I don't mind. I guess if it's confidential then it doesn't really matter that much."* (Participant 5). It was also recognised that they have control over their data as *"if I don't want to send it, I don't need to send it"* (Participant 10) and *"I just could not put it in if I didn't want to"* (Participant 1). Some felt that the type of physiological data being collected was not of importance to anyone other than HCPs, therefore control was not a significant issue:

I'm not that fussed, because, you know, anybody that's got access to my data's using it to help me, so I'm not fussed. Nobody's going to write to *The Sun* [newspaper] and say, "Oh, her BP's 200 over 102. You know?" (Participant 14).

Many were also aware of "*all these horror stories about, you know, data hacks and breaches*" (Participant 12), although didn't think it was an issue regarding the Lenus Health Platform.

Problems with hardware. One participant living in a more remote area struggled with having to connect the iPhone to the internet to send over their data - "*I had no internet in the house, it (was) one of these stormy days.*" (Participant 14).

A common complaint was that the Bluetooth connectivity between iPhone and BP monitor was temperamental. For some, the BP monitor and BP app connected via Bluetooth without issue, however for many the app "*just kept saying the same measurements, it never once matched what the actual device said*" (Participant 5). Although this issue is likely specific to the hardware used, some felt it "*was quite demotivating*" (Participant 1).

6.4.1.2 Usability of the Lenus HealthPlatform's apps

User-friendly. Almost all participants found the apps "*really easy... nice and simple*" (Participant 8), "*quite clear, quite easy to see, everything that came up was pretty*

straightforward” (Participant 7) and generally enjoyed using them. However, there were a couple who found the apps were *“not the easiest thing to use”* (Participant 17) and felt that:

If it’s going to be used particularly for older people, it has got to be absolutely idiot-proof... It’s got to be simple, no options and really clear what you have to do... “Press me,” basically, almost. One button really to do everything (Participant 6).

What participants liked. Participants identified many things they liked about the Lenus Health Platform apps - in particular they enjoyed *“just having the facility to be able to keep an eye on your vital signs”* (Participant 6) and recognised the significance of being able to view their health data over time:

...I actually enjoyed the graphics that you got over time for the BP and the body composition (Participant 2).

The ease in which they could take their measurements, quickly upload them to the Lenus Health Platform and not *“have to write it down”* (Participant 7) was also valued.

What participants did not like. Participants typically did not enjoy the plainness of the pedometer and BC apps, stating *“they weren’t particularly user-friendly and they weren’t particularly exciting”* (Participant 17):

...okay, it (pedometer app) told me how many steps I did, but it didn't seem to give me any more information. Although it was a simple reading, I didn't find it particularly informative (Participant 6).

Motivation. Participants felt that viewing their health data regularly would motivate them to lead healthier lives, e.g. increasing steps per day – *“I think definitely seeing my steps every day made me motivated, like, oh I really didn't move yesterday, I should move today”* (Participant 5) or reducing their BP if it was regularly high:

I think if I had consistently high BP or consistently low BP it would give me motivation to do something about it but because I was relatively in the healthy region it was kind of quite nice to know that you're kind of healthy (Participant 3).

6.4.1.3 Recommendations

Adaptations to apps. Reminders to the phone, e.g. a text from the researcher or an automated push notification within the app were recommended - *“Maybe if it popped up if I hadn't taken it in two days to say, can you take your BP?”* (Participant 1). Also, reminders for PA were recommended, much like the reminder to move adopted by Fitbit (Fitbit Inc, San Francisco, CA, USA) and Apple smartwatches. The ability to set goals was also recommended:

...something built in where it would be, sort of, reminders every so often... Because although it might give you a target of so many steps a day, but if you're getting small reminders to do so many steps an hour, then that all adds up to your total daily amount (Participant 12).

...you could put in, like, some goals especially in the sort of step count bit or maybe in the weight bit, I suppose. Yes, so just to say, well done, you've achieved or you've improved from last week, that sort of thing (Participant 4).

A *"kind of help section or how-to"* (Participant 12), was recommended as a useful addition, as well as receiving feedback via the apps, e.g. *"you should go and speak to your doctor"* (Participant 8). Being able to confirm or correct their data - *"maybe just a, kind of, retry button... "Are we correct?" Rather than taking a value and then just putting it straight into the app and that is the measurement."* (Participant 19) - was also suggested.

Communication. Two-way communication between patient and HCP via a *"chat function"* (Participant 1) within the app was recommended, as well as confirmation that their HCP had viewed their uploaded data on the Lenus Health Platform - *"There's nothing to say, yes we got this, thanks"* (Participant 5).

General recommendations. Participants felt that the Lenus Health Platform would be more streamlined *"if you could just have it in one (app) and send it all at once"* (Participant 5) and that *"it would be better if you were constantly logged in"* (Participant 4). Making the apps as

simple as possible was viewed as beneficial due to the varying ages and technical ability of NHS patients. Five participants expressed concern that older patients may struggle with the system - *“I could see why maybe older people may find it more difficult than me”* (Participant 11) and one older participant had their partner send their measurements via the apps for them as they are *“a bit of a technophobe and probably wouldn’t have really known how to do it”* (Participant 16).

Visual representation. Many participants mentioned that they would have liked the apps to be more visual. Where the BP app utilised a traffic-light system to show high, normal or low BP, participants felt that something similar for the pedometer and BC apps would be valuable - *“if you go over 10,000 steps it was green for that day, just to, sort of, hit home”* (Participant 2):

...the pedometer and the, kind of, BM, the weight ones were just a number and if it graphically showed you how you were losing weight or gaining weight, you know, through a graph or some sort of chart or something, that the app showed you, then that would probably be more, sort of, helpful, I think (Participant 17).

Also, some felt the apps needed more information, particularly the pedometer app - *“I did 8,000 steps, when was that? Was that all in one walk or was it a lot of little stuff?”* (Participant 6). The addition of time within the BP app was viewed as a valuable addition *“because it would only make it more accurate if you were doing it at the same time every day”* (Participant 20).

6.4.1.4 Impact on the NHS

Facilitators. Participants felt that they would receive better care from the NHS with the addition of the Lenus Health Platform: *“It should be much better and it should be instant and secure”* (Participant 7); *“I suppose if all the information’s in the one place, it would make it easier for them (HCPs)”* (Participant 20). One of the reasons given was the reduced face-to-face contact with their HCP as they can *“remotely access that (data) without you having to specifically make an appointment”* (Participant 17), as they *“know how difficult it is to get a doctor’s appointment”* (Participant 9). Also, being able to *“genuinely tell whether I have got high BP or whether it’s just, you know, the occasion of being at the doctor’s”* (Participant 10), was valued.

Another potential benefit was that HCPs would be able to view trends within their patients’ health data as *“it gives more information than just a snapshot to interpret my health”* (Participant 3) and *“any monitoring like that over a long period is obviously going to have a truer picture of your actual health”* (Participant 10).

Barriers. One participant felt that *“getting people to move with the times”* (Participant 14), in relation to switching from traditional face-to-face healthcare to an online DHP, may be a potential barrier. Another made the astute point that, *“whether it will lead to better care is quite a distinction because once again, you’re reliant on the people that are using it to use it properly”* (Participant 6).

6.4.2 Part 2 – HCPs

Table 6-2: Themes and sub-themes from thematic analysis of HCP interviews.

Themes	Subthemes
1 – Implementation of the Lenus Health Platform within the NHS	<i>1.a – Facilitators</i>
	<i>1.b – Barriers</i>
	<i>1.c – Has the potential to be implemented within the NHS</i>
2 – Usability of the Lenus Health Platform	<i>2.a – Visual representation</i>
	<i>2.b – User-friendly</i>
3 – Technology	<i>3.a – Data sharing</i>
	<i>3.b – Current use of electronic systems</i>
4 – Recommendations	<i>4.a – Additional measurements</i>
	<i>4.b – Additions to the Lenus Health Platform interface</i>

6.4.2.1 Implementation of the Lenus Health Platform within the NHS

Facilitators. One benefit identified was “*data sharing online*” (HCP 2) between HCPs, particularly between “*different members of the medical team, from different specialties*” (HCP 6) as well as allowing for “*secondary care to share with primary care*” (HCP 10). This was valued as “*there’s so many examples of local policies and local procedures that don’t necessarily... that don’t speak to one another*” (HCP 7):

...it brings it all on one screen rather than cross referencing, because this is part of the huge problem in the healthcare system, is lots of different systems, this system, a

different system with blood results in it on another computer screen and then physical notes, writing down in your notes what you found when you examined them (HCP 2).

It was recognised that the Lenus Health Platform could help with aiding decisions as:

...you've got the information on them, their BP, certainly, yes, it would make it easier to treat, so what information you've got can help... you'd be more, maybe, more inclined to treat a bit earlier, more aggressively, if you had more information (HCP 9).

Also, to "*see the direct influence on changing your medication*" (HCP 6), based on viewing patient data over time. The ability to give patients a simple intervention was also valued:

...if we're wanting to look at improving patient's care or improving certain outcomes we're going to be able to highlight those patients that could benefit (HCP 1).

HCPs felt that the Lenus Health Platform would be beneficial for "*chronic disease monitoring*" (HCP 10) as well as monitoring BP over time prior to surgery, rather than the traditional...

...pre-op assessment, they come in for one visit and they're stressed out, they've come a fair distance, struggle to find parking, they've got to take the day off work or whatever, so they turn up and the biggest one is the BP and HR being high, they're

already a bit stressed out and you look at their BP and you go, oh, maybe we need to refer you to a cardiologist before you get your hip replacement (HCP 2).

Another HCP reported that it was the “*same with BMI y’know sometimes for non-urgent surgery we will choose not to immediately offer patients surgery for example, a common one in gynaecology*” and that patients would...

...come up like regularly just basically to see if her weights came down yet to see if we can list her for theatre yeah and actually that patient could just have this system in place and once the BMI was low enough that we were aiming for ehm we’d trigger an alert to the consultant gynaecologist for example (HCP 1).

The Lenus Health Platform was also thought to be valuable for viewing trends in patient data as it “*tells you exactly what the physical activity is, you can see what’s happening over time, an upward trend, downward trend*” (HCP 3), and that “*in an outpatient clinic, it would be very, very useful*” (HCP 2). Being able to monitor patients in more “*remote locations, or someone maybe that finds it hard to get out, housebound*” (HCP 9) was also viewed as advantageous.

A major potential benefit reported was that it could improve efficiency and “*reduce face-to-face consulting and GP (General Practitioner) time, and reduce waiting lists for people who really need them*” (HCP 10), while also reducing the burden currently on the NHS:

...if you can measure your BP yourself, at home, and upload it to the internet... you wouldn't need to go in to see a nurse to get your BP taken, you might not need to go and see a doctor as often... it's going to save money. The reason the NHS would be interested in it is if it saved money... and I can see that working (HCP 3).

Another key benefit was improved patient autonomy as:

...it empowers the patients as well because a lot of the time they feel powerless if they've got a certain condition and can't really do much about it. If they're actually feeling that they're in control of it a bit more and helping to do something about it, then it might improve their health as well (HCP 4).

Also, it may help to "*motivate the patients*" (HCP 3) due to the fact "*the patients know that you can see what they're doing*" (HCP 2).

Lastly, all HCPs identified that sharing data within a multidisciplinary team would mean nursing staff or allied health professionals could also monitor patients as "*you don't need to be a doctor to look at a graph or to monitor trends*" (HCP 3):

I'm thinking about GP workload and not adding to it, but I don't think this would. I think this would enable nurses to do most of the chronic disease management, to monitor... it'd be easy for them to (HCP 10),

Barriers. HCPs reported a few potential barriers to implementation of the Lenus Health Platform. Firstly, *“the cost for the NHS”* (HCP 10) and:

“the availability... of the kind of technology involved, so obviously you need the computers and definitely where I work there is not always enough computers when you need to get onto one” (HCP 8).

Some also reported that the apps *“might be more tricky for older patients to be able to use”* (HCP 1):

all elderly people aren't going to have access to an app and they're not going to be able to enter their own data, but if you're talking about people in their 40s and 50s and 60s, I'm not going to be ageist, but, yes, I guess that would be the only limitation, other people who haven't got smart phones... (HCP 10).

Moreover, HCPs will have to *“check that the person is competent to use it (apps) in the first place”* and if not, provide training to the individual directly or indirectly, which would potentially be costly and time consuming.

Furthermore, many HCPs indicated that patients could potentially ‘fake’ their data, “*if you said, ‘Listen, I want you to do 10,000 steps for the next two weeks, and see how you find your BP goes from there,’ and they just palm it off to their nephew or niece...*” (HCP 2). However, they “*don’t think people would be terribly motivated to do so*” (HCP 3) and that “*patients have to take responsibility for themselves as well*” (HCP 5).

Lastly, there were concerns regarding the Lenus Health Platform’s suitability with other IT systems, as “*you already have a fairly creaking IT service, so you need something that fitted in to the IT service that was agreed, that was nationwide*” (HCP 7).

Has the potential to be implemented within the NHS. All HCPs felt that the Lenus Health Platform had the potential to be implemented within the NHS. Some of the main reasons were that “*it may help make the service more efficient*” (HCP 3) and “*anything that allows you to have ownership, to share ownership, of health is a good thing*” (HCP 7). Some HCPs felt there would be “*loads of stumbling blocks along the way*” (HCP 5), however “*it’s a way of moving forward as well, isn’t it? Things are becoming more computerised and it’s a good way of doing it*” (HCP 4) and that “*there needs to be data sharing online, there has to be... it has to happen for the efficiency of the NHS*” (HCP 2).

6.4.2.2 Usability of the Lenus Health Platform

Visual representation. All HCPs found the visual representations of data to be “*nice and bright, it was easy to use and pretty intuitive*” (HCP 5) and that “*presenting it (data)*

graphically, is a very sound concept” (HCP 3). Viewing patient data graphically meant they were *“able to see it all in a graph over time”* (HCP 10):

it’s a lot quicker to be able to pictorially see what’s going on and translate that into whether a change in therapy has been useful, or a change in lifestyle has been useful, or whatever it is that’s been the intervention (HCP 7).

User-friendly. All HCPs found the Lenus Health Platform to be a *“user-friendly”* (HCP 5), *“straightforward”* (HCP 9), *“useful workable platform”* (HCP 7). Specifically, being able to bookmark patients who *“may be pushing very high risk, someone with high BP, high BMI”* was decidedly valued, as well as being able to *“put in the patient’s name and it’ll come up with it (data)”* (HCP 10). The Lenus Health Platform’s *“very easy to navigate”* (HCP 1) interface was also appreciated, particularly the *“ability to group patients together, as well, in terms of people who may be triggered as being hypertensive”* (HCP 7). Some felt that while the platform was easy to navigate with only some ‘patient’ data on it, they had concerns *“once you get into hundreds and hundreds of patients, you might start to find it difficult to find them... but you’ve got a search function, so that should be fine”* (HCP 2). Although the search function potentially negates this concern, it is an important point that should be explored before implementation.

6.4.2.3 Technology

Data sharing. Some were concerned regarding quality control of the equipment used, particularly the *“calibration and technique as well with BP monitors”* (HCP 6) and the

necessity *“to make sure they’re not giving false readings”* (HCP 9). However, *“not having that data versus having some data that may have some dubious quality control is a pay-off worth making”* (HCP 3) and *“trends are important. If you are five millimetres off, or five millimetres off the other way, not a huge worry”* (HCP 7).

Some stated that *“the main worry is always patient confidentiality”* (HCP 2), however, others felt *“the kind of data that it is probably isn’t particularly sensitive from a healthcare point of view”* (HCP 10):

“it’s (web-based platforms) all heavily audited who accesses it and you can only access it from within the NHS, so a kind of virtual private VPN, so I don’t see any reason why this data couldn’t be held securely” (HCP 3).

However, *“because the patients are on it at home as well, they would have to come up with some sort of encryption”* (HCP 8).

Current use of electronic systems. HCPs described other electronic systems that they have used within the NHS, such as *“one for children called iGrow, apparently. It is a database, not everyone has access to it, but it has the child’s weight and height and centiles”* (HCP 6), while stating that nothing like the Lenus Health Platform currently exists:

...we use similar things in [this region], something called Clinical Portal, and so the idea of a web-based platform is quite familiar, and it's useful because you can access it from home using VPNs... the data is not collected as cleverly as this... Nothing like that happens at the moment (HCP 3).

6.4.2.4 Recommendations

Additional measurements. HCPs recommended several additional measurements that would be beneficial to integrate within the Lenus Health Platform, as can be seen in Table 6-3.

Table 6-3: HCP recommended additional measurements for the Lenus Health Platform.

Measurements	Quote
Menstrual diary	“patients who are having menstrual disorders taking a menstrual diary so that could be quite useful here” (HCP 1).
Peak flow	“peak flows for asthmatics” (HCP 2).
Diabetes	“They could maybe put in their blood sugars and then you could see a trend about how well controlled the diabetes is” (HCP 4).
Tachycardia	“if they had a heartrate monitor, when they were having those palpitations they would know what their heartrate is, that would be helpful to know. Are they having true tachycardia?” (HCP 6).
Sleep disorders	“There’s meant to be this undiagnosed, or largely undiagnosed, epidemic of people with sleep disorders, largely related to obesity, sleep apnoea and things like that, so if you could show people’s sleep data, quite interesting” (HCP 7).
Temperature	“temperature, things like that” (HCP9).
Food diary	“food diary inputs” (HCP 10).
Renal Function	“renal function” (HCP 5).

Additions to the Lenus Health Platform interface. HCPs felt that “*if you can customise it (the Lenus Health Platform) for patients*” (HCP 2) and “*adjust alarms for each patient... You could potentially change the flagging up when there’s an abnormality*” (HCP 7). As well as “*making them (graphs) a bit more obvious as to when it’s abnormal so you can skim*” (HCP 7), aiding efficiency.

The addition of “*a little list of your most recently looked at*” (HCP 5) and “*being able to add notes*” (HCP 2) was recommended, as well as “*having a little patient comment, so say BP was through the roof they could put a comment... ‘Stuck in traffic jam on my way home from work and feeling a bit stressed.’*” (HCP 6). Also, a section for “*small hints and tips that would come up? So, linking in a bit of advice*” (HCP 5), within the patient apps.

One HCP thought it may be a good idea to add a photo of patients:

...you’ll be seeing 40 patients a day and you might forget... go, ‘Did you see the guy that came in with a prostate problem, or was he the...?’ you know. I know GPs take notes but it might be useful if there was a consent area where the patients consent to have a photo up (HCP 2).

Another HCP felt “*the CHI number... might be useful*” in enabling patient identification as it is already “*pretty ubiquitous between primary and secondary care*” (HCP 5).

Furthermore, it was recommended that “*some sort of input for PA*” (HCP 1) and being able to view “*step count over time*” as it “*gives you some idea of the intensity*” (HCP 7) would be advantageous in gaining a more in-depth look at patient PA levels.

6.5 Discussion

The current study aimed to establish the usability of the Lenus Health Platform and associated iPhone apps within a cohort of ‘mock patients’ and HCPs. The themes that were generated from the interviews demonstrate that participants found the apps straightforward to use, understood the value of metrics being measured and believed that the implementation of the Lenus Health Platform within the current NHS setup would improve their quality of care. The concept of the apps being used to share data with HCPs and reduce NHS contact time was perceived as favourable. HCPs in both primary and secondary care believed that a service such as the Lenus Health Platform that enables patients to share their data remotely with their HCPs would be a helpful tool to the NHS. HCPs identified that patients monitoring their health parameters over time would allow them to view a more reliable representation of their health, therefore, enabling to provide more efficient care. However, HCPs felt there were some barriers to a service like the Lenus Health Platform being implemented within the NHS, yet these were far fewer than the potential benefits.

Part 1 – ‘mock patients’. Participants responded positively to the idea of sharing their health data with HCPs as they felt the data being collected was not sensitive. Most participants found the Lenus Health Platform associated apps easy to use and generally enjoyed using them, this is important as a recent randomised control trial evaluating the use of a digital health system

for long-term COPD management found that the system's interface being easy to use supports patient compliance (Velardo *et al.*, 2017).

Participants also felt being able to have two-way communication with their HCPs within the apps would be beneficial. However, the option of two-way communication may increase the cost of implementing the Lenus Health Platform within the NHS as personnel may require training in how to properly manage and respond to comments from patients (Chow *et al.*, 2016). Several benefits of the Lenus Health Platform being implemented within the NHS were identified by participants such as a reduction in face-to-face appointments as well as believing it would result in a higher standard of care for patients. The latter was also found in a usability and feasibility study of a mobile app for patients with complex chronic disease and disability, where patients felt there was an improvement in patient-centred care as well as providing the patient with a sense of responsibility over their health (Steele Gray *et al.*, 2016).

There were a few potential barriers to the Lenus Health Platform being implemented within the NHS identified by participants. Firstly, it requires access to the internet. One participant living in a more rural location within Scotland had issues sending their data due to their unreliable internet connection. This is an issue that has arisen in several other m-Health studies (Pfaeffli Dale *et al.*, 2015; Dicianno *et al.*, 2016) and is important to note as remote monitoring of patients is a significant potential benefit of the Lenus Health Platform. Therefore, contingency options may be put needed in these circumstances. Some participants also had issues with the Bluetooth BP monitor malfunctioning and felt this hindered their motivation to continue taking daily BP measurements. This supports findings from a previous study evaluating the usability of a mobile app to remotely measure and monitor pain symptoms in sickle cell disease where

technical malfunctions resulted in significantly fewer data entries by participants (Jonassaint *et al.*, 2015). While the hardware issues were unrelated to the Lenus Health Platform it does stress the importance of integrating devices that are proven to be valid and reliable.

Part 2 – HCPs. All HCPs interviewed in the current study believed the Lenus Health Platform had the potential to be implemented into the current NHS care setup. Many facilitating factors were identified such as reducing the need for face-to-face appointments with HCPs, especially in the context of measuring BP in pre-op patients. HCPs felt that this would reduce waiting times for patients who really need it, save the NHS money and also improve patient care. Compared to clinic BP readings, at-home monitoring of BP has been shown to improve systolic and diastolic BP, with greater improvements predicted with the addition of telemonitoring, such as with the Lenus Health Platform (Agarwal *et al.*, 2011). HCPs recognised that it would benefit patients who struggle to make it to a medical centre due to their remote location, or patients who are housebound. Another benefit of the Lenus Health Platform identified was that it may help to improve patient autonomy and motivate patients. Lastly, HCPs expressed that being able to share data within a multidisciplinary team via the Lenus Health Platform would enable nursing staff or allied health professionals to monitor patients, thereby not adding to GP's workload. Increased workload was identified as one of the major barriers to e-Health intervention implementation in several studies within a recent systematic review, with e-Health being described as resource and time demanding (Granja, Janssen and Johansen, 2018). Therefore, the ability to easily share the workload across the vast NHS personnel may help to reduce the stagnation of interest and commitment in e-Health systems as seen in hospitals across the Netherlands, resulting in a lack of actual e-Health adoption (Faber, Geenhuizen and Reuver, 2017).

Several potential barriers arose during the interviews with HCPs, such as the potential additional cost to the NHS and the availability of technology. As mentioned by one HCP, they are not always able to access a computer when they need to, therefore NHS sites may have to invest in more computers in order for HCPs to use the Lenus Health Platform. Also, the possible requirement of IT staff to teach HCPs to use the platform may result in additional costs. Faber, Geenhuizen and Reuver (2017) refer to these issues as organisational readiness, comprising of technological and financial readiness, and found that these had a positive influence on e-Health adoption. Some HCPs had stated that an important marker of the Lenus Health Platform's successful implementation within the NHS will be how it integrates with other e-Health and IT systems that are currently in use which aligns with a recent qualitative study investigating a self-management care-path for chronic somatic conditions (Ciere *et al.*, 2019).

Strengths and limitations

Older adults being included in the participant cohort is a strength of the current study, as m-Health systems are more likely to be successfully adopted by older adults if they are involved in the earlier stages of development (Kapadia *et al.*, 2015). However, all but two participants had some previous experience of PA and/or health monitoring with the use of wearables and/or apps, which is not representative of the general population in the UK (Strain, Wijndaele and Brage, 2019). Therefore, the results of the current study may not be generalisable to the wider UK population. Another limitation of the current study is that healthy individuals were recruited as 'mock patients'. The perceptions of these individuals may differ from those who have a diagnosed chronic condition whereby they require ongoing clinical care. Although a

limitation, this type of study is a necessary first step to demonstrate proof of concept and to further improve upon the Lenus Health Platform prior to a larger trial within an NHS patient cohort.

Conclusion

Mock patients generally enjoyed using the Lenus Health Platform's associated apps and recognised the significance of being able to view their health data over time. They were aware of the potential benefit of their data being collected and shared with HCPs and were content with the process via the Lenus Health Platform. There were some concerns regarding accuracy of measurements and the uncertainty of those who had access to the data, but ultimately felt they had control over their data. HCPs felt that the Lenus Health Platform could improve efficiency, reduce face-to-face consulting and help with aiding decisions. Potential costs to the NHS and the Lenus Health Platform's integration with other e-Health and IT systems were concerns held by HCPs. Overall, both mock patients and HCPs believed the Lenus Health Platform had the potential to be implemented within the NHS. Therefore, the current study demonstrated proof of concept, paving the way for a full evaluation of the Lenus Health Platform integrated into existing healthcare within the NHS.

**CHAPTER 7: Study 4 - Fitbit Measured Physical Activity Decreased
upon Commencement of UK COVID-19 Lockdown**

7.1 Introduction

With the recent COVID-19 pandemic, the world was thrust into a period of social-distancing, with many nations under government-mandated lockdowns. In Scotland, United Kingdom, the initial lockdown began on the 24th of March 2020, with a strict stay-at-home order. However, there were a few exceptions: essential shopping once a day; exercise once a day alone or with members of own household; medical reasons/carer responsibilities; and travelling to and from essential work. All gyms, swimming pools and indoor sporting venues were closed. Many workplaces moved to home-based working as well as all children/students learning from home with nursery, school and university closures. The limit on only being allowed outside to exercise once a day was lifted on the 11th of May 2020, almost seven full weeks after it was implemented (GOV.UK, 2020a).

It is important to know whether PA levels changed during the COVID-19 lockdowns as partaking in regular PA is widely accepted to result in decreased risk for all-cause mortality and chronic health conditions such as cancer, CVD, type-2 diabetes etc., (Warburton, Nicol and Bredin, 2006). Furthermore, 1-in-6 deaths in the UK are associated with a lack of PA with recent estimations indicating that physical inactivity costs the UK around £7 billion each year, £0.9 billion of which directly affects the UK's NHS. The UK population is estimated to be ~20% less physically active than in the 1960s, with current projections suggesting a rise to 35% by 2030 (GOV.UK, 2022b). Therefore, knowing whether government-mandated lockdowns negatively affect population levels of PA is imperative and can potentially aid in further lockdown-initiating discussions.

During the week ending 22nd of March 2020 – the week before the UK went into lockdown – activity-tracker manufacturer ‘Fitbit’ reported an 8% decline in step count within the UK Fitbit wearing population, compared to the same week in 2019 (Fitbit Staff, 2020). Interestingly, UK data from the Office for National Statistics showed that self-reported time spent keeping fit increased significantly from 28th March to 26th April 2020, compared to UK data from a 2014 – 2015 time-use study (Office for National Statistics, 2020). However, these results could reflect longer-term societal changes due to the amount of time between studies, and therefore be unrelated to the COVID-19 pandemic. Both a scoping review and systematic review of the effect of COVID-19 on PA levels, stated that most studies reported a decrease in PA due to lockdowns (Caputo and Reichert, 2020; Stockwell *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, Kingsnorth *et al.*, (2021) found light intensity activity decreased with commencement of the UK lockdown while MVPA increased. This may be due to the adoption of new/different PA modalities.

To recognise changes in population levels of PA, we need to be able to measure them, either via self-reported methodologies or, preferably, objectively with the use of research-grade accelerometers. While accelerometers are small and can be easily provided to participants for the duration of a research study (Doherty *et al.*, 2017), they are not as useful when the investigation of PA levels warrants retrospection. In such instances, PA tracking wearables that participants already own, such as a Fitbit, can be used in its place. These Fitbit devices are worn on the wrist and measure PA using a tri-axial accelerometer, as well as a photoplethysmography (PPG) optical sensor if HR-enabled. Fitbit proprietary algorithms are used to provide an estimation of several variables: step count; EE; active minutes; steps climbed; distance travelled; and sleep duration and ‘score’. The consumer-adoption of such PA tracking wearables, as well as their utilisation in research, has increased exponentially in recent

years (Ferreira *et al.*, 2021). This type of widespread, consistently collected PA data allows for the investigation of PA behaviours prior to, as well as during, the UK COVID-19 lockdown.

While communities adapted to this unprecedented societal challenge, it is important to understand what impact this had on PA behaviours. It is accepted that maintaining a healthy weight and level of fitness protects against serious disease and adverse events in COVID-19 infection (Hamer *et al.*, 2020; Sallis *et al.*, 2021; Ezzatvar *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the primary aim of this study was to investigate the difference in adult PA behaviours with the use of Fitbits, prior-to and during lockdown. A secondary aim was to explore, qualitatively, how and why PA behaviours changed during and post-lockdown.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Participants

Twenty adults volunteered to take part: fifteen females and five males (mean \pm SD: age 41 \pm 13 years). Inclusion criteria consisted of: \geq 18 years; no physical mobility issues; and use of a HR-enabled Fitbit (Fitbit, San Francisco, CA) activity tracker. Participants were given access to a data-encrypted website where they read an information sheet before providing informed consent.

7.2.2 Procedures

Through the data-encrypted website, participants answered simple demographic questions before giving permission for the research team to access and download Fitbit data for four distinct weeks (Table 7-1). Variables included: step count (steps·day⁻¹); PA intensity (METs); HR (bpm) and EE (kcal·day⁻¹). Participants were lastly asked via the website if they would be happy to be contacted at a later date to take part in a virtual, semi-structured interview regarding how/why PA behaviours may have changed due to social-distancing/lockdown.

Table 7-1: Dates for each week of data.

Variable	Beginning Date	End Date
‘Year Before’ UK Lockdown	24 th March 2019	30 th March 2019
‘Month Before’ UK Lockdown	24 th February 2020	1 st March 2020
‘Start’ of UK Lockdown	24 th March 2020	30 th March 2020
‘Month In’ to UK Lockdown	21 st April 2020	27 th April 2020

7.2.3 Interviews

The same twenty participants also volunteered to take part in a short semi-structured interview. This included focused and specific questions regarding the participant’s opinion on PA tracking, duration of Fitbit use, other types of PA tracking/monitoring, and questions specific to PA before, during and after the COVID-19 lockdown. Interviews were conducted in October 2020, took place via Microsoft Teams and were recorded, with participant consent, for later transcription. The mean duration of the interviews was 14 minutes (range 9.5 to 31 min). Interviews were conducted as per section 3.7 in chapter 3.

7.2.4 Data processing and analysis

Fitbit wear-time was calculated using HR and step data. Any minute with a step count or HR > 0 was defined as a valid minute of wear-time (Collins *et al.*, 2019). A valid day was defined as ≥ 10 hours of wear and ≥ 4 valid days was defined as a valid week (Troiano *et al.*, 2008; Collins *et al.*, 2019).

Step count, light intensity activity and peak HR data were normally distributed, therefore a repeated measures ANOVA was run for each variable. Post hoc analysis was performed with a Tukey adjustment for multiple comparisons. MVPA, as well as average total daily expenditure, wear minutes and average HR were not normally distributed. Friedman tests were run on the non-normally distributed data to determine if there were differences between the four weeks. Pairwise comparisons were performed with a Durbin-Conover correction for multiple comparisons.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Wear-time

Nine participant's data were excluded from analysis: five were missing ≥ 1 full week of data; two had < 4 valid days for a single week; one did not have any HR data; and there was an issue in downloading one participants' data that could not be resolved. Therefore, data from eleven participants were analysed (eight females and three males). Wear-time data across the four

weeks are presented in Table 7-2. There was no significant difference in wear-time between the four weeks ($P = 0.08$). Participants recorded an average of 7 ± 0.0 days; 7 ± 0.0 days; 7 ± 0.6 days (range 5 – 7) and 7 ± 0.5 days (range 6 – 7) of valid data for the ‘year before’, ‘month before’, ‘start’ and ‘month in’ to the COVID-19 lockdown, respectively.

Table 7-2: Average valid wear minutes across four weeks: the ‘year before’, ‘month before’, ‘start’ and ‘month in’ to the COVID-19 lockdown. One full day = 1440 minutes.

	Year Before	Month Before	Start	Month In
Mean \pm SD (mins\cdotday$^{-1}$)	1297 \pm 174	1362 \pm 39	1316 \pm 96	1342 \pm 72
Range (mins\cdotday$^{-1}$)	627	111	341	213

7.3.2 METs

Average total daily minutes spent in light intensity activity (1.6 – 2.9 METs) the ‘month before’ lockdown was significantly higher than a ‘month in’ to lockdown ($P = 0.02$). There was no difference between the ‘year before’ and: ‘month before’ ($P = 0.46$); ‘start’ ($P = 0.91$); and a ‘month in’ ($P = 0.38$). There was no significant difference between the ‘month before’ and ‘start’ ($P = 0.16$), and there was also no significant difference between the ‘start’ and a ‘month in’ ($P = 0.78$).

Average total daily minutes spent in MVPA (>3 METs) at the ‘start’ of lockdown was significantly lower than the ‘year before’ ($P = 0.02$), the ‘month before’ ($P = 0.007$) and a ‘month in’ to lockdown ($P = 0.04$). There was no significant difference between the ‘year

before' and: 'month before' ($P = 0.72$) and a 'month in' ($P = 0.72$). There was also no significant difference between the 'month before' and a 'month in' ($P = 0.47$). All MET data across the four weeks are presented in Figure 7-1.

7.3.3 EE

Average total daily EE the 'year before' lockdown was significantly greater than the 'start' ($P = 0.004$) and a 'month in' ($P = 0.03$), but not different from the 'month before' lockdown ($P = 0.36$). The 'month before' lockdown also saw a significantly larger average total daily EE than the 'start' of lockdown ($P = 0.03$). There was no statistical difference between the 'month before' and a 'month in' ($P = 0.20$) or between the 'start' and a 'month in' to lockdown ($P = 0.36$). EE data across the four weeks are presented in Figure 7-2.

7.3.4 Step count

There was no significant difference in steps between the four weeks ($P = 0.25$). Step count data across the four weeks are presented in Figure 7-3.

7.3.5 HR

Average HR across the 'year before' (73 ± 10 bpm), 'month before' (72 ± 9 bpm), 'start' (71 ± 9 bpm) and a 'month in' (72 ± 9 bpm) to lockdown was not statistically significant ($P = 0.40$).

Peak HR across the ‘year before’ (141 ± 16 bpm), ‘month before’ (134 ± 13 bpm), ‘start’ (137 ± 19 bpm) and a ‘month in’ (138 ± 12 bpm) to lockdown was also not statistically significant ($P = 0.52$).

Figure 7-1: Average total daily minutes in light (1.6 - 2.9 METs), MVPA (>3 METs) across a full week the ‘year before’, ‘month before’, ‘start’ and ‘month in’ of the COVID-19 lockdown. * denotes statistical significant difference from ‘Start’, \$ denotes statistical significant difference from ‘Month In’.

Figure 7-2: Box and whiskers plot of total daily EE across a full week the ‘year before’, ‘month before’, ‘start’ and ‘month in’ of the COVID-19 lockdown. Each box represents the interquartile range, extending from the 25th to the 75th percentile of each group’s distribution of values. The line inside each box represents the median and the + represents the mean. The whiskers represent the minimum and maximum values. * denotes statistical significant difference from ‘Start’, \$ denotes statistical significant difference from ‘Month In’.

Figure 7-3: Box and whiskers plot of total daily step count across a full week the ‘year before’, ‘month before’, ‘start’ and ‘month in’ of the COVID-19 lockdown. Each box represents the interquartile range, extending from the 25th to the 75th percentile of each group’s distribution of values. The line inside each box represents the median and the + represents the mean. The whiskers represent the minimum and maximum values.

7.3.6 Interviews

For the qualitative data to accurately reflect the quantitative data, only the eleven participants' who were included in the quantitative analysis were included in the qualitative analysis. Themes and subthemes that were identified from the thematic analyses of the eleven interview transcripts are presented in Table 7-3.

Table 7-3: Themes and sub-themes from thematic analysis of eleven qualitative interviews.

Themes	Subthemes
1 – PA monitoring	<i>1.a – Fitbit model and length of use</i> <i>1.b – PA tracking</i>
2 – PA before lockdown	<i>2.a – Type and frequency</i> <i>2.b – Opinion on PA before lockdown</i>
3 – PA during lockdown	<i>3.a – Behaviour change</i> <i>3.b – Type and frequency</i> <i>3.c – PA prevention</i> <i>3.d – PA awareness</i> <i>3.e – Fitbit interaction</i>
4 – PA after lockdown	<i>4.a – Amount and type of PA</i> <i>4.b – Relationship with PA</i> <i>4.c – Fitbit interaction</i> <i>4.d – General comments</i>

7.3.6.1 PA monitoring

Fitbit model and length of use. All participants reported they had used a Fitbit device for several years, ranging from 2 to 4 years, with three participants having upgraded to a newer Fitbit model within that time. The current Fitbit models used by participants are detailed in Table 7-4.

Table 7-4: Models of Fitbit used by participants.

Fitbit Model	No. of Participants
Charge 2	5
Versa 2	2
Blaze	2
Ionic	1
HR 2	1

PA tracking. Most participants had used some sort of fitness tracking device or mobile app previously, as can be seen in Table 7-5. Two participants had only ever used a Fitbit. All participants had a positive opinion of tracking and monitoring their PA - it was seen as a way to “make sure that I’m kind of active” (Participant 4) as well as providing “a record of it right there so it allows you to then increase your activity or decrease your activity” (Participant 10). Some felt it was “quite motivating to do” (Participant 11) and found it “quite useful. Because it obviously just gives you some information about how active I actually am, or not sometimes as the case might be” (Participant 14). Others described PA tracking as “just something I do, that’s just what I do, you know I’ve been doing it for the past umpteen years” (Participant 15)

and have “*always tracked my exercise, so it’s not any different really*” (Participant 16). One participant explained how they “*quite like keeping a track of it*” but “*didn’t think I would when I initially bought it*” (Participant 19).

Table 7-5: Wearables and smartphone apps previously used by participants.

Device	Mobile Apps	No. of Participants
<i>Garmin Watch</i>		3
	<i>My Fitness Pal</i>	3
	<i>Strava</i>	2
	<i>Map My Fitness</i>	1
	<i>Google Fit</i>	1
	<i>Map My Walks</i>	1
	<i>Nutracheck</i>	1
<i>Generic fitness tracker</i>		1
<i>Wahoo Element Gold (cycling computer)</i>		1
<i>Garmin (cycling computer)</i>		1

7.3.6.2 PA before Lockdown

Type and frequency. Participants were asked to estimate how often they would participate in PA, and what type of PA, before the COVID-19 lockdown began. The most common types of PA were structured gym workouts/classes and walking. Other types of PA mentioned were running; cycling; yoga; pilates; swimming; indoor climbing; curling; racquetball and football.

In terms of frequency, most participants reported they would take part in PA three to four times a week, with some participants stating they did some type of PA (e.g., walking) every day.

Opinion on PA before lockdown. Participants were asked whether they were concerned about their PA before lockdown. Most participants reported that they were indeed concerned, with some stating that they “*had been finding it difficult to get into a regular routine for exercise before lockdown*” (Participant 13) or they were “*always kind of, you know, aware that I was, you know, that I wanted to do exercise and making sure that I fitted it in and things*” (Participant 11). One participant specified “*as a nurse, I feel that I should be practicing what I preach so that sort of motivates me to ensure that I do exercise regularly and follow Scottish government guidelines*” (Participant 16). Others felt that their PA didn’t concern them as they were “*doing enough exercise*” (Participant 10), “*it just gave me something to do*” (Participant 5) or that it was “*just part of me as it were*” (Participant 15).

7.3.6.3 PA during Lockdown

Behaviour change. Participants were asked if they felt their PA behaviours had changed once lockdown and social-distancing were implemented. All participants said their PA behaviours changed, with three stating there was “*definitely*” (Participants 14, 15 and 18) a change and one reporting “*yeah, in a massive way*” (Participant 10). Only one participant declared their PA behaviours “*didn’t change that much*” but that they “*probably did a bit more*” (Participant 19) during lockdown.

Type and frequency. As the UK lockdown involved only being allowed out of the house to exercise for one hour per day, most participants used that time to go a walk or to do some other type of PA outside, including: running; cycling; rollerblading and martial arts. Many participants also did some at-home workouts, including yoga; step aerobics; weight training; body-weight training; high-intensity cardio; dance-based classes and indoor cycling. These activities were either self-led or via Zoom/YouTube and were estimated to take place three to four times a week. For others, they *“could count on one hand the number of times I actually tried to do successful bodyweight exercises”* as *“motivation wasn’t the same”* (Participant 15). It was common for PA levels to be higher towards the beginning of lockdown, before drifting off as time went on:

I tried to go out for a run. It was, I mean it was only sort of, 20-minute run before settling down to work every other day, uhm and I did that for about three weeks, and then gave up and did nothing (Participant 5).

...so at the very beginning of the lockdown period ehm I was, I was actually doing very well. I was going out probably three times per week to do like a run and then practice some martial arts in the park, ehm so that was about three times a week and then after a few weeks I don’t know what happened, but I guess it’s probably, it’ll probably be known as lockdown depression or whatever set in and I didn’t do anything for quite some weeks (Participant 10).

Most participants felt that the lockdown provided them the opportunity to start new types of PA that they hadn’t taken part in prior to the lockdown. For some, that meant taking part in PA

with their family: "...yeah it allowed my wife and I to, to start sort of exercising together which is something that we didn't normally do" (Participant 10); "...yeah the rollerblading as well. So exercising as a family has been a bit of a new thing, that's been fun" (Participant 11).

Doing at-home workouts was new to some participants, with a few mentioning they had specifically tried the "*Joe Wicks YouTube things, you know, he was doing the PE for the kids...*" (Participant 14), but didn't do them regularly, with one jokingly stating "*he (Joe Wicks) nearly killed me, so I gave him up*" (Participant 19). Some participants mentioned that the lockdown allowed them the time to do PA they had done in the past, specifically: "*revisit the belly dancing stuff*" (Participant 11) and "*reengage with yoga*" (Participant 17). One felt they were able to do more walking and "*didn't realise the amount of nice walks that were round about the village that I stay in*" (Participant 4).

PA prevention. The biggest change in participant's PA was due to no longer being able to attend the gym to work out by themselves or as part of a group class. Others who took part in indoor sport (racquetball, climbing, curling and martial arts) or group-sport outside (group cycling and football) were also prevented from doing so:

...it certainly put the kibosh on group cycling so that stopped... I'd be lucky if I was going out once a week on my bike... I just couldn't be bothered to be honest. I just lost motivation. I was used to maybe going out, well certainly at least every week, for a maybe 50 or 60 miles but it kinda just stopped. And then when I did go out, it was just as much as I could... maybe 20 or 30 miles, if that sometimes (Participant 14).

...would have gone, maybe over the kind of spring, we would maybe have driven and gone for some longer hill walks. So, we were definitely constrained from doing that in the first phase of lockdown (Participant 17).

Some noticed that *“a lot more walking was kind of built into my days before lockdown”* (Participant 11) and that lockdown *“prevented me from doing the sort of required walking so it, it needed me to be motivated which you know, hard”* (Participant 10). Only two participants reported that the lockdown didn't prevent them from doing any PA they normally would *“because I just walked”* (Participant 18).

Participants stated that not getting to do their usual PA made them feel *“not particularly great to be honest”* (Participant 14), *“quite restricted and I was quite resentful”* (Participant 11) and *“a wee bit kinda anxious about not being able to do any physical activity”* (Participant 4):

...ehm pretty low pretty depressed to be honest with you cause eh not only do you not get the benefits from the physical exercise but you know almost everything that I was involved in is in some way or other like team related so it's the same group of people you see at your five-a-side football, so there's the comradery there, and then there's with the kung-fu school for the martial arts that's a very tight knit group of people so when you stop seeing them for ehm you know twice a week for each of the exercises, that's... it's not just the physical part you're missing but it's also the sociable aspect (Participant 10).

Some felt “*a bit annoyed really*” (Participant 19) and found it “*a bit frustrating*” (Participant 16), while one felt missing out on PA “*was frustrating, but in the grander scheme of things, it was the lesser of two evils as it were*” (Participant 15).

PA awareness. Participants were asked whether they felt they were more or less aware of their PA during lockdown, compared to before lockdown, with the vast majority of participants declaring they were more aware. Particularly, participants felt that they were “*very aware that I wasn’t doing anything in a sense*” (Participant 10) and that the lockdown

...just made you think more about making sure that you were active because you weren’t getting out to do your normal every day, you know, going back and forth to your work and whatever (Participant 13).

Only one participant felt they were “*probably more aware of it before (lockdown)... but actually during the lockdown period, not particularly*” (Participant 5).

Fitbit interaction. Participants were asked if they thought their interaction with their Fitbit watch and/or app changed during lockdown. Some participants felt that there was a change in how often they interacted with their Fitbit app/watch:

...there were a couple of days where I didn't put it (Fitbit watch) on, I guess yeah, I just sort of stopped thinking about my physical health as much... Yeah, I probably didn't check it (Fitbit app) half as much as I normally do (Participant 5).

A couple of participants felt they checked their Fitbit app more during the lockdown compared to before - *"yeah I probably did, sort of, look more at the app to make sure that I was doing a kind of decent number of steps a day"* (Participant 13).

For many participants, they felt their interaction with their Fitbit app/watch *"didn't change, no, I just used it the same way"* (Participant 19) during lockdown:

...no I don't think so, no. I think I just continued to wear it probably as much as possible because I was actually interested to see, like for example, does my RHR change as a result of the lack of exercise and so on... So I was, I'm a scientist myself so, I love data and so that's basically, that's one of the reasons why I use all these tools, I like looking at the graphs and looking at the trends and connecting up to my activities and so on, so no I continued to do this just to monitor it for myself (Participant 10).

7.3.6.4 PA after Lockdown

Amount and type of PA. Participants were asked whether they felt they did more or less PA once the lockdown was lifted, compared to during lockdown. Four participants felt they did more PA after lockdown, four felt they did less and three felt it was *"probably about the same*

overall” (Participant 17). The difference in answers stemmed from the different working/living situations. Those who did less after lockdown attributed it to *“now that obviously I’m back at the office again”* (Participant 4) and *“because I started working, I don’t have as much time”* (Participant 18). Those who did more PA recognised that this may have been due to the restrictions easing *“in the summer so it was warm and you know, I was probably more likely to feel like it would be good to get out”* (Participant 14). However, the main reason for the increase in activity was getting back *“to the gym”* (Participant 5), it being *“possible to play outside five-a-side football again”* (Participant 10) and being able to travel to do *“a bit of hill walking as well”* (Participant 13).

For most participants, the type of PA was either *“pretty similar to before lockdown”* (Participant 11) or similar to during lockdown. For some, although they could go back to the gym post-lockdown, they hadn’t *“actually went back to the gym yet so, so no, I probably, I wouldn’t say that it’s (type of PA) changed that much”* (Participant 4):

I’m probably not going to actual the gym building itself as much as I did before. So I’m maybe only going twice a week now. I’m continuing with the walking and the running and using the equipment that I’ve got it at home, but I think that’s just, I think that will increase, I think it’s just, at the moment I’m just not sure because the, ehm, COVID’s not quite settled yet. I think there’s a bit of a wariness about actually attending the gym, and when I do go, I get frustrated that people that are not cleaning the equipment, so I just think oh well. So there’s a bit of, ehm, hesitance about going back as much as I used to do, but I’m hoping that will change... (Participant 16).

The most common change from after lockdown compared to before lockdown was the introduction of “*doing more bodyweight exercises*” (Participant 15) and “*relying more now on doing stuff in the house*” (Participant 14).

Relationship with PA. Five participants felt they had a better relationship with PA post-lockdown and only one participant felt their relationship with PA was “*not as good... because I feel like I’m no longer as motivated to do it as I used to be*” (Participant 10). Five participants also felt their relationship with PA wasn’t “*any different to be honest*” (Participant 16) as “*I’ve always valued it. I’ve always put it high up on the list as it were*” (Participant 15) and “*it’s something I’ve always done. I just had to alter what I did*” (Participant 19). The reasons given for a positive change were:

...ehm just because I had more time to actually like I don't know, go out and go a walk and stuff like that, that I probably wouldn't have done otherwise part from on a Sunday most weeks (Participant 4).

I would say I probably do more different forms of it. Ehm it's nice, I really enjoyed exercising as a family and going out on bikes (Participant 11).

I didn't do anything indoors. I didn't do any and that's probably been one of my weaknesses over, over the years is that I've concentrated far too much on aerobic exercise and not enough strength. And I certainly think that that's something that's come out of this whole episode is that I'm much happier doing strength exercise, strength-

based exercises, y'know doing a wee bit of yoga and a wee bit of, y'know like my squats, my press ups and things (Participant 14).

Fitbit interaction. Most participants felt their interaction with their Fitbit watch/app was “*just the same*” (Participant 15) once lockdown was lifted. Only two participants felt there was a change: one noticed how they were “*more determined to record stuff*” (Participant 14), as their PA increased once lockdown was lifted; the other felt, after their Fitbit interaction decreased during lockdown, their interaction was now “*pretty much back to normal*” (Participant 5).

General comments. Before finishing the interviews, participants were asked if they had any general comments on PA and the Scotland lockdown. Some mentioned how:

...it's just made me appreciate how important exercise is, not just from a physical health, ehm, which is something I've always thought about, but I suppose I'm thinking more about my mental health... I think that's been really an eye opener (Participant 16)

I think it made me realise the, much more than before, the effect it had on my mood. You know, it seemed like having a positive effect. I don't think I was so aware of it for me because I was just busy. But yeah, it kind of became a way of you know, of looking after myself and making sure my mood stayed okay during lockdown (Participant 11).

Some comments were a little less positive regarding PA and the lockdown, with a participant stating they “*just sort of gave up on the idea*” (Participant 5). Another participant weighed up the long-term damage that could emerge from locking down the country:

I keep wondering about this, like, the overall effect that limiting people’s ability to take part in physical activity might have in the long term and whether... the danger that happens when people put on like half a stone to a stone during this time, the dangers that they might face long term, it might end up outweighing the, eh, sort of short-term risk of catching the virus. That’s just something that I keep thinking about, it’s just that all of this, the lockdown restrictions and so on that are put upon us – they might end up doing more damage in the long term than they’re saving us from in the short term (Participant 10).

One participant mentioned that they hoped the government wouldn’t enact another full lockdown:

...because it was really... it was pretty grim. In terms of not being able to go out with anybody else, not being able to walk or run or cycle with other people. I think we should just, if we have a lockdown, you know, keep schools open, keep universities open, whatever, and do, do what we can to sort of try and keep people in contact. I think we should just try and learn the lessons, I think, from that first lockdown (Participant 14).

7.4 Discussion

The current study adds to the emerging data evidencing the extent to which the COVID-19 lockdown influenced PA behaviours in the UK's adult population. The difference in PA levels, prior-to and during lockdown, was investigated using a mixed-methods approach. Specifically, Fitbit data from four distinct weeks were compared: the 'year before' lockdown (24/03/19 – 30/03/19); the 'month before' lockdown (24/02/20 – 01/03/20); the 'start' of lockdown (24/03/20 – 30/03/20); and a 'month in' to lockdown (21/04/20 – 27/04/20). The primary findings were that Fitbit measured PA decreased upon the commencement of the UK lockdown. Specifically, there were significant changes in average total daily minutes spent in light and MVPA, as well as average total daily EE across the four weeks. Wear-time, step count and HR did not significantly change across the four weeks.

Average total daily minutes spent in MVPA saw the greatest change, with significantly less MVPA at the 'start' of lockdown compared to all other weeks (Figure 7-1). This is understandable as with the 'start' of lockdown, the UK government introduced the rule of only being allowed out of the house for one hour per day to exercise. The qualitative data collected from semi-structured interviews show that participants were prevented from doing their normal PA during lockdown, such as attending the gym (including gym-based classes), taking part in indoor-sport (racquetball, climbing, curling and martial arts) or group-sport outside (cycling and football). This reduction of PA upon the commencement of the UK lockdown was observed in other studies. Smartphone-measured PA decreased by 37% during the first week of lockdown, compared to January 2020 (McCarthy, Potts and Fisher, 2021). Strain et al., (2022b) found that self-reported PA participation in general reduced from 83% in 2016-2019, to 77%

in 2020, when comparing the same time period (mid-April to mid-May). Similarly, Salman et al., (2021) discovered that UK older adults' self-reported METs (min/week) significantly decreased during lockdown compared to before.

What is interesting to observe however, is that MVPA significantly increased a 'month in' to the lockdown, even though these measures were still in place, although they did not return to pre-COVID-19 levels. These findings are similar to the results of another UK-based study that investigated COVID-19 lockdown-related changes in PA using Fitbit data. However, they also observed an increase in MVPA from the week before- to -the beginning of lockdown which continued to increase in the weeks after lockdown began, surpassing pre-COVID-19 levels (Kingsnorth et al., 2021). The authors looked at the weekly change in PA over 30 weeks (02/12/19 to 22/06/20), which may account for the earlier and continued detected increase in MVPA, whereas the current study looked at 4 distinct weeks spanning one year. Spence et al., (2021) found that 57% of UK study participants self-reported that they either maintained or increased their PA during lockdown, however, they asked participants about their current PA levels in June 2020, compared to the three months prior to lockdown - therefore missing the initial period of stricter rules around leaving the house which ended in May 2020. Bu et al., (2021) found that 62% of participants self-reported little change in their PA between March and August 2020, with 9% reporting an increase in PA during lockdown, however this data was collected weekly over several months whereas the current study looked at four distinct weeks. The inconsistent findings within the previous literature are likely due to the distinctive methodologies adopted to capture PA behaviour change and the differing definitions of 'during lockdown'.

In the current study, the increase in MVPA a month into the lockdown may be due to the adoption of new types of PA, e.g., at-home workouts and exercising as a family, as participants stated they became more aware of their PA during lockdown as they knew they were not doing enough. A 'month in' to lockdown also coincided with an increase, although not significant ($136 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$; $P = 0.36$), in average total daily EE compared to the 'start' of lockdown, as can be seen in Figure 7-2. Average total daily EE the 'year before' was significantly higher than the 'start' and a 'month in' to lockdown. Also, EE a 'month before' was significantly higher than the 'start' of lockdown. However, a recent systematic review has shown Fitbit wearables (as well as many other commercially available wearables) to vary widely in their EE estimates in controlled and free living settings, with a tendency to underestimate (Fuller *et al.*, 2020).

Minutes spent in light intensity activity the 'month before' lockdown were significantly higher than a 'month in' to lockdown and while not significant, time spent in light intensity did decrease by 12% with the onset of lockdown. These results confirm the findings of Kingsnorth *et al.*, (2021), although they observed a steeper decrease in light PA at the start of the UK lockdown and found it start to increase by a month in, whereas in the current study, time spent in light intensity PA had continue to reduce by a month in. However, as the current study looked at four separate weeks, it is impossible to say what happened between the 'start' of lockdown and a 'month in'. There are fewer studies to compare our light intensity findings with as most of the available data relating to COVID-19 PA behaviour change are self-reported and as light intensity activity tends to account for household tasks and is generally more intermittent, it is therefore less likely to be recalled (Strain *et al.*, 2022b). However, understanding the change in light PA during lockdown is essential as higher levels of even light PA in social-distancing

older adults during the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in less symptoms of depression (Callow *et al.*, 2020).

Although step count changes across the four weeks were not statistically significant, there was a 21% reduction in average daily step count at the ‘start’ of lockdown compared to the ‘year before’ (Figure 7-3). Considering only 61.4% of the population in England met the UK guideline of 150 minutes of moderate intensity PA from Nov 2020 – 2021 (GOV.UK, 2022a), any reduction in daily PA is cause for concern. Interestingly, Pépin *et al.*, (2020) found that countries that implemented partial or no lockdown had little to no changes in average daily step count compared to the pre-pandemic period. Therefore, future studies should further investigate the impact of lockdowns in comparison to countries that did not have one or only partially locked down.

Interestingly, while wear-time did not change significantly across the observed weeks and participants largely reported no change in their Fitbit use pre-, during- and post-lockdown – data in this study (Table 7-2) shows that mean wear-time was lowest the year before, with a considerably larger range than all other weeks. Therefore, the changes in PA observed cannot be explained by participants wearing their Fitbit less upon the commencement of the lockdown.

A secondary aim was to explore, qualitatively, how and why PA behaviours changed during lockdown, as well as after lockdown. Interestingly some participants mentioned in the interviews that they felt they exercised more at the beginning of lockdown, which then decreased as time went on. This is contrary to our overall findings, where PA decreased in general upon commencement of the lockdown, and then had increased by the following month.

However, interviews were conducted in October 2020, after the conclusion of the UK's first official lockdown, therefore there may be some recall bias. Regardless of whether participants had accurately depicted their PA behaviour change, even a perceived decrease in PA has recently been associated with an increase in stress and anxiety (Duncan *et al.*, 2020). Faulkner *et al.*, (2021) found that individuals with negatively affected PA as a result of lockdown reported poorer wellbeing and mental health. This was confirmed by the current study, with participants noting that lockdown prevented them from doing certain types of PA, particularly group-based, which ultimately negatively affected their mental health. Encouragingly, throughout the interviews conducted as part of the current study, some participants mentioned that they felt like the lockdown enabled them to try working out with family or new types of PA such as online, video-based exercises during lockdown, which have recently been shown to illicit improved feelings of psychological, physical and social wellbeing (Cronshaw, 2021). Therefore, promoting these types of at-home activities may be beneficial in a similar lockdown event, or generally to help support more isolated individuals who are unable to make it to a physical class or gym.

This is the first study, to our knowledge, that has investigated the change in PA behaviours across four distinct weeks: the 'year before', the 'month before', the 'start' and a 'month in' to the UK COVID-19 lockdown. By utilising a mixed-methods approach, we were able to gain insight into participants' individual experience of how the lockdown impacted their PA, as well as objectively measured outcomes. By looking at a full week's worth of data a 'year before' lockdown we were able to compare pre-lockdown and during-lockdown data that was representative of the exact same time of year and season. However, there are some limitations. The data in the current study may not be comparable to the average UK resident for several reasons. Prior to the lockdown being introduced, vulnerable people and those at high-risk of

COVID-19 complications were advised to self-isolate, therefore the changes observed across the four weeks may have differed in these populations. Furthermore, although participants were recruited via social media with limited inclusion criteria (18 years of age or older, with no physical mobility issues, and currently using a HR-enabled Fitbit) all participants exceeded the PA guidelines across all weeks. This may be due to the study being specifically about PA behaviour and people with an interest in PA may have been more inclined to take part (Bietz et al., 2016). Also, Fitbit owners, and other fitness tracking device owners, tend to be more physically active (Xie, Jo and Hong, 2020). Another possible and unavoidable limitation in regards to study sample biases, is that only Fitbit users willing to share their data with the research team could take part, with previous literature showing that not everyone is happy to share personal health data (Bietz et al., 2016; Cheung et al., 2016). Additionally, Fitbit, as well as other activity tracker manufacturers, can update their firmware and algorithms spontaneously and without notice, thereby potentially affecting the results of the current study and other longitudinal studies. Lastly, nine participant's data were excluded from analysis, leaving a small sample size of eleven. This was due to three participants having no data collected over the four weeks inspected, one participant with no collected data for two out of the four weeks, and another participant with no data for one of the four weeks. Additionally, two participants did not meet the criteria for a valid week (≥ 4 valid days), one participant had no HR data collected and the data of one participant could not be downloaded.

In conclusion, PA behaviours were negatively affected by the COVID-19 lockdown with participants noting feelings of depression, frustration and anxiety due to not being able to partake in their normal PA. Encouragingly, PA increased a month into the lockdown, although not to pre-COVID-19 levels, with some participants exploring new ways to be physically

active. Therefore, in the event of a similar pandemic situation, health officials should encourage participation in PA for both physical and mental health.

CHAPTER 8: General Discussion

8.1 Introduction

Regular PA participation and a reduction in SB has long been understood to elicit extensive positive health effects, such as a reduction in the risk of heart failure, cancer, CVD, type-2 diabetes, premature mortality and stroke (Hupin *et al.*, 2015; Pandey *et al.*, 2015; Kyu *et al.*, 2016; Wang *et al.*, 2022). Understanding these benefits to human life has been underpinned by the ability to measure PA and SB. The methodologies adopted to measure free living PA have transformed over the last century, beginning with the simple mechanical pedometer (Stunkard, 1960) and progressing to consumer activity trackers and smartphones. Numerous studies have been conducted on the validity and feasibility of such technology. This thesis extends our understanding of measuring and monitoring free living PA with wearable technology and the importance of being able to do so accurately and remotely. In this final chapter, the findings from four empirical studies will be summarised and the implications will be considered in the context of PA measurement.

8.2 Summary of main findings

8.2.1 Study 1 (Chapter 4) – Validity of the iPhone M7 Motion Coprocessor to Estimate PA during Structured and Free-Living Activities in Healthy Adults

The aims of this study were to 1) assess the validity of the iPhone M7 motion coprocessor for estimating step count and subsequently estimating EE (with the use of the ActivityTracker app) during treadmill walking, jogging, running, stationary cycling, and an aerobics session, 2)

compare measurements of step count between the iPhone and GT3X+ during a two-week period of free living.

To address aim 1, a single experimental trial was conducted in the laboratory to determine the validity of iPhone estimates of step count and EE in comparison to MC and IC, respectively. There was almost perfect agreement in measurements of step count between iPhone and MC during treadmill walking, jogging and running. The iPhone was most accurate at the vigorous ($8.0 \pm 1.1 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) intensity and least accurate at the moderate intensity ($6.5 \pm 0.9 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), suggesting that there is not a linear relationship between speed and accuracy, contrary to the findings of Major and Alford (2016). However, the differences found between the three speeds in the current study were minimal, with MAPEs $<2\%$ for all three speeds. The iPhone significantly underestimated EE during the treadmill trial compared to IC and agreement between the measurements was poor. Lastly, throughout stationary cycling and aerobics, the iPhone significantly underestimated EE and showed poor agreement with IC.

To address aim 2, a two-week observational period took place during which free-living PA data was concurrently monitored using the iPhone and GT3X+ accelerometer. Estimates of daily step count from the iPhone and GT3X+ were compared. The agreement in daily step count between the two devices was substantial, however the iPhone recorded significantly fewer daily steps ($1,095 \text{ steps}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) compared to the GT3X+.

The findings of this study indicate that the iPhone 5S is an appropriate tool for estimating step count during treadmill walking and jogging, but not for estimating EE. Furthermore, when

compared to the GT3X+ during a period of free living, the iPhone significantly underestimated daily step count. This suggests that the iPhone may not be an appropriate method for measuring daily PA.

8.2.2 Study 2 (Chapter 5) – A Mixed-Methods Study to Explore the Use of Smartphones in Estimating Physical Activity during Free Living

The aims of this study were to 1) evaluate the convergent validity of a user's own iPhone for measuring daily step count by comparing to both an iPhone and GT3X+ accelerometer that were worn continuously around the waist in healthy adults, 2) explore, using a qualitative approach, the habits of each user with their mobile device during the monitoring period, their previous experience with wearable technologies for PA monitoring, and their perception on the use of smartphones to measure PA and SB.

To address aim 1, participants who used an iPhone 5S or newer as their personal smartphone were provided with and asked to carry an iPhone 5S and GT3X+ accelerometer around their waist in a neoprene pouch for seven days, while using their personal iPhone as they normally would. They were asked to only remove the devices for sleep, bathing, or swimming and to record in a provided diary any extended periods of non-wear time. Results showed that participants' personal iPhone recorded significantly fewer daily steps than a continuously worn iPhone (1,284 steps·day⁻¹) and GT3X+ accelerometer (882 steps·day⁻¹). Wear-time data confirms that participants' personal iPhone was carried on their person less than the waist-mounted devices.

To achieve the second aim, participants took part in a short semi-structured interview. The qualitative findings revealed that participants would leave their phone on a surface when at work or home, which is likely the reason for the underestimation of daily steps.

The findings from study 2 suggest that when using a smartphone in everyday life, the daily step count measured will likely be lower than actual steps taken. Therefore, using a smartphone as a PA monitoring device should only be considered an estimate of daily step count. Users should subsequently account for this underestimation of objective PA when interpreting their data and be aware that the accuracy of their smartphone in measuring habitual PA depends directly on how frequently they have it on their person.

8.2.3 Study 3 (Chapter 6) – Evaluation of a DHP: The Usability and Feasibility of the Lenus Health Platform Within Healthy Adults and Healthcare Professionals.

The aims of this study were to 1) Determine the usability of a novel DHP (the Lenus Health Platform) and associated apps in a sample of healthy adults fulfilling the role of secondary care patients (mock patients), 2) determine the usability of a novel DHP (the Lenus Health Platform) in a sample of HCPs currently working in the UK's publicly funded healthcare system, the NHS.

To achieve the first aim, a convenience sample of healthy adults were presented with a simulated healthcare scenario requiring them to self-monitor BP, BM and daily step count over two weeks and share the data with the research team using the Lenus Health Platform. Following this, a semi-structured interview was conducted to discuss their experience. The themes that were generated from the interviews indicate that participants found the apps easy to use, recognised the importance of the metrics being measured, and believed that integrating the Lenus Health Platform into the current NHS system would enhance quality of care. The idea of using the apps to share data with HCPs and reduce in-person contact with the NHS was viewed positively.

To address aim 2, a purposive sample of HCPs currently employed by the NHS were given access to the Lenus Health Platform along with mock patient data. After a review period, the HCPs participated in semi-structured interviews to discuss the platform's usability, feasibility, and acceptability. The interviews revealed that HCPs in both primary and secondary care felt that a service like the Lenus Health Platform, which allows patients to share their data remotely with HCPs, would be a valuable resource for the NHS. HCPs noted that patients tracking their health parameters over time would offer a more accurate picture of their overall health, enabling them to deliver more efficient care. While HCPs acknowledged some barriers to implementing a service like the Lenus Health Platform within the NHS, they felt that these challenges were considerably outweighed by the potential benefits.

The findings from study 3 indicate that both cohorts agreed the Lenus Health Platform has the potential for successful implementation within the NHS. As a result, this study provided proof

of concept, laying the groundwork for a comprehensive evaluation of the Lenus Health Platform within the existing NHS healthcare system.

8.2.4 Study 4 (Chapter 7) – Fitbit Measured Physical Activity Decreased upon Commencement of UK COVID-19 Lockdown

The aims of this study were to 1) investigate the difference in adult PA behaviours, prior-to, during and after a national lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic, 2) explore, qualitatively, how and why PA behaviours changed during and post-lockdown.

To address aim 1, participants answered basic demographic questions through a data-encrypted website. On the same platform, they granted access to their Fitbit data for four specific weeks: the year before, the month before, the start, and a month into the first UK COVID-19 lockdown. Data downloaded from Fitbit included: step count ($\text{steps}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$); PA intensity (METs); HR (bpm) and EE ($\text{kcal}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$). The results revealed that: Fitbit-measured MVPA at the start of lockdown was significantly lower compared to all other weeks; light intensity activity the month before lockdown was significantly higher than a month in; and daily EE the year before was significantly higher than the start and a month into lockdown. Wear-time, HR, and step count did not show significant changes over the four weeks.

To achieve the second aim, participants were asked via the website if they would be willing to be contacted later to participate in a virtual, semi-structured interview about how and why their PA behaviours may have changed due to social distancing and lockdown measures. The

interviews included questions about the participant's views on PA tracking, the duration of their Fitbit use, other methods of PA tracking or monitoring, as well as questions related to their PA levels before, during, and after the COVID-19 lockdown. The interviews revealed that participants were unable to engage in their usual physical activities during lockdown. These activities included going to the gym (and attending gym-based classes), participating in indoor sports such as racquetball, climbing, curling, and martial arts, as well as outdoor group sports like cycling and football. Subsequently, participants had feelings of anxiety, depression and frustration.

The findings from this final study confirm previous work indicating that PA behaviours were negatively affected by the COVID-19 lockdown (McCarthy, Potts and Fisher, 2021; Salman et al., 2021; Strain et al., 2022b). Encouragingly, PA levels increased a month into the lockdown, though they did not return to pre-COVID-19 levels, with some participants finding new ways to stay active. Thus, in the event of a similar pandemic situation, health officials should promote PA to support both physical and mental well-being.

8.3 The iPhone as a PA measurement tool

Today, most adults carry a smartphone equipped with hardware capable of measuring locomotion, with 76% of the UK population reporting smartphone ownership in 2018 (Taylor & Silver, 2019). Utilising the smartphone as a PA monitor can reduce study costs and participant burden as no extra device, such as an accelerometer, is required. Therefore, the smartphone has been adopted as a PA monitor in research studies (Althoff *et al.*, 2017). Many studies have shown smartphones to be accurate at estimating step count within a laboratory

setting (Höchsmann et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2016), however they can tend to underestimate step count during free living (Duncan et al., 2018; Amagasa *et al.*, 2019).

In this PhD thesis, the validity of the iPhone 5S was assessed throughout various laboratory physical activities as well as free living (chapter 4). Furthermore, the validity of users' own iPhone for measuring step-count during free living was also evaluated (chapter 5). The collective findings of this PhD show that an iPhone used naturally (not continuously worn) underestimates daily step count by ~1,000 steps compared to a continuously worn GT3X+. Furthermore, a naturally used iPhone measures ~1,300 steps less than a continuously worn iPhone. This underestimation of ~1,300 daily steps is in line with previous research (Duncan et al., 2018; Amagasa *et al.*, 2019). However, Duncan et al., (2018) compared the iPhone 6 to the GT3X+, while Amagasa *et al.*, (2019) compared iPhones 5S, 6, 6S, 6plus, SE and 7 to a pedometer (Kenz Lifecorder). Consequently, it can be assumed that when using an iPhone in everyday life to estimate daily step count, the real total is around 1,000 steps more than the value provided by the iPhone. This is not an insignificant number, as a 1,000 daily step increase can reduce arterial stiffness, a key marker of cardiovascular and morbidity (Cavero-Redondo et al., 2019).

The iPhone showed almost perfect agreement with MC steps during the treadmill trial in chapter 4, while the GT3X+ demonstrated moderate agreement with this gold standard measurement. This suggests that the underestimation of steps during free-living in chapters 4 and 5 may be attributed to how frequently participants carried the phone and where they positioned it on their body. While chapter 5 used qualitative methods to gather informative data on why participants would leave the iPhone behind while taking steps, it relied solely on

participant's recall. Furthermore, the iPhone does not provide a direct measure of wear-time and, to our knowledge, no established methods exist for calculating this metric. Therefore, daily wear-time for both waist-worn and personal iPhones in chapter 5 was estimated based on the number of hours with at least one recorded step. Subsequently, this estimation of wear-time should be considered when interpreting the findings of chapter 5.

Throughout the stationary cycling and aerobics trial in chapter 4, the iPhone significantly underestimated EE and showed poor agreement with IC. The likely cause of the consistent underestimation of EE during the cycling trial is the stable position of the trunk, where the device was placed. While a shank placement of the GT3X+ accelerometer has previously been shown to improve accuracy of pedal-revolution count during cycling when compared to a waist placement (Gatti et al., 2016), the same trunk placement was used throughout all activities of the laboratory trial as it ecologically valid. Therefore, these findings are relevant and generalisable to everyday life.

8.4 The Effect of COVID-19 Lockdowns on PA

The qualitative results of chapter 7 revealed that the COVID-19 lockdown negatively affected participants' mental health, eliciting feelings of depression and anxiety. These findings confirm those of other studies investigating mental health changes within UK adults during the COVID-19 pandemic (Pierce *et al.*, 2020; O'Connor *et al.*, 2021). However, these studies didn't investigate why these changes occurred. One participant within chapter 7 mentioned that they were going out for a run roughly three times a week at the beginning of lockdown, however

after a few weeks they felt that ‘lockdown depression’ set in and they stopped. Another participant stated that they were used to going out at least once a week on a group-cycling session, but upon the commencement of the COVID-19 lockdown and the rule of only one form of exercise per day alone or with members of your household, they stopped (GOV.UK, 2020). Instead, they didn’t go out as regularly and would only manage about half the distance of what they did previously, due to a loss of motivation. Several participants mentioned a lack of motivation to participate in PA directly caused by the lockdown. This is to be expected as autonomy is one of the three innate psychological needs which when unfulfilled leads to reduced motivation and subsequently well-being (Ryan and Deci, 2000).

While step count changes between the year before, month before, start and a month into lockdown were not statistically significantly different, there was an average reduction of 2,465 daily steps at the start of lockdown compared to the year before. This reduction of step count during the UK COVID-19 lockdown was also found by Janssen and colleagues (2020). They theorise that this was down to only being allowed out the house to exercise for one hour per day and a switch to home-based PA, which would involve less walking around. The qualitative findings from chapter 7 support this, with participants stating that they did much less ‘required walking’ in lockdown that they used to do in normal day-to-day life.

8.5 Strengths and limitations

The use of the iPhone 5S throughout this thesis may also be considered a limitation due to its first being released in 2013 and no longer being sold by Apple. However, it was not possible to purchase enough newer iPhones within the confinements of a PhD budget. Nonetheless,

when considering the oldest iPhone used by participants of study 2 was the iPhone 6, iPhone 5S' successor, the iPhone 5S isn't so outdated to not be relevant. The inclusion of different models of iPhone in chapter 5 was also an unavoidable limitation as it was not possible to recruit enough participants who used an iPhone 5S as their personal smartphone. There were eight different models of iPhone used by participants in chapter 5, which highlights the issue of new consumer wearable devices constantly being released to market and subsequently the issue of incompatibility of PA estimates between consumer wearable devices (Strain et al., 2022a). Therefore, taking this into account, the true reason behind the significant difference in daily step count between the iPhones is uncertain. Future studies should look to repeat our study using the same smartphone model across all participants to eliminate this uncertainty.

This thesis was the first to compare daily step counts from an iPhone 5S and a GT3X+ worn continuously around the waist to participant's own iPhone used normally in daily life. However, these waist-mounted devices face similar limitations to personal phones, as participants sometimes removed them or forgot to wear them for certain periods. Although not normalising the data for wear-time could be viewed as a limitation, this approach offers valuable understanding of how an individual's behaviour with their personal smartphone influenced PA measurement (i.e. step count). Normalising for wear-time would have veiled this important observation.

The addition of qualitative data is a major strength of this thesis; however, a potential limitation is the length of the interviews. In chapter 5, interviews ranged from 9.5 to 31 minutes, the lower end being particularly short for a qualitative interview. This was likely due to the questions in the interview schedule being quite brief and to the point, e.g., "have you done any other kind

of PA or health monitoring before?” and “where did you tend to keep your personal phone on you?”. There were only a couple of questions that elicited a longer response, e.g., “how would you feel if you were asked to do this kind of PA monitoring by your GP for an extended period of time?”. The qualitative aspect of this study provided interesting data, e.g., participants who had previously monitored their PA found this type of behaviour change technique improved their motivation to be more physically active and less sedentary, which is in line with previous research (Compernelle *et al.*, 2019; Nuss *et al.*, 2021). However, the main reason behind the interviews was to gain insight on user behaviour with smartphones that would otherwise be missed with a quantitative-only methodology. Nevertheless, this study was the first of its kind (to our knowledge) to adopt a mixed-methods approach when evaluating the validity of a user’s own smartphone for measuring daily step count.

With respect to transferability, the qualitative data in chapters 5, 6 and 7 enriched the understanding of user habits with smartphones, the usability of a DHP, and how/why PA behaviours changed during and post-lockdown. The qualitative findings of chapter 7 (e.g. disruption to routine, technology-mediated motivation, importance of group PA) resonate with broader experiences during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic, enhancing analytic transferability (Polit & Beck, 2010). By providing thick description of participant contexts and behaviours, this work allows readers to judge the relevance to other populations or settings, such as health promotion or digital intervention design (Korstjens & Moser, 2018). However, a major limitation of chapter 6 is that while the study was carried out as a proof-of-concept study prior to a proposed similar study within the NHS, no proof-of-concept guidelines or frameworks were followed. Therefore, the findings are likely not generalisable to other proof-of-concept studies (Johnson, Adkins & Chauvin, 2020).

This thesis was the first to investigate the change in PA behaviours across the year before, month before, start and a month into lockdown using a mixed-methods approach. This enabled the collection of qualitative insights into how the lockdown impacted participants' PA, alongside objectively measured outcomes. However, although participants were recruited via social media and with minimal inclusion criteria, chapter 7 lacked representative sampling. Participants all exceeded the PA guidelines across all four weeks, which is not representative of the Scottish adult population, with only 65% of Scottish adults meeting the UK PA guidelines for MVPA (Scottish Government, 2022). Therefore, the findings of this chapter may not be generalisable to the broader UK citizen.

8.6 Significance

Physical inactivity is a major risk factor for premature mortality and NCDs (Lee et al., 2012). Although NCDs are often associated with older adults, 9 million deaths worldwide in 2019 occurred in individuals under the age of 60 (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network, 2020). In the same year, over 800,000 deaths globally and almost 11,000 deaths in the UK were attributed to low PA (Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network, 2020). Conversely, regular PA and limited SB supports physical and mental health at all ages.

Measuring population PA is crucial for understanding the impact of PA on NCDs, which has predominantly involved the use of PA questionnaires and accelerometers in research. However, smartphones have been recently used in PA surveillance studies (Althoff et al., 2017). A key

advantage of using smartphones as PA trackers is the ability to download third-party apps with custom algorithms to estimate variables, such as EE. Furthermore, with the use of internet-based DHPs such as the Lenus Health Platform, users can upload and store their smartphone-measured PA data, making it accessible to third parties remotely. However, the validity of smartphones to measure parameters of PA is lacking. Therefore, the purpose of the first study in this PhD was to assess the validity of the iPhone 5S' estimations of step count and EE within a laboratory setting, as well as daily step count during free living. The findings from this study expand upon previous works (Major & Alford, 2016), while also being a crucial first step in providing 'proof of concept' of the Lenus Health Platform and associated apps. The results of the third study established a foundation for a thorough evaluation of the Lenus Health Platform within the current NHS healthcare system. As mentioned in the foreword, the intended plan for study 4 was to explore patient and clinician user experience of the Lenus Health Platform within an NHS secondary care environment. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the study couldn't go ahead. Nonetheless, the Lenus Health Platform has continued to develop and is now widely utilised in the clinical environment, for example, by using predictive AI models to detect clinical risks early across a range of NCD, such as COPD and Heart Failure.

8.7 Future directions

This thesis has shown that smartphones may be a useful tool in PA monitoring, however, future directions may include advancements in sensor technology to improve the accuracy and reliability of measurements. Additionally, researchers can explore the development and validation of standardised algorithms that can be used across different smartphone models/apps to ensure consistency in data collection. Furthermore, studies should continue to compare

smartphone-based measurements with other established methods of PA assessment, such as accelerometers and pedometers, to determine the level of agreement and validity between these different measurement tools. Additionally, studies should look to repeat study 2 using the same smartphone model across all participants to eliminate the uncertainty of whether the findings were a result of the incompatibility of PA estimates between consumer wearable devices. Lastly, future research should also aim to enhance participant compliance and engagement with smartphone-based PA tracking, as adherence to the technology and consistent usage is essential for obtaining accurate and reliable data. However, the effect of smartphone use in general should be taken into consideration as spending more time using a smartphone has been associated with low levels of PA, high levels of SB, poor sleep quality and poor state of mood (Grimaldi-Puyana et al., 2020).

In recent decades, rapid advancements in digital technology have brought transformative changes to nearly every aspect of human activity, leading to the rise of digital health as a significant field of research. Digital health includes a broad array of technologies and innovations designed to transform healthcare delivery and enhance patient outcomes (McGinnis, Fineberg and Dzau, 2021). However, the rapid digital transformation in healthcare has the potential to widen health inequalities (Sieck *et al.*, 2021; Richardson *et al.*, 2022). Health interventions can lead to disparities, as they are often adopted unevenly, leaving disadvantaged populations underserved. To avoid the digital transformation in healthcare creating health inequalities, it is recommended that healthcare systems implement a strategy for digital health that is informed by digital inclusion. This involves ensuring that the community's access to devices and internet connectivity is considered, and patients are supported in both adopting and consistently using the technology. Digital inclusion involves providing equitable access to, and effective use of, information and communication

technologies, which includes affordable broadband internet; devices that support internet use; access to training in digital literacy; reliable technical support; and online content and applications that promote self-reliance, engagement, and collaboration (O'Connor *et al.*, 2021). These elements are essential for leveraging mobile technology in healthcare.

8.8 Overall conclusions

Physical inactivity is a major risk factor for premature death and NCDs. Participating in regular PA and reducing time spent in sedentary behaviour supports physical and mental health. Measuring population PA is crucial for understanding its impact on NCDs. This thesis was the first to compare iPhone 5S estimations of both laboratory-based step count and EE with gold-standards. The data showed that the iPhone 5S is a suitable tool for estimating step count, but not for estimating EE, during treadmill walking and jogging. Improving the prediction algorithms in mobile apps to include HR and/or GPS data could enhance the iPhone's accuracy in estimating EE (Howe, Moir and Easton, 2017). Compared to a continuously waist-worn accelerometer in free-living conditions, the iPhone 5S significantly underestimated daily step count.

Furthermore, this thesis was the first to compare daily step counts from an iPhone 5S worn continuously around the waist to participant's own iPhone used normally in daily life. Using a mixed-methods methodology allowed us to gain insight on user behaviour with smartphones that would have been overlooked with a purely quantitative methodology. The findings from chapter 5 confirm the free living findings of chapter 4 and previous research - the iPhone significantly underestimates daily step count when compared to a continuously worn device

(Duncan et al., 2018; Amagasa *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, we advise users to consider this underestimation of objective PA when interpreting their data and to be aware that their smartphone's accuracy in measuring habitual activity depends on how frequently they carry it with them and keep it on their person.

The findings from chapter 6 reveal that both cohorts agreed the Lenus Health Platform has strong potential for successful implementation within the NHS. Consequently, this chapter serves as proof of concept, establishing a foundation for a comprehensive evaluation of the Lenus Health Platform within the current NHS healthcare system.

The final experimental chapter of this thesis supports previous research showing that PA behaviours were negatively impacted by the COVID-19 lockdown (McCarthy, Potts and Fisher, 2021; Salman et al., 2021; Strain et al., 2022b). Interestingly, PA levels increased one month into the lockdown, although they did not return to pre-COVID-19 levels, with some participants discovering new ways to remain active. Therefore, in the event of a similar pandemic, health officials should encourage PA to support overall mental and physical well-being.

In conclusion, the findings of this PhD expand the knowledge of PA monitoring using mHealth technologies in both laboratory and free-living settings, provides proof of concept of a novel DHP and confirms previous evidence of a decline in PA at the onset of the COVID-19 lockdown.

References

Aadland, E. and Ylvisåker, E. (2015) 'Reliability of the Actigraph GT3X + Accelerometer in Adults under Free-Living Conditions', *PLoS ONE*, 10(8), pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0134606>.

ACSM (2017) *ACSM's Guidelines for Exercise Testing and Prescription (10th edition)*, Wolters Kluwer. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13398-014-0173-7.2>.

Activity and Health Research (1992) *Allied Dunbar National Fitness Survey. A Report on Activity Patterns and Fitness Levels: Main Findings*. . London: Sports Council and Health Education Authority.

Agarwal, R. *et al.* (2011) 'Role of home blood pressure monitoring in overcoming therapeutic inertia and improving hypertension control: A systematic review and meta-analysis', *Hypertension*, 57(1), pp. 29–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.110.160911>.

Åkerberg, A., Söderlund, A. and Lindén, M. (2016) 'Investigation of the validity and reliability of a smartphone pedometer application', *European Journal of Physiotherapy*, 18(3), pp. 185–193. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/21679169.2016.1174297>.

Allegrante, J.P., Wells, M.T. and Peterson, J.C. (2019) 'Interventions to Support Behavioral Self-Management of Chronic Diseases', *Annual Review of Public Health*. Annual Reviews Inc., pp. 127–146. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-040218-044008>.

Alley, S. *et al.* (2016) 'Interest and preferences for using advanced physical activity tracking devices: Results of a national cross-sectional survey', *BMJ Open*, 6(7), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-011243>.

Althoff, T. *et al.* (2017) ‘Large-scale physical activity data reveal worldwide activity inequality’, *Nature*, 547(7663), pp. 336–339. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature23018>.Large-scale.

Amagasa, S. *et al.* (2019) ‘How well iphones measure steps in free-living conditions: Cross-sectional validation study’, *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 7(1), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/10418>.

Antero Kesaniemi (Chair), Y. *et al.* (2001) ‘Dose-response issues concerning physical activity and health: an evidence-based symposium’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 33(Supplement), pp. S351–S358. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005768-200106001-00003>.

Appel, L.J. (2003) ‘Lifestyle Modification as a Means to Prevent and Treat High Blood Pressure’, *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, 14(90002), pp. 99S – 102. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.asn.0000070141.69483.5a>.

Arem, H. *et al.* (2015) ‘Leisure time physical activity and mortality: A detailed pooled analysis of the dose-response relationship’, *JAMA Internal Medicine*, 175(6), pp. 959–967. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2015.0533>.

Arogamam, G., Manivannan, N. and Harrison, D. (2019) ‘Review on Wearable Technology Sensors Used in Consumer Sport Applications’, *Sensors*, 19(1983), pp. 1–26.

Attig, C. and Franke, T. (2022) ‘Why do People Abandon Activity Trackers? The Role of User Diversity in Discontinued Use’, *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction*, pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2022.2067935>.

Bammann, K. *et al.* (2021) ‘Generation and validation of ActiGraph GT3X+ accelerometer cut-points for assessing physical activity intensity in older adults. The OUTDOOR ACTIVE

validation study', *Plos One*, 16(6), p. e0252615. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0252615>.

Banbury, A., Roots, A. and Nancarrow, S. (2014) 'Rapid review of applications of e-health and remote monitoring for rural residents', *Australian Journal of Rural Health*, 22(5), pp. 211–222. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajr.12127>.

Barreira, T. V. *et al.* (2013) 'Comparison of GT3X Accelerometer and YAMAX Pedometer Steps/Day in a Free-Living Sample of Overweight and Obese Adults', *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 10, pp. 263–270.

van der Berg, J.D. *et al.* (2016) 'Associations of total amount and patterns of sedentary behaviour with type 2 diabetes and the metabolic syndrome: The Maastricht Study', *Diabetologia*, 59(4), pp. 709–718. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-015-3861-8>.

Bietz, M.J. *et al.* (2016) 'Opportunities and challenges in the use of personal health data for health research', *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 23(e1), pp. 1–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocv118>.

Blair, S.N. *et al.* (1989) 'Physical Fitness and All-Cause Mortality. A Prospective Study of Healthy Men and Women', *JAMA: The Journal of the American Medical Association*, 262(17), pp. 2395–2401.

Blair, S.N. (2009) 'Physical inactivity: The biggest public health problem of the 21st century', *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 43(1), pp. 1–2. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1440-2440\(07\)70066-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1440-2440(07)70066-x).

Bland, M.J. and Altman, D.G. (1986) 'Statistical Methods for Assessing Agreement Between Two Methods of Clinical Measurement', *The Lancet*, 327(8476), pp. 307–310. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(86\)90837-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(86)90837-8).

- Blond, K. *et al.* (2020) ‘Association of high amounts of physical activity with mortality risk: A systematic review and meta-analysis’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 54(20), pp. 1195–1201. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2018-100393>.
- Bort-roig, J. *et al.* (2014) ‘Measuring and Influencing Physical Activity with Smartphone Technology: A Systematic Review’, *Sports Medicine*, 44, pp. 671–686. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-014-0142-5>.
- Boudreaux, B.D. *et al.* (2024) ‘Harmonization of three different accelerometers to classify the 24 h activity cycle’, *Physiological Measurement*, 45(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6579/ad37ed>.
- Brady, R. *et al.* (2022) ‘Patterns of Accelerometer-Measured Physical Activity and Health Outcomes in Adults: A Systematic Review’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 54(7), pp. 1155–1166. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000002900>.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) ‘Using thematic analysis in psychology’, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 7–101.
- Bravata, D.M. *et al.* (2007) ‘Using pedometers to increase physical activity and improve health: A systematic review’, *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 298(19), pp. 2296–2304. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.298.19.2296>.
- Bu, F. *et al.* (2021) ‘Longitudinal changes in physical activity during and after the first national lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic in England’, *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), pp. 1–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-97065-1>.
- Bull, F.C., Maslin, T.S. and Armstrong, T. (2009) ‘Global physical activity questionnaire (GPAQ): Nine country reliability and validity study’, *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 6(6), pp. 790–804. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.6.6.790>.

Cain, K.L. *et al.* (2013) ‘Using accelerometers in youth physical activity studies: a review of methods’, *Journal of physical activity & health*, 10(3), pp. 437–450. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.10.3.437>.

Callow, D.D. *et al.* (2020) ‘The Mental Health Benefits of Physical Activity in Older Adults Survive the COVID-19 Pandemic’, *American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 28(10), pp. 1046–1057. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jagp.2020.06.024>.

Caputo, E.L. and Reichert, F.F. (2020) ‘Studies of Physical Activity and COVID-19 during the Pandemic: A Scoping Review’, *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 17(12), pp. 1275–1284. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2020-0406>.

Casey, M. *et al.* (2014) ‘Patients’ experiences of using a smartphone application to increase physical activity: The SMART MOVE qualitative study in primary care’, *British Journal of General Practice*, 64(625), pp. 500–508. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp14X680989>.

Caspersen, C.J., Powell, K.E. and Christenson, G.M. (1985) ‘Physical Activity, Exercise, and Physical Fitness: Definitions and Distinctions for Health-Related Research’, *Public Health Reports*, 100(2), pp. 126–131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nq/s9-IX.228.365-f>.

Cavero-Redondo, I. *et al.* (2019) ‘Steps per Day and Arterial Stiffness: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis’, *Hypertension*, 73(2), pp. 350–363. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.118.11987>.

Chan, A. *et al.* (2022) ‘Reporting adherence, validity and physical activity measures of wearable activity trackers in medical research: A systematic review’, *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 160, p. 104696. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2022.104696>.

Cheung, C. *et al.* (2016) ‘Privacy attitudes among early adopters of emerging health technologies’, *PLoS ONE*, 11(11), pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0166389>.

Chief Medical Officers (2019) *UK Chief Medical Officers’ Physical Activity Guidelines*, Department of Health and Social Care. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/physical-activity-guidelines-uk-chief-medical-officers-report>.

Chow, C.K. *et al.* (2016) ‘mHealth in Cardiovascular Health Care’, *Heart Lung and Circulation*, pp. 802–807. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlc.2016.04.009>.

Ciere, Y. *et al.* (2019) ‘Implementation of an eHealth self-management care path for chronic somatic conditions’, *Clinical eHealth*, 2, pp. 3–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceh.2019.04.001>.

Collins, J.E. *et al.* (2019) ‘Validation of the fitbit charge 2 compared to the actigraph GT3X+ in older adults with knee osteoarthritis in free-living conditions’, *PLoS ONE*, 14(1), pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211231>.

Compernelle, S. *et al.* (2019) ‘Effectiveness of interventions using self-monitoring to reduce sedentary behavior in adults: A systematic review and meta-analysis’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*. BioMed Central Ltd. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-019-0824-3>.

Craig, C.L. *et al.* (2003) ‘International physical activity questionnaire: 12-Country reliability and validity’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 35(8), pp. 1381–1395. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/01.MSS.0000078924.61453.FB>.

Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2003). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Cronshaw, S. (2021) 'Web workouts and consumer well-being: The role of digital-physical activity during the UK COVID-19 lockdown', *The Journal of Consumer Affairs*, pp. 1–16.

Dall, P.M. *et al.* (2018) 'Characteristics of a Protocol to Collect Objective Physical Activity/Sedentary Behavior Data in a Large Study: Seniors USP (Understanding Sedentary Patterns)', *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 1(1), pp. 26–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jmpb.2017-0004>.

Dicianno, B.E. *et al.* (2016) 'Feasibility of using mobile health to promote self-management in Spina Bifida', *American Journal of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 95(6), pp. 425–437. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/PHM.0000000000000400>.

Ding, D. *et al.* (2020) 'Towards better evidence-informed global action: Lessons learnt from the Lancet series and recent developments in physical activity and public health', *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 54(8), pp. 462–468. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2019-101001>.

Doherty, A. *et al.* (2017) 'Large scale population assessment of physical activity using wrist worn accelerometers: The UK biobank study', *PLoS ONE*, 12(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0169649>.

Domin, A. *et al.* (2021) 'Smartphone-based interventions for physical activity promotion: Scoping review of the evidence over the last 10 years', *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 9(7). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/24308>.

Duncan, G.E. *et al.* (2020) ‘Perceived change in physical activity levels and mental health during COVID-19: Findings among adult twin pairs’, *PLoS ONE*, 15(8 August), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0237695>.

Duncan, M.J. *et al.* (2018) ‘Walk this way: validity evidence of iphone health application step count in laboratory and free-living conditions’, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 36(15), pp. 1695–1704. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2017.1409855>.

Dwyer, T. *et al.* (2007) ‘The inverse relationship between number of steps per day and obesity in a population-based sample - The AusDiab study’, *International Journal of Obesity*, 31(5), pp. 797–804. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ijo.0803472>.

van Dyck, D. *et al.* (2015) ‘International study of objectively measured physical activity and sedentary time with body mass index and obesity: IPEN adult study’, *International Journal of Obesity* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ijo.2014.115>.

Dyrstad, S.M. *et al.* (2014) ‘Comparison of self-reported versus accelerometer-measured physical activity’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 46(1), pp. 99–106. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0b013e3182a0595f>.

Ekelund, U. *et al.* (2019) ‘Dose-response associations between accelerometry measured physical activity and sedentary time and all cause mortality: Systematic review and harmonised meta-analysis’, *The BMJ*, 366, pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.l4570>.

Ekelund, U. *et al.* (2020) ‘Joint associations of accelerometer measured physical activity and sedentary time with all-cause mortality: A harmonised meta-analysis in more than 44 000 middle-aged and older individuals’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 54(24), pp. 1499–1506. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2020-103270>.

Evenson, K.R. *et al.* (2022) ‘Historical development of accelerometry measures and methods for physical activity and sedentary behavior research worldwide: A scoping review of observational studies of adults’, *PLoS ONE*, 17(11 November), pp. 1–27. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0276890>.

Evenson, K.R., Goto, M.M. and Furberg, R.D. (2015) ‘Systematic review of the validity and reliability of consumer-wearable activity trackers’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 12(159). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-015-0314-1>.

Ewing, C. *et al.* (1998) ‘ACSM Position Stand: The Recommended Quantity and Quality of Exercise for Developing and Maintaining Cardiorespiratory and Muscular Fitness, and Flexibility in Healthy Adults’, *Med. Sci. Sports Exerc*, 30(6), pp. 975–991. Available at: <http://ovidsp.tx.ovid.com.libproxy.csun.edu/sp3.15.1b/ovidweb.cgi>.

Ezzatvar, Y. *et al.* (2022) ‘Physical activity and risk of infection, severity and mortality of COVID-19: a systematic review and non-linear dose-response meta-analysis of data from 1 853 610 adults’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 56(20), pp. 1188–1193. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2022-105733>.

Faber, S., van Geenhuizen, M. and de Reuver, M. (2017) ‘eHealth adoption factors in medical hospitals: A focus on the Netherlands’, *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 100, pp. 77–89. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2017.01.009>.

Fairclough, S.J. *et al.* (2016) ‘Wear compliance and activity in children wearing wrist- and hip-mounted accelerometers’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 48(2), pp. 245–253. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000000771>.

Faulkner, J. *et al.* (2021) ‘Physical activity, mental health and well-being of adults during initial COVID-19 containment strategies: A multi-country cross-sectional analysis’, *Journal of*

Science and Medicine in Sport, 24(4), pp. 320–326. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2020.11.016>.

Feehan, L.M. *et al.* (2018) ‘Accuracy of fitbit devices: Systematic review and narrative syntheses of quantitative data’, *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 6(8). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/10527>.

Ferguson, T. *et al.* (2015) ‘The validity of consumer-level, activity monitors in healthy adults worn in free-living conditions: A cross-sectional study’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 12(42). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-015-0201-9>.

Ferreira, J.J. *et al.* (2021) ‘Wearable technology and consumer interaction: A systematic review and research agenda’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 118(January). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106710>.

Fornias, E. *et al.* (2019) ‘Dose-response relationship between very vigorous physical activity and cardiovascular health assessed by heart rate variability in adults : Cross-sectional results from the EPIMOV study’, *Plos One*, 4, pp. 1–14.

Franssen, W.M.A. *et al.* (2023) ‘The potential harms of sedentary behaviour on cardiometabolic health are mitigated in highly active adults : a compositional data analysis’, *Journal of Activity, Sedentary and Sleep Behaviors*, 7, pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44167-023-00015-7>.

Freedson, P.S. and Miller, K. (2000) ‘Objective monitoring of physical activity using motion sensors and heart rate.’, *Research quarterly for exercise and sport*, 71(2 Suppl), pp. S21-9.

Fuller, D. *et al.* (2020) ‘Reliability and Validity of Commercially Available Wearable Devices for Measuring Steps, Energy Expenditure, and Heart Rate: Systematic Review’, *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 8(9), pp. 1–23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/18694>.

Gaglio, B. *et al.* (2020) ‘Methodological standards for qualitative and mixed methods patient centered outcomes research’, *The BMJ*, 371. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m4435>.

Gastin, P.B. *et al.* (2018) ‘Validity of the ActiGraph GT3X+ and BodyMedia SenseWear Armband to estimate energy expenditure during physical activity and sport’, *Journal of science and medicine in sport*, 21(3), pp. 291–295. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2017.07.022>.

Gatti, Anthony A. *et al.* (2016) ‘GT3X+ accelerometer placement affects the reliability of step-counts measured during running and pedal-revolution counts measured during bicycling’, *Journal of Sports Sciences* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2015.1096018>.

Gebel, K. *et al.* (2015) ‘Effect of moderate to vigorous physical activity on all-cause mortality in middle-aged and older Australians’, *JAMA Internal Medicine*, 175(6), pp. 970–977. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2015.0541>.

Giurgiu, M. *et al.* (2023) ‘Assessment of 24-hour physical behaviour in adults via wearables: a systematic review of validation studies under laboratory conditions’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*. BioMed Central Ltd. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-023-01473-7>.

Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network (2020) *Global Burden of Disease Study 2019 (GBD 2019) Results*, Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation – IHME. Available at: <https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/>.

Glynn, L.G. *et al.* (2014) ‘Effectiveness of a smartphone application to promote physical activity in primary care: The SMART MOVE randomised controlled trial’, *British Journal of General Practice*, 64(624), pp. 384–391. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp14X680461>.

Gordon, B.A., Bruce, L. and Benson, A.C. (2016) ‘Physical activity intensity can be accurately monitored by smartphone global positioning system “app”’, *European Journal of Sport Science*, 16(5), pp. 624–631. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2015.1105299>.

GOV.UK (2020) *Prime Minister’s Statement on Coronavirus (COVID-19): 23 March 2020*, GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/pm-address-to-the-nation-on-coronavirus-23-march-2020%0Ahttps://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/pm-statement-on-coronavirus-18-march-2020%0Ahttps://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/pm-address-to-the-nation-on-coronavirus>.

GOV.UK (2022a) *Physical Activity*, GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.ethnicity-facts-figures.service.gov.uk/health/diet-and-exercise/physical-activity/latest#main-facts-and-figures>.

GOV.UK (2022b) *Physical activity: applying All Our Health*, GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/physical-activity-applying-all-our-health/physical-activity-applying-all-our-health>.

Granja, C., Janssen, W. and Johansen, M.A. (2018) ‘Factors determining the success and failure of ehealth interventions: Systematic review of the literature’, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 20(5), pp. 1–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/10235>.

Grimaldi-Puyana, M. *et al.* (2020) ‘Associations of objectively-assessed smartphone use with physical activity, sedentary behavior, mood, and sleep quality in young adults: A cross-

sectional study', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(10). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17103499>.

Guthold, R. *et al.* (2018) 'Worldwide trends in insufficient physical activity from 2001 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 358 population-based surveys with 1·9 million participants', *The Lancet Global Health*, 6(10), pp. e1077–e1086. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30357-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30357-7).

Hafner, M. *et al.* (2020) 'Estimating the global economic benefits of physically active populations over 30 years (2020-2050)', *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 54(24), pp. 1482–1487. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2020-102590>.

Hallal, P.C. *et al.* (2012) 'Global physical activity levels: Surveillance progress, pitfalls, and prospects', *The Lancet*, 380(9838), pp. 247–257. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)60646-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60646-1).

Hamburg, N.M. *et al.* (2007) 'Physical inactivity rapidly induces insulin resistance and microvascular dysfunction in healthy volunteers', *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*, 27(12), pp. 2650–2656. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.107.153288>.

Hamer, M. *et al.* (2020) 'Lifestyle risk factors, inflammatory mechanisms, and COVID-19 hospitalization: A community-based cohort study of 387,109 adults in UK', *Brain Behavior and Immunity*, 87(January), pp. 184–187.

Hanci, E. *et al.* (2020) 'Measuring commitment to self-tracking: development of the C2ST scale', *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 24(6), pp. 735–746. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00779-020-01453-9>.

Harari, G.M. *et al.* (2016) ‘Using Smartphones to Collect Behavioral Data in Psychological Science: Opportunities, Practical Considerations, and Challenges’, *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 11(6), pp. 838–854. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691616650285>.

Hartley, P. *et al.* (2018) ‘Using accelerometers to measure physical activity in older patients admitted to hospital’, *Current Gerontology and Geriatrics Research*, 2018. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/3280240>.

Hartman, S.J. *et al.* (2022) ‘Fitbit Use and Activity Levels From Intervention to 2 Years After: Secondary Analysis of a Randomized Controlled Trial’, *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 10(6), p. e37086. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/37086>.

Healy, G.N. *et al.* (2011) ‘Sedentary time and cardio-metabolic biomarkers in US adults: NHANES 200306’, *European Heart Journal*, 32(5), pp. 590–597. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehq451>.

Healy, P. *et al.* (2018) ‘Virtual outpatient clinic as an alternative to an actual clinic visit after surgical discharge: a randomised controlled trial’, *BMJ Quality & Safety*, pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2018-008171>.

Hekler, E.B. *et al.* (2015) ‘Validation of Physical Activity Tracking via Android Smartphones Compared to ActiGraph Accelerometer: Laboratory-Based and Free-Living Validation Studies’, *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 3(2), p. e36. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/mhealth.3505>.

Helmerhorst, H.J.F. *et al.* (2012) ‘A systematic review of reliability and objective criterion-related validity of physical activity questionnaires’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-9-103>.

Hendker, A. *et al.* (2020a) ‘The implication of wearables and the factors affecting their usage among recreationally active people’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(22), pp. 1–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17228532>.

Hermesen, S. *et al.* (2016) ‘Using feedback through digital technology to disrupt and change habitual behavior: A critical review of current literature’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 57, pp. 61–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.12.023>.

Hermesen, S. *et al.* (2017) ‘Determinants for sustained use of an activity tracker: Observational study’, *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 5(10). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/mhealth.7311>.

Hildebrand, M. *et al.* (2014) ‘Age group comparability of raw accelerometer output from wrist- and hip-worn monitors’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 46(9), pp. 1816–1824. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000000289>.

Hill, J.O. and Wyatt, H.R. (2005) ‘Role of physical activity in preventing and treating obesity’, *Journal of Applied Physiology*, 99(2), pp. 765–770. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappphysiol.00137.2005>.

Hoare, E. *et al.* (2017) ‘Exploring motivation and barriers to physical activity among active and inactive australian adults’, *Sports*, 5(3), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports5030047>.

Höchsmann, C. *et al.* (2018) ‘Validity of activity trackers, smartphones, and phone applications to measure steps in various walking conditions’, *Scand J Med Sci Sports*, 28(7), pp. 1818–1827. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13074>.

Höchsmann, C. *et al.* (2020) ‘Validity of smartphones and activity trackers to measure steps in a free-living setting over three consecutive days’, *Physiological Measurement*, 41(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6579/ab635f>.

Hodkinson, A. *et al.* (2019) ‘Accelerometer- and Pedometer-Based Physical Activity Interventions among Adults with Cardiometabolic Conditions: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis’, *JAMA Network Open*, 2(10). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.12895>.

Hoque, R. and Sorwar, G. (2017) ‘Understanding factors influencing the adoption of mHealth by the elderly: An extension of the UTAUT model’, *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 101(September 2015), pp. 75–84. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2017.02.002>.

Howe, C.C.F., Moir, H.J. and Easton, C. (2017) ‘Classification of Physical Activity Cut-Points and the Estimation of Energy Expenditure During Walking Using the GT3X+ Accelerometer in Overweight and Obese Adults’, *Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science*, 21(3), pp. 127–133. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1091367X.2016.1271801>.

Hulteen, R.M. *et al.* (2017) ‘Global participation in sport and leisure-time physical activities: A systematic review and meta-analysis’, *Preventive Medicine*, 95, pp. 14–25.

Hupin, D. *et al.* (2015) ‘Even a low-dose of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity reduces mortality by 22% in adults aged ≥ 60 years: A systematic review and meta-analysis’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 49(19), pp. 1262–1267. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2014-094306>.

Imai, Y. *et al.* (1993) ‘Characteristics of a community-based distribution of home blood pressure in Ohasama in northern Japan’, *Journal of Hypertension*, 11(12). Available at: https://journals.lww.com/jhypertension/Fulltext/1993/12000/Characteristics_of_a_community_based_distribution.17.aspx.

International Telecommunication Union (2023) *New global connectivity data shows growth, but divides persist*. Geneva.

Ioannidis, J. (2017) 'Next-generation systematic reviews: Prospective meta-analysis, individual-level data, networks and umbrella reviews', *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 51(20), pp. 1456–1458. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2017-097621>.

Jakicic, J.M. *et al.* (2019) 'Association between Bout Duration of Physical Activity and Health: Systematic Review', *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 51(6), pp. 1213–1219. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000001933>.

Jakicic, J.M. and Otto, A.D. (2005) 'Physical activity considerations for the treatment and prevention of obesity.', *The American journal of clinical nutrition*, 82(1 Suppl), pp. 226–229. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn.82.1.226s>.

Janssen, X. *et al.* (2020) 'Changes in Physical Activity, Sitting and Sleep across the COVID-19 National Lockdown Period in Scotland', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17, p. 9362.

Jarrett, H., Fitzgerald, L. and Routen, A.C. (2015) 'Inter-instrument reliability of the Actigraph GT3X+ Ambulatory Activity Monitor during free-living conditions in adults', *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 12(3), pp. 382–387. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2013-0070>.

Johnson, J.L., Adkins, D. & Chauvin, S., 2020. A review of the quality indicators of rigor in qualitative research. *The Qualitative Report*, 25(1), pp.23–42.

Johnson, M. *et al.* (2016) 'Validity of the Samsung Phone S Health application for assessing steps and energy expenditure during walking and running: Does phone placement matter?', *DIGITAL HEALTH*, 2(1–8), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207616652747>.

Jonassaint, C.R. *et al.* (2015) ‘Usability and Feasibility of an mHealth Intervention for Monitoring and Managing Pain Symptoms in Sickle Cell Disease: The Sickle Cell Disease Mobile Application to Record Symptoms via Technology (SMART)’, *Hemoglobin*, 39(3), pp. 162–168. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/03630269.2015.1025141>.

Jones, A.M. and Doust, J.H. (1996) ‘A 1% treadmill grade most accurately reflects the energetic cost of outdoor running’, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 14(4), pp. 321–327. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640419608727717>.

Jones, M.I. *et al.* (2012) ‘Patient self-monitoring of blood pressure and self-titration of medication in primary care: the TASMINH2 trial qualitative study’, *British Journal of General Practice*, 62, pp. e135–42. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp13X668168>.

Kang, M. *et al.* (2009) ‘Effect of pedometer-based physical activity interventions: A meta-analysis’, *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 80(3), pp. 648–655. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2009.10599604>.

Kannel, W.B. (1996) ‘Blood Pressure as a Cardiovascular Risk Factor: Prevention and Treatment’, *JAMA*, 275(20), pp. 1571–1576. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1996.03530440051036>.

Kapadia, V. *et al.* (2015) ‘Emerging ICT implementation issues in aged care’, *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 84(11), pp. 892–900. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2015.07.002>.

Keadle, S.K. *et al.* (2019) ‘A Framework to evaluate devices that assess physical behavior’, *Exercise and Sport Sciences Reviews*, 47(4), pp. 206–214. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/JES.0000000000000206>.

Kingsnorth, Andrew P. *et al.* (2021) ‘Changes in Device-Measured Physical Activity Patterns in U.K. Adults Related to the First COVID-19 Lockdown’, *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 4(3), pp. 247–256. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jmpb.2021-0005>.

Korstjens, I. & Moser, A., 2018. Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 4: Trustworthiness and publishing. *European Journal of General Practice*, 24(1), pp.120–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2017.1375092>

Kyu, H.H. *et al.* (2016) ‘Physical activity and risk of breast cancer, colon cancer, diabetes, ischemic heart disease, and ischemic stroke events: Systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013’, *BMJ (Online)*, 354, pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i3857>.

Lavie, C.J., O’Keefe, J.H. and Sallis, R.E. (2015) ‘Exercise and the heart-the harm of too little and too much’, *Current Sports Medicine Reports*, 14(2), pp. 104–109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/JSR.0000000000000134>.

Lee, I.M., Shiroma, E.J., Lobelo, F., Puska, P., Blair, S.N., Katzmarzyk, P.T., *et al.* (2012) ‘Effect of physical inactivity on major non-communicable diseases worldwide: An analysis of burden of disease and life expectancy’, *The Lancet*, 380(9838), pp. 219–229. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)61031-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61031-9).

Lee, J.A. *et al.* (2015) ‘Concurrent validation of the Actigraph gt3x+, Polar Active accelerometer, Omron HJ-720 and Yamax Digiwalker SW-701 pedometer step counts in lab-based and free-living settings’, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 33(10), pp. 991–1000. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2014.981848>.

Lenus Health (2020). Available at: <https://lenushealth.com/> (Accessed: 8 March 2020).

Leung, W. *et al.* (2021) 'Factors associated with validity of consumer-oriented wearable physical activity trackers: a meta-analysis', *Journal of Medical Engineering & Technology*, pp. 1–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03091902.2021.1893395>.

Leung, W. *et al.* (2022) 'A meta-analysis of Fitbit devices: same company, different models, different validity evidence', *Journal of Medical Engineering & Technology*, 46(2), pp. 102–115. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03091902.2021.2006350>.

Liao, Y. *et al.* (2019) 'The Future of Wearable Technologies and Remote Monitoring in Health Care', *American Society of Clinical Oncology Educational Book*, (39), pp. 115–121. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1200/edbk_238919.

Lin, L.I. (1989) 'A Concordance Correlation Coefficient to Evaluate Reproducibility', *Biometrics*, 45(1), pp. 255–268. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2532051>.

Liu, F., Wanigatunga, A.A. and Schrack, J.A. (2021) 'Assessment of Physical Activity in Adults Using Wrist Accelerometers', *Epidemiologic Reviews*, 43(1), pp. 65–93. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxab004>.

Lupton, D. (2013) 'Quantifying the body: Monitoring and measuring health in the age of mHealth technologies', *Critical Public Health*, 23(4), pp. 393–403. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09581596.2013.794931>.

Maher, C. *et al.* (2017) 'Users' experiences of wearable activity trackers: A cross-sectional study', *BMC Public Health*, 17(880). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-017-4888-1>.

Majeed, A., Maile, E.J. and Bindman, A.B. (2020) 'The primary care response to COVID-19 in England's National Health Service', *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 113(6), pp. 208–210. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076820931452>.

Major, Matthew J. and Alford, M. (2016) ‘Validity of the iPhone M7 motion co-processor as a pedometer for able-bodied ambulation’, *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 34(23), pp. 2160–2164. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2016.1189086>.

Majumder, S., Mondal, T. and Deen, M.J. (2017) ‘Wearable sensors for remote health monitoring’, *Sensors (Switzerland)*. MDPI AG. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s17010130>.

Mammen, G. and Faulkner, G. (2013) ‘Physical activity and the prevention of depression: A systematic review of prospective studies’, *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 45(5), pp. 649–657. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2013.08.001>.

Le Masurier, G.C., Lee, S.M. and Tudor-Locke, C. (2004) ‘Motion Sensor Accuracy under Controlled and Free-Living Conditions’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 36(5), pp. 905–910. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/01.MSS.0000126777.50188.73>.

McCarthy, H., Potts, Henry W W and Fisher, A. (2021) ‘Physical activity behavior before, during, and after COVID-19 restrictions: Longitudinal smartphone-tracking study of adults in the United Kingdom’, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 23(2), pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/23701>.

McCartney, M. (2017) ‘Margaret McCartney: Innovation without sufficient evidence is a disservice to all’, *BMJ (Online)*, 358, pp. 1–2. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j3980>.

McCartney, M. (2018) ‘Margaret McCartney: AI in medicine must be rigorously tested’, *BMJ (Online)*, 361(April). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k1752>.

McGinnis, J.M., Fineberg, H. V. and Dzau, V.J. (2021) ‘Advancing the Learning Health System’, *New England Journal of Medicine*, 385(1), pp. 1–5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp2103872>.

McMinn, D. *et al.* (2013) ‘Measuring Activity Energy Expenditure: Accuracy of the GT3X+ and Actiheart Monitors’, *International Journal of Exercise Science*, 6(3), pp. 217–229.

Middelweerd, A. *et al.* (2015) ‘What features do Dutch university students prefer in a smartphone application for promotion of physical activity? A qualitative approach’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 12(1), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-015-0189-1>.

Migueles, J.H. *et al.* (2017) ‘Accelerometer Data Collection and Processing Criteria to Assess Physical Activity and Other Outcomes: A Systematic Review and Practical Considerations’, *Sports Medicine*, 47(9), pp. 1821–1845. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-017-0716-0>.

Migueles, J.H. *et al.* (2019) ‘Comparability of published cut-points for the assessment of physical activity: Implications for data harmonization’, *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine and Science in Sports*, 29(4), pp. 566–574. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13356>.

Montoye, A.H.K., Vusich, J., *et al.* (2018) ‘Heart Rate Alters, But Does Not Improve, Calorie Predictions in Fitbit Activity Monitors’, *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 1(1), pp. 9–17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jmpb.2018-0003>.

Montoye, A.H.K., Moore, R.W., *et al.* (2018) ‘Reporting accelerometer methods in physical activity intervention studies: A systematic review and recommendations for authors’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 52(23), pp. 1507–1516. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2015-095947>.

Morales, J. and Akopian, D. (2017) ‘Physical activity recognition by smartphones, a survey’, *Biocybernetics and Biomedical Engineering*, 37(3), pp. 388–400. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbe.2017.04.004>.

Morris, J.N. and Hardman, A.E. (1997) 'Walking to health', *Sports Medicine*, 23(5), pp. 306–332. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-199723050-00004>.

Norton, K., Norton, L. and Sadgrove, D. (2010) 'Position statement on physical activity and exercise intensity terminology', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 13(5), pp. 496–502. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2009.09.008>.

Nuss, K. *et al.* (2021) 'Effects of Motivational Interviewing and Wearable Fitness Trackers on Motivation and Physical Activity: A Systematic Review', *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 35(2), pp. 226–235. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0890117120939030>.

O'Brien, W.J. *et al.* (2017) 'Exploring the challenges in obtaining physical activity data from women using hip-worn accelerometers', *European Journal of Sport Science*, 17(7), pp. 922–930. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461391.2017.1323952>.

O'Connor, R.C. *et al.* (2021) 'Mental health and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic: Longitudinal analyses of adults in the UK COVID-19 Mental Health & Wellbeing study', *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 218(6), pp. 326–333. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.2020.212>.

O'Donovan, G. *et al.* (2013) 'Objectively measured physical activity, cardiorespiratory fitness and cardiometabolic risk factors in the Health Survey for England', *Preventive Medicine*, 57(3), pp. 201–205. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2013.05.022>.

Ohkubo, T. *et al.* (2004) 'How many times should blood pressure be measured at home for better prediction of stroke risk? Ten-year follow-up results from the Ohasama study', *Journal of Hypertension*, 22(6). Available at: https://journals.lww.com/jhypertension/Fulltext/2004/06000/How_many_times_should_blood_pressure_be_measured.9.aspx.

Ozemek, C. *et al.* (2014) ‘Intermonitor reliability of the GT3X+ accelerometer at hip, wrist and ankle sites during activities of daily living’, *Physiological Measurement*, 35(2), pp. 129–138. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0967-3334/35/2/129>.

Padwal, R.S. *et al.* (2007) ‘The 2007 Canadian Hypertension Education Program recommendations for the management of hypertension: Part 1 - Blood pressure measurement, diagnosis and assessment of risk’, *Canadian Journal of Cardiology*, 23(7), pp. 529–538. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0828-282X\(07\)70797-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0828-282X(07)70797-3).

Pandey, A. *et al.* (2015) ‘Dose-Response Relationship Between Physical Activity and Risk of Heart Failure: A Meta-Analysis’, *Circulation*, 132(19), pp. 1786–1794. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.115.015853>.

Pandey, A. *et al.* (2016) ‘Continuous dose-response association between sedentary time and risk for cardiovascular disease a meta-analysis’, *JAMA Cardiology*, 1(5), pp. 575–583. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2016.1567>.

Pépin, J.L. *et al.* (2020) ‘Wearable activity trackers for monitoring adherence to home confinement during the COVID-19 pandemic worldwide: Data aggregation and analysis’, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(6), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/19787>.

Pettinico, G. and Milne, G.R. (2017) ‘Living by the numbers: understanding the “quantification effect”’, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 34(4), pp. 281–291. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-06-2016-1839>.

Pfaeffli Dale, L. *et al.* (2015) ‘Acceptability of a mobile health exercise-based cardiac rehabilitation intervention: A randomized trial’, *Journal of Cardiopulmonary Rehabilitation and Prevention*, 35(5), pp. 312–319. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1097/HCR.0000000000000125>.

Pierce, M. *et al.* (2020) ‘Mental health before and during the COVID-19 pandemic: a longitudinal probability sample survey of the UK population’, *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(10), pp. 883–892. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30308-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30308-4).

Polit, D.F. & Beck, C.T., 2010. Generalization in quantitative and qualitative research: Myths and strategies. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 47(11), pp.1451–1458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2010.06.004>

Pontin, F. *et al.* (2021) ‘Socio-demographic determinants of physical activity and app usage from smartphone data’, *Social Science and Medicine*, 284(March), p. 114235. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114235>.

Post, M.W. (2016) ‘What to Do With “Moderate” Reliability and Validity Coefficients?’, *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 97(7), pp. 1051–1052. Available at: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2016.04.001>.

Poushter, J. (2016) ‘Smartphone Ownership and Internet Usage Continues to Climb in Emerging Economies’, *Pew Research Center*, pp. 1–45. Available at: <http://www.pewglobal.org/2016/02/22/smartphone-ownership-and-internet-usage-continues-to-climb-in-emerging-economies/>.

Prince, S.A. *et al.* (2008) ‘A comparison of direct versus self-report measures for assessing physical activity in adults: A systematic review’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 5(56). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-5-56>.

Pulsford, R.M. *et al.* (2023) ‘The impact of selected methodological factors on data collection outcomes in observational studies of device-measured physical behaviour in adults: A systematic review’, *The international journal of behavioral nutrition and physical activity*, 20(1), p. 26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-022-01388-9>.

Rebar, A.L. *et al.* (2015) ‘A meta-meta-analysis of the effect of physical activity on depression and anxiety in non-clinical adult populations’, *Health Psychology Review*, 9(3), pp. 366–378. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17437199.2015.1022901>.

Reid, R.E.R. *et al.* (2017) ‘Validity and reliability of Fitbit activity monitors compared to ActiGraph GT3X+ with female adults in a free-living environment’, *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 20(6), pp. 578–582. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2016.10.015>.

Reiner, M. *et al.* (2013) ‘Long-term health benefits of physical activity--a systematic review of longitudinal studies.’, *BMC public health*, 13(813). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-813>.

Rey Lopez, J.P. *et al.* (2019) ‘Associations of vigorous physical activity with all-cause, cardiovascular and cancer mortality among 64 913 adults’, *BMJ Open Sport and Exercise Medicine*, 5(1), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjsem-2019-000596>.

Rezaei, N. and Grandner, M.A. (2021) ‘Changes in sleep duration, timing, and variability during the COVID-19 pandemic: Large-scale Fitbit data from 6 major US cities’, *Sleep Health*, 7(3), pp. 303–313. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleh.2021.02.008>.

Richardson, S. *et al.* (2022) ‘A framework for digital health equity’, *npj Digital Medicine*, 5(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00663-0>.

Rosenberger, M.E. *et al.* (2019) ‘The 24-Hour Activity Cycle: A New Paradigm for Physical Activity’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 51(3), pp. 454–464. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000001811>.

Ryan, R.M. and Deci, E.L. (2000) ‘Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being.’, *American psychologist*, 55(1), pp. 68–71.

Ryba, T. V. *et al.* (2022) ‘Developing mixed methods research in sport and exercise psychology: potential contributions of a critical realist perspective’, *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 20(1), pp. 147–167. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1612197X.2020.1827002>.

Sallis, J.F. and Saelens, B.E. (2000) ‘Assessment of physical activity by self-report: Status, limitations, and future directions’, *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 71, pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2000.11082780>.

Sallis, R. *et al.* (2021) ‘Physical inactivity is associated with a higher risk for severe COVID-19 outcomes: A study in 48 440 adult patients’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 55(19), pp. 1099–1105. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2021-104080>.

Salman, D., Beaney, T., E Robb, C., De Jager Loots, Celeste A., *et al.* (2021) ‘Impact of social restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic on the physical activity levels of adults aged 50-92 years: A baseline survey of the CHARIOT COVID-19 Rapid Response prospective cohort study’, *BMJ Open*, 11(8), pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-050680>.

Samitz, G., Egger, M. and Zwahlen, M. (2011) ‘Domains of physical activity and all-cause mortality: Systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis of cohort studies’, *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 40(5), pp. 1382–1400. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyr112>.

Santos-Lozano, A. *et al.* (2013) ‘Actigraph GT3X: Validation and determination of physical activity intensity cut points’, *International Journal of Sports Medicine*, 34(11), pp. 975–982. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0033-1337945>.

Sasaki, J.E., John, D. and Freedson, P.S. (2011) ‘Validation and comparison of ActiGraph activity monitors’, *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 14(5), pp. 411–416. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2011.04.003>.

Saunders, T.J. *et al.* (2020) ‘Sedentary behaviour and health in adults: an overview of systematic reviews’, *Applied physiology, nutrition, and metabolism*, 45, pp. S197–S217. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1139/apnm-2020-0034>.

Scarborough, P. *et al.* (2011) ‘The economic burden of ill health due to diet, physical inactivity, smoking, alcohol and obesity in the UK: An update to 2006-07 NHS costs’, *Journal of Public Health*, 33(4), pp. 527–535. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdr033>.

Schuch, F.B. *et al.* (2018) ‘Physical activity and incident depression: A meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies’, *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 175(7), pp. 631–648. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2018.17111194>.

Schulz, M. and Hennis-Plasschaert, J.A. (2016) ‘REGULATIONS’, *Official Journal of the European Union*, pp. 119/1-119/88. Available at: <https://gdpr-info.eu/> (Accessed: 8 March 2020).

Schuna, J.M., Johnson, W.D. and Tudor-Locke, C. (2013) ‘Adult self-reported and objectively monitored physical activity and sedentary behavior: NHANES 2005-2006’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 10, pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-10-126>.

Scottish Government (2021) *The Scottish Health Survey A National Statistics Publication for Scotland*.

Sellers, C. *et al.* (2016) ‘Validity and reliability of the activPAL3 for measuring posture and stepping in adults and young people’, *Gait and Posture*, 43, pp. 42–47. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2015.10.020>.

Shah, S.S. *et al.* (2021) ‘Mobile app-based remote patient monitoring in acute medical conditions: Prospective feasibility study exploring digital health solutions on clinical workload during the covid crisis’, *JMIR Formative Research*, 5(1), pp. 1–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/23190>.

Shin, G. *et al.* (2019) ‘Wearable activity trackers, accuracy, adoption, acceptance and health impact: A systematic literature review’, *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 93, p. 103153. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2019.103153>.

Shiroma, E.J. *et al.* (2013) ‘Patterns of Accelerometer-Assessed Sedentary Behavior in Older Women’, *JAMA*, 310(23), pp. 2562–3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.278896.Patterns>.

Sieck, C.J. *et al.* (2021) ‘Digital inclusion as a social determinant of health’, *npj Digital Medicine*, 4(1), pp. 5–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00413-8>.

Silva, A.G. *et al.* (2020) ‘Effectiveness of mobile applications running on smartphones to promote physical activity: A systematic review with meta-analysis’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(7), pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17072251>.

Singh, B. *et al.* (2023) ‘Effectiveness of physical activity interventions for improving depression, anxiety and distress: an overview of systematic reviews’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 0, pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2022-106195>.

Skotte, J. *et al.* (2014) ‘Detection of physical activity types using triaxial accelerometers’, *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 11(1), pp. 76–84. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2011-0347>.

Spence, J.C. *et al.* (2021) ‘Determinants of physical activity among adults in the United Kingdom during the COVID-19 pandemic: The DUK-COVID study’, *British Journal of Health Psychology*, 26(2), pp. 588–605. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjhp.12497>.

Staff, F. (2020) *The Impact Of Coronavirus On Global Activity*, *Fitbit blog*. Available at: <https://blog.fitbit.com/covid-19-global-activity/>.

Stamatakis, E. *et al.* (2020) ‘Emerging collaborative research platforms for the next generation of physical activity, sleep and exercise medicine guidelines: The Prospective Physical Activity, Sitting, and Sleep consortium (ProPASS)’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 54(8), pp. 435–437. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2019-100786>.

Stamatakis, E. *et al.* (2021) ‘Untapping the Health Enhancing Potential of Vigorous Intermittent Lifestyle Physical Activity (VILPA): Rationale, Scoping Review, and a 4-Pillar Research Framework’, *Sports Medicine*, 51(1), pp. 1–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-020-01368-8>.

Stamatakis, E. *et al.* (2022) ‘Association of wearable device-measured vigorous intermittent lifestyle physical activity with mortality’, *Nature Medicine*, 28(12), pp. 2521–2529. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-02100-x>.

Statista (2023a) *Fitbit - statistics & facts*, *Statista*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/topics/2595/fitbit/#topicOverview>.

Statista (2023b) *Fitness trackers - statistics & facts*, *Statista*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/topics/4393/fitness-and-activity-tracker/>.

Statistics, O. for N. (2020) *Coronavirus and how people spent their time under lockdown*, Office for National Statistics. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/nationalaccounts/satelliteaccounts/bulletins/coronavirusandhowpeoplespenttheirtimeunderrestrictions/28marchto26april2020#the-gap-in-unpaid-work-between-men-and-women>.

Steele Gray, C.A. *et al.* (2016) ‘The electronic Patient Reported Outcome (ePRO) Tool: Testing usability and feasibility of a mobile app for patients with complex chronic disease and disability in primary care settings’, *International Journal of Integrated Care*, 16(6), p. 211. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5334/ijic.2759>.

Stergiou, G.S. *et al.* (2007) ‘Home Blood Pressure Is as Reliable as Ambulatory Blood Pressure in Predicting Target-Organ Damage in Hypertension’, *American Journal of Hypertension*, 20(6), pp. 616–621. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjhyper.2006.12.013>.

Stevens, M.L. *et al.* (2020) ‘Thigh-worn accelerometry for measuring movement and posture across the 24-hour cycle: A scoping review and expert statement’, *BMJ Open Sport and Exercise Medicine*, 6(1), pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjsem-2020-000874>.

Stiglbauer, B., Weber, S. and Batinic, B. (2019) ‘Does your health really benefit from using a self-tracking device? Evidence from a longitudinal randomized control trial’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 94(August 2018), pp. 131–139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.01.018>.

Stockwell, S. *et al.* (2021) ‘Changes in physical activity and sedentary behaviours from before to during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown: A systematic review’, *BMJ Open Sport and Exercise Medicine*, 7(1), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjsem-2020-000960>.

Strain, T. *et al.* (2020) ‘Wearable-device-measured physical activity and future health risk’, *Nature Medicine*, 26(9), pp. 1385–1391. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-1012-3>.

Strain, T., Wijndaele, K., *et al.* (2022a) ‘Considerations for the Use of Consumer-Grade Wearables and Smartphones in Population Surveillance of Physical Activity’, *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 5(1), pp. 8–14.

Strain, T. *et al.* (2022b) ‘Population level physical activity before and during the first national COVID-19 lockdown: A nationally representative repeat cross-sectional study of 5 years of Active Lives data in England’, *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe*, 12, p. 100265. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanep.2021.100265>.

Strain, T., Wijndaele, K. and Brage, S. (2019) ‘Physical activity surveillance through smartphone apps and wearable trackers: Examining the UK potential for nationally representative sampling’, *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 7(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2196/11898>.

Strath, S. J., Kaminsky, L. A., Ainsworth, B. E., Ekelund, U., Freedson, P. S., Gary, R. A., ... & Swartz, A. M. (2013). Guide to the assessment of physical activity: Clinical and research applications. *Circulation*, 128(20), 2259–2279. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.0000435708.67487.da>

Stunkard, A. (1960) ‘A Method of Studying Physical Activity in Man’, *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 8, pp. 595–601.

Swan, M. (2013) ‘The quantified self: Fundamental disruption in big data science and biological discovery’, *Big Data*, 1(2), pp. 85–99. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1089/big.2012.0002>.

Tanaka, H., Monahan, K.D. and Seals, D.R. (2001) ‘Age-predicted maximal heart rate revisited’, *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 37(1), pp. 153–156. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097\(00\)01054-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097(00)01054-8).

Taylor, K. and Silver, L. (2019) *Smartphone Ownership Is Growing Rapidly Around the World, but Not Always Equally*. Available at: <http://www.pewglobal.org/2019/02/05/smartphone-ownership-is-growing-rapidly-around-the-world-but-not-always-equally/>.

Thompson, W.R. (2015) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2016’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 19(6), pp. 9–18.

Thompson, W.R. (2016) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2017’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 20(6), pp. 8–17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/FIT.0000000000000834>.

Thompson, W.R. (2017) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2018’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 21(6), pp. 10–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/FIT.0000000000000834>.

Thompson, W.R. (2018) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2019’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 22(6), pp. 10–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/FIT.0000000000000834>.

Thompson, W.R. (2019) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2020’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 23(6), pp. 10–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/FIT.0000000000000834>.

Thompson, W.R. (2021) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2021’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 25(1), pp. 10–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/FIT.0000000000000834>.

Thompson, W.R. (2022) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2022’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 26(1), pp. 11–20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/FIT.0000000000000834>.

Thompson, W.R. (2023) ‘Worldwide Survey of Fitness Trends for 2023’, *ACSM’s Health and Fitness Journal*, 27(1), pp. 9–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/FIT.0000000000000834>.

Thomson, N.K. *et al.* (2019) ‘The Accuracy Of A Smartphone To Measure Laboratory And Free-living Physical Activity’, *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 51(6S), pp. 372–373.

Thomson, N.K. *et al.* (2021) ‘Validity of the iPhone M7 Motion Coprocessor to Estimate Physical Activity during Structured and Free-Living Activities in Healthy Adults’, *Journal for the Measurement of Physical Behaviour*, 4(3), pp. 1–9.

Tomer, A. *et al.* (2020) *Digital Prosperity: HOW BROADBAND CAN DELIVER HEALTH AND EQUITY TO ALL COMMUNITIES*, (*Metropolitan Infrastructure Initiative: Brookings Institution*).

Tovin, M.M. and Wormley, M.E. (2023) ‘Systematic Development of Standards for Mixed Methods Reporting in Rehabilitation Health Sciences Research’, *Physical Therapy*, 103(11). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ptj/pzad084>.

Tremblay, M.S. *et al.* (2010) ‘Physiological and health implications of a sedentary lifestyle’, *Applied Physiology, Nutrition and Metabolism*, 35, pp. 725–740. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1139/H10-079>.

Tremblay, M.S. *et al.* (2017) ‘Sedentary Behavior Research Network (SBRN) - Terminology Consensus Project process and outcome’, *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 14(1), pp. 1–17. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-017-0525-8>.

Troiano, R.P. *et al.* (1996) ‘The relationship between body weight and mortality: A quantitative analysis of combined information from existing studies’, *International Journal of Obesity and Related Metabolic Disorders*, 20(1), pp. 63–75.

Troiano, R.P. *et al.* (2008) ‘Physical activity in the United States measured by accelerometer’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 40(1), pp. 181–188. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0b013e31815a51b3>.

Troiano, R.P. *et al.* (2014) ‘Evolution of accelerometer methods for physical activity research’, *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 48(13), pp. 1019–1023. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2014-093546>.

Tudor-Locke, C., Barreira, T. V. and Schuna, J.M. (2015) ‘Comparison of step outputs for waist and wrist accelerometer attachment sites’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 47(4), pp. 839–842. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000000476>.

Tudor-Locke, C. and Bassett, D.R. (2004) ‘How Many Steps/Day Are Enough?’, *Sports Medicine*, 34(1), pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-200434010-00001>.

Turner, K. *et al.* (2021) ‘Sharing patient-generated data with healthcare providers: Findings from a 2019 national survey’, *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 28(2), pp. 371–376. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa272>.

UK Chief Medical Officer’s Guidelines (2011) *Start Active, Stay Active: A report on physical activity from the four home countries*’ Chief Medical Officers, Department of Health, Physical Activity, Health Improvement and Protection. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0021364011030027>.

Velardo, C. *et al.* (2017) ‘Digital health system for personalised COPD long-term management’, *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 17(1), pp. 1–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1086/BBLv216n1p23>.

Vinnikova, A. *et al.* (2020) ‘The Use of Smartphone Fitness Applications: The Role of Self-Efficacy and Self-Regulation’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(7639).

Walkden, J.A., McCullagh, P.J. and Kernohan, W.G. (2019) ‘Patient and carer survey of remote vital sign telemonitoring for self-management of long-term conditions’, *BMJ Health and Care Informatics*, 26(1), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjhci-2019-100079>.

Wang, Z. *et al.* (2022) ‘Sedentary behavior and the risk of stroke: A systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis’, *Nutrition, Metabolism and Cardiovascular Diseases*, 32(12), pp. 2705–2713. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.numecd.2022.08.024>.

Warburton, D.E.R., Nicol, C.W. and Bredin, S.S.D. (2006) ‘Health benefits of physical activity: the evidence.’, *Canadian Medical Association Journal*, 174(6), pp. 801–809. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1503/cmaj.051351>.

Weir, J.B. de V (1949) ‘NEW METHODS FOR CALCULATING METABOLIC RATE WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PROTEIN METABOLISM’, *Journal of Physiology*, 109(5), pp. 1–9.

WHO (2020) ‘Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19) Situation Report’, *World Health Organization*, (12 April 2020), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.2633>.

Wijndaele, K. *et al.* (2015) ‘Utilization and Harmonization of Adult Accelerometry Data: Review and Expert Consensus’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 47(10), pp. 2129–2139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000000661>.

Wild, S. *et al.* (2015) ‘Qualitative study of telemonitoring of blood glucose and blood pressure in type 2 diabetes’, *BMJ Open*, 5(12). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2015-008896>.

World Health Organization (2010) *Global Recommendations on Physical Activity for Health*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241599979>.

World Health Organization (2011) *mHealth: New horizons for health through mobile technologies, Global Observatory for eHealth Series*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4258/hir.2012.18.3.231>.

World Health Organization (2018) *Global action plan on physical activity 2018–2030: more active people for a healthier world, World Health Organization 2018*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpolmod.2006.06.007>.

World Health Organization (2020a) *Global Health Estimates 2020: Deaths by Cause, Age, Sex, by Country and by Region, 2000-2019.*, Geneva, World Health Organization. Available at: <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/mortality-and-global-health-estimates/ghe-leading-causes-of-death>.

World Health Organization (2020b) *WHO Guidelines on physical activity, sedentary behaviour, World Health Organization*. Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/325147/WHO-NMH-PND-2019.4-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y%0Ahttp://www.who.int/iris/handle/10665/311664%0Ahttps://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/325147>.

World Health Organization (2021) *Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020-2025*, World Health Organization. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-020-1789-7>.

World Health Organization (2022) *Global status report on physical activity 2022*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/teams/health-promotion/physical-activity/global-status-report-on-physical-activity-2022>.

World Medical Association (2013) 'Declaration of Helsinki, Ethical Principles for Scientific Requirements and Research Protocols', *World Medical Association*, (June 1964), pp. 29–32. Available at: <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/>.

Xie, Z., Jo, A. and Hong, Y.R. (2020) 'Electronic wearable device and physical activity among US adults: An analysis of 2019 HINTS data', *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 144(October), p. 104297. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2020.104297>.

Yanagibori, R. *et al.* (1998) 'Effect of 20 days' bed rest on the reverse cholesterol transport system in healthy young subjects', *Journal of Internal Medicine*, 243(4), pp. 307–312. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2796.1998.00303.x>.

Yen, H.Y., Jin, G. and Chiu, H.L. (2023) 'Smartphone app-based interventions targeting physical activity for weight management: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials', *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 137, p. 104384. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2022.104384>.

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Interview schedule for study 2

Introduction:

Thank you for agreeing to take part. Do you give consent for this interview being recorded?

This discussion will remain confidential and there will be no identifying information published.

General Questions

- 1. How did you get on with this over the past week?**
- 2. Do you or have you used any physical activity wearables before such as fitbit?**
 - a) Which wearable was it?
 - b) How long did you use it?
 - c) Did/do you find it useful?
- 3. Have you done any other kind of physical activity or health monitoring before?**
 - a) Was that through your GP/Hospital/Clinic?
 - b) What measurements/metrics were you or your health care professional interested in?

Wear-Time

- 4. Were you able to secure the phone and accelerometer to your waist every day?**
 - a) For how long throughout each day?
 - b) What were the reasons if not?
 - c) Did you find it comfortable or uncomfortable wearing them around the waist all day?
- 5. Where did you tend to keep your personal phone on you?**
 - a) Was it kept in the same place each day or did it depend on what you were doing that day?
- 6. How would you feel if you were asked to do this kind of physical activity monitoring by your GP for an extended period of time?**
 - a) Can you explain why you think that?

Specific-to-data

7. Could you explain these periods of non-wear time?

- a) Were you PA but not wearing the phone?
- b) Were you wearing the phone but sedentary?

Additional Comments from Participants

8. Do you have any other comments you would like to make?

I would like to thank you for participating in this interview.

Appendix 2 – Interview schedule for ‘mock patients’ within study 3

Introduction:

Thank you for agreeing to take part. I [Interviewer] will be the one to conduct this interview today and with your permission, this interview will be recorded. I will be asking your views and opinions on the Lenus Health Platform as someone who used it over the past two weeks. This discussion will remain confidential and there will be no identifying information published.

General Questions

9. How did you get on with this over the past couple of weeks?

10. Were you able to keep your phone with you every day?

- a) For how long throughout each day?
- b) Were there specific reasons why you were not able to keep your phone with you?

11. Were there any barriers to this?

- a) Could you please explain more as to why this was a barrier?

Usability of the App

12. Did you find the platform user-friendly?

- a) What about the platform did you think was user-friendly/ not user-friendly?

13. What the process of uploading your data like?

- a) Was it simple/difficult to do?

14. What did you think were the positives of the platform?

- a) Why did you think that this was a good thing about the platform?

15. What did you think were the negatives of the platform?

- a) Why did you think this was a bad thing about the platform?

16. What did you think worked well?

- a) Why did this work well for you?

17. Was there anything that you thought was confusing or misleading?

- a) Why was this confusing/misleading?

- b) How do you think this could be made clearer?

Participants Expectations

18. Did you find it useful seeing your own data?

- a) Why did you find this useful/ not useful?
- b) How did you feel about monitoring your own data?
(encouraging/motivational/upsetting)

19. Are you comfortable with your data being collected in this way?

- a) Why do you think that?

20. Do you think this is something that you would use long term?

- a) Can you explain why you think/ do not think you would?

21. Part of the reason for this is to reduce face-to-face meetings with health professionals. Do you think this is a suitable replacement for that?

- a) Can you please explain you think that? (yes or no)

22. Do you trust the technology?

- a) Why do you (not) trust the technology?

Participant Recommendations

23. What would you want to see in a platform like this?

- a) Why do you think this would be useful?

24. Was there anything missing that would have been helpful?

- a) Why would this be helpful?

Additional Comments from Participants

25. Do you have any other comments you would like to make?

I would like to thank you for participating in this interview.

Appendix 3 – Interview schedule for HCPs within study 3

Introduction:

Thank you for agreeing to take part. I [Interviewer] will be the one to conduct this interview today and with your permission, this interview will be recorded. I will be asking your views and opinions on the Lenus Health Platform from a clinician's perspective. This discussion will remain confidential and there will be no identifying information published.

General Questions

26. What are your initial thoughts on the platform as it was presented to you?

- a) What was it about this feature [or other] that stood out for you?
- b) Do you have any questions regarding the platform?

Usability of the App

27. Did you find the platform user-friendly?

- b) What about the platform did you think was user-friendly/ not user-friendly?

28. Was the platform easy/difficult to view patient data?

- a) How might this be improved?

29. What did you think were the positives of the platform?

- b) Why did you think that this was a good thing about the platform?

30. What did you think were the negatives of the platform?

- b) Why did you think this was a bad thing about the platform?

31. What did you think worked well?

- b) Why did this work well for you?

32. Was there anything that you thought was confusing or misleading?

- c) Why was this confusing/misleading?
- d) How do you think this could be made clearer?

Clinician Expectations

- 33. Did you find it useful seeing patients' data?**
c) Why did you find this useful/ not useful?
- 34. Do you think that this could help improve the monitoring of pre-op patients?**
a) Can you please clarify why it would/ would not help?
- 35. Do you think this is something that you would use long term to monitor patients' conditions?**
b) Can you explain why you think/ do not think you would?
- 36. Part of the reason for this is to reduce face-to-face meetings with patients. Do you think this is a suitable replacement for that?**
b) Can you please explain you think that? (yes or no)
- 37. Do you think this platform could be implemented within the NHS?**
a) Why do you think this?
b) What do you think the barriers would be to this?
c) What do you think the advantages would be?
- 38. Do you trust the technology?**
b) Why do you (not) trust the technology?
- 39. What kind of impact do you think a platform like this could have on the NHS?**
a) Would this impact be a perceived as a benefit or detriment to the NHS?

Participant Recommendations

- 40. What would you want to see in a platform like this from a clinician's point of view?**
b) Why do you think this would be useful?
- 41. Was there anything missing that would have been helpful?**
b) Why would this be helpful?

Additional Comments from Clinicians

- 42. Do you have any other comments you would like to make?**

I would like to thank you for participating in this interview.

Appendix 4 – Interview schedule for study 4

Introduction:

Thank you for agreeing to take part. I [Interviewer] will be the one to conduct this interview today and with your permission, this interview will be recorded. Could you just confirm you consent to this interview being recorded? I will be asking about details pertaining to your physical activity, this includes all forms of exercise – walking, following routines online, cycling etc. This discussion will remain confidential and there will be no identifying information published. If at any point you miss a question due to signal or sound quality, please don't hesitate to ask me to repeat it. I'll start with some general questions, then questions regarding before, during and after lockdown.

General Questions

- 1. In general, how do you feel about tracking and/or monitoring your physical activity?**
 - a. Can you explain why you feel that way?
- 2. What do you use to track/monitor your physical activity?**
 - a. How long have used it?
 - b. Have you used anything else?

Prior to lockdown

- 3. Before lockdown and social-distancing, what type of physical activity did you take part in?**
 - a. How often did you take part?
 - b. Anything else?
- 4. Before lockdown, was physical activity something you were concerned about?**
 - a. Why was that?

During lockdown

- 5. Do you feel your physical activity behaviours changed once lockdown and social distancing were implemented?**

- a. Can you explain why you feel that way?
- 6. During lockdown, what type of physical activity did you take part in?**
- a. How often?
 - b. Anything else?
- 7. During lockdown, were you more or less aware of your physical activity?**
- a. Why was that?
- 8. Did lockdown give you the opportunity to start any new physical activity?**
- a. What type?
 - b. Why was that?
- 9. Did lockdown prevent you from doing any physical activity you normally would?**
- a. What type?
 - b. Why was that?
 - c. How did that make you feel?
- 10. Did your interaction with physical activity related technology (such as Fitbit) change due to lockdown?**
- a. Why do you think that was?
 - b. What about checking your PA data through the app?

After Lockdown

- 11. Since lockdown has been lifted, do you think you do more or less physical activity?**
- a. Why do you think that?
 - b. Has the type of physical activity changed?
- 12. Has your interaction with physical activity related technology (such as Fitbit) changed now that lockdown has been lifted?**
- a. Why do you think that?
 - b. What about checking your PA data through the app?
- 13. Do you feel you have a better relationship with physical activity now than before the Covid-19 lockdown?**
- a. Why do you think that?

Additional Comments from Participants

14. Do you have any other comments you would like to make regarding your physical activity and the Covid-19 lockdown?

I would like to thank you for participating in this interview.

Appendix 5 – Sample of coding/theme generation.

Quote	Initial code/s	Subtheme/s	Theme/s
<p><i>“Yeah, I think it made me realize the, much more than before, the effect it had on my mood. You know, it seemed like having a positive effect. I don't think I was so aware of it for me because I was just busy. But yeah, it kind of became a way of you know, of looking after myself and making sure my mood stayed okay during lockdown.”</i></p>	<p>Fitbit app interaction changed during lockdown</p>	<p>Fitbit interaction</p>	<p>PA during lockdown</p>
<p><i>“Ehm maybe on a Sunday so probably just one walk a week for a couple hours maybe?”</i></p>	<p>Type of PA before lockdown</p> <p>Frequency of PA before lockdown</p>	<p>Type and frequency</p>	<p>PA before lockdown</p>

<p><i>“Ehm I just I've got a Fitbit, so I like to kind of make sure that I do about 10,000 steps a day, most days or at least 70,000 a week on average. So I just like to make sure that I'm kind of active that way.”</i></p>	<p>Opinion on PA tracking</p> <p>Frequency of PA before lockdown</p>	<p>PA tracking</p> <p>Type and frequency</p>	<p>PA monitoring</p> <p>PA before lockdown</p>
<p><i>“Yeah, I think it made me realize the, much more than before, the effect it had on my mood. You know, it seemed like having a positive effect. I don't think I was so aware of it for me because I was just busy. But yeah, it kind of became a way of you know, of looking after myself and making sure my mood stayed okay during lockdown.”</i></p>	<p>Comments of PA and lockdown</p>	<p>General comments</p>	<p>PA after lockdown</p>